

Revisiting Equivalence in Abstract Argumentation (Preprint)

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Abstract

We consider notions of equivalence of abstract argumentation frameworks. In particular, we introduce *serialisation equivalence*, which provides a notion of equivalence that takes the underlying dialectical structure of extensions in an argumentation framework into account. Under this notion, two argumentation frameworks are only considered equivalent if they possess not only the same extensions wrt. some semantics, but also the same serialisation sequences. A serialisation sequence is thereby a decomposition of an extension into a series of minimal acceptable sets. In essence, such a sequence offers insight into the order in which arguments need to be brought forward to resolve the conflicts and to justify a particular position in the argumentation framework. We embed this new notion into a broader landscape of equivalence for abstract argumentation. To this end, we examine established notions of equivalence, namely strong equivalence as well as different variants of expansion and deletion equivalence and contribute missing characterisation results for various semantics under these notions. Subsequently, we thoroughly analyse the relationships between a variety of semantics under these equivalence notions as well as the relationships between different equivalence notions in general. Finally, we provide a full analysis of the computational complexity of deciding all considered equivalence notions in abstract argumentation.

Keywords: knowledge representation, formal argumentation, serialisability, semantics, equivalence, complexity

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1. Introduction

The field of knowledge representation and reasoning is an important area within artificial intelligence (AI) research (Brachman and Levesque, 2004; Bench-Capon and Dunne, 2007). Especially, in light of the recent rise of large language models and other black-box AI approaches, the need for transparent and explainable AI models has grown even more apparent (Leofante et al., 2024).

While there are many promising approaches to knowledge representation and reasoning (van Harmelen et al., 2008; Atkinson et al., 2017), for instance, answer set programming (Lifschitz, 2019), description logics (Baader et al., 2008) or default logics (Reiter, 1980), in this work we will set our focus on the field of *formal argumentation* (Baroni et al., 2018b; Gabbay et al., 2021). Formal argumentation is inspired by human reasoning (Antaki and Leudar, 1992; Miller, 2019), making it particularly well-suited for developing explainable and contestable AI systems (Vassiliades et al., 2021; Leofante et al., 2024). Argumentation-based approaches can either be used directly as an intrinsically explainable system or they can be employed to provide post-hoc explanations for black-box models (Cyras et al., 2021). Moreover, argumentative approaches have found many applications, for instance in law and legal reasoning (Bench-Capon et al., 2009; Prakken and Sartor, 2015; Atkinson et al., 2020).

The (*abstract*) *argumentation frameworks* (AFs) as introduced by Dung (1995) have emerged as one of the major formalisms in knowledge representation and reasoning. An argumentation framework consists of a set of arguments and an attack relation between these arguments and we can simply represent it as a directed graph. Reasoning in abstract argumentation is done via argumentation semantics (Baroni et al., 2018a), which determine sets of arguments (called extensions) that are considered jointly acceptable wrt. different criteria. For instance, the basic property of *admissibility* requires a set to be conflict-free and to defend all of its arguments. Maximal admissible sets are then called *preferred* extensions.

Equivalence is a popular and well-studied topic in the field of knowledge representation, and particularly also in formal argumentation. The non-monotonicity of these approaches makes equivalence a delicate property and gives room for different approaches. Specifically, in non-monotonic settings, adding new information may invalidate previous conclusions. As a consequence, standard semantic equivalence is often too weak to guaran-

tee interchangeability in broader contexts (Lifschitz et al., 2001; Oikarinen and Woltran, 2011). This observation has led to the development of refined equivalence notions that incorporate varying contextual aspects. The seminal work by Lifschitz et al. (2001) introduced strong equivalence for logic programs, while Turner (2001) considered strong equivalence of default and causal theories (Turner, 2004). Oikarinen and Woltran (2011) then introduced strong equivalence for abstract argumentation and, more recently, the connection between strong equivalence in logic programming and abstract argumentation has been examined (Buraglio et al., 2025). Notable is also the work of Baumann and Strass (2022), in which they define an abstract characterisation of strong equivalence for non-monotonic knowledge representation approaches based on logics. Moreover, stronger equivalence notions facilitate accounting for implicit information that is not immediately visible in the AFs (Oikarinen and Woltran, 2011). This aspect is the main motivation behind our novel equivalence notion, as we will outline below. In addition to the above, the study of equivalence gives interesting and valuable insight into the nature of argumentation semantics and their relationships (Baumann, 2018). In particular, the question under which circumstances two argumentation frameworks yield the same extensions wrt. some semantics σ has received considerable attention in the literature (Baroni and Giacomin, 2008; Kuhlmann et al., 2021).

As a form of defeasible reasoning, formal argumentation is inherently linked to dialectics (Hage, 2000; Caminada, 2018). One major aspect of dialectical argumentation is its procedural nature: arguments are followed by counter-arguments (and so on) (Hage, 2000; Rescher, 1977). Although an argumentation framework models this well on the syntactic level, the procedural aspect is somewhat lost in the semantical extensions (Verheij, 1996). In order to adhere to the inherent dialectics that are modelled in formal argumentation, a notion of equivalence between AFs should take into account the underlying argumentation process, i. e., such a notion should respect the order in which the arguments of an extension need to be presented for it to be admissible. In order to address this, we consider the notion of *serialisability* for admissibility-based semantics (Thimm, 2022), which provides a decomposition scheme for extensions into a series of non-empty minimal admissible sets, called serialisation sequences. These serialisation sequences provide a deeper insight into the acceptability than the extension itself. In particular, they provide a view of the order in which the arguments of the extension need to be accepted, highlighting which conflicts in the argumentation framework

need to be resolved before others can be addressed.

From a dialectical perspective, it seems only natural to take the additional information regarding the order of acceptance into account when deciding the equivalence of two AFs. For instance, the AFs in Figure 1 are considered equivalent wrt. preferred semantics under the standard equivalence notion since they both only have the preferred extension $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}\}$. In other words, they have the same semantical conclusion. However, the underlying reasoning is different in both AFs: In \mathcal{F}_1 the argument \mathbf{a} defends \mathbf{c} , while it is the other way around in \mathcal{G}_1 . Hence, from a dialectical point of view, we would actually not want to consider them equivalent.

Figure 1: The AFs \mathcal{F}_1 and \mathcal{G}_1 which are equivalent wrt. preferred semantics.

A stricter equivalence notion is needed to distinguish the AFs \mathcal{F}_1 and \mathcal{G}_1 from above. One prominent approach to distinguish these kinds of AFs is *strong equivalence* (Oikarinen and Woltran, 2011), where two AFs \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are only considered equivalent if they possess the same extensions after being conjoined with some arbitrary AF \mathcal{H} (see Section 2.3 for the formal definitions). For that reason, the AFs in Figure 1 are not strongly equivalent wrt. preferred semantics (imagine adding a new argument that attacks \mathbf{a} , which yields different preferred extensions for \mathcal{F}_1 and \mathcal{G}_1). Note however, strong equivalence does not actually consider the underlying process in order to distinguish two AFs. This becomes apparent in the following example. The strictness of strong equivalence notion means that, for instance, the AFs \mathcal{F}_2 and \mathcal{G}_2 from Figure 2 are not strongly equivalent wrt. preferred semantics, even though they can reasonably be considered equivalent. Both frameworks have \mathbf{a} defending \mathbf{d} against \mathbf{b} and \mathbf{c} , with the only difference being the two attacks between the always rejected arguments \mathbf{b} and \mathbf{c} . From a dialectical point of view, these attacks are insignificant as they do not influence the acceptable sets of arguments, and so we would want to consider these AFs to be equivalent. In particular, one might argue that the underlying reasoning behind the only preferred conclusion $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{d}\}$ is the same in both \mathcal{F}_2 and \mathcal{G}_2 : \mathbf{a} refutes both \mathbf{b} and \mathbf{c} and thus makes \mathbf{d} acceptable.

Figure 2: The AFs \mathcal{F}_2 and \mathcal{G}_2 which are not strongly equivalent wrt. preferred semantics.

In this work, we will consider equivalence notions in abstract argumentation in detail. Beyond *standard* and *strong equivalence* (Oikarinen and Woltran, 2011) there exists several other equivalence notions in the literature, see Baumann and Brewka (2018). Specifically the different notions of *expansion equivalence* (Baumann, 2012a) and *deletion equivalence* (Baumann, 2014a) will be considered in detail over the course of this work. Note that there are also various works that consider equivalence in other argumentation formalisms, namely in argumentation frameworks with collective attacks (Dvorák et al., 2019), claim-augmented argumentation frameworks (Baumann et al., 2023), structured argumentation frameworks (Rapberger and Ulbricht, 2023) as well as abstract dialectical frameworks (Heyninck et al., 2022).

Let us briefly outline our contributions in this work in more detail. Our main goal is to establish the notion of serialisation equivalence, situate it in the landscape of equivalences, and provide a comprehensive overview of equivalence in abstract argumentation. Serialisation equivalence provides a stronger notion of equivalence than the standard equivalence notion, by incorporating the additional implicit information about the order of argument acceptance and the order of conflict resolution within an extension. Specifically, serialisation equivalence provides a notion to compare argumentation frameworks based on the actual underlying reasoning that they represent and not only whether they come to the same semantical conclusions. We then also investigate the relationships between different admissibility-based semantics under serialisation equivalence.

Furthermore, we examine the relations between serialisation equivalence and numerous equivalence notions from the literature, including standard and strong equivalence. In particular, our results show that serialisation

equivalence is generally situated between standard equivalence on one hand and strong equivalence as well as most expansion and deletion equivalences on the other hand. We also provide missing characterisation results for the existing equivalence notions and complete the analysis of the relations between semantics under these equivalence notions. Consequently, our work contributes a comprehensive survey of equivalence notions in abstract argumentation and can be considered as an extension of the work of Baumann and Brewka (2018).

Finally, we analyse all equivalence notions, including our novel serialisation equivalence, in terms of complexity. As it turns out, deciding serialisation equivalence is typically as hard as deciding standard equivalence, while simultaneously providing a more fine-grained notion of equivalence.

To summarise, the main contributions of this work are as follows:

1. We establish missing characterisation results for various variants of expansion equivalence and deletion equivalence and investigate semantical relations under these equivalence notions (Section 3).
2. We characterise serialisation equivalence and investigate the relations between the equivalence wrt. different semantics and examine in detail its relation to other equivalence notions from the literature (Section 4).
3. We provide a comprehensive overview over the landscape of equivalence notions wrt. a wide variety of admissibility-based semantics (Section 5).
4. We analyse the computational complexity of deciding serialisation equivalence in comparison the other equivalence notions (Section 6).

In Section 2 we recall the necessary background on abstract argumentation, serialisability and equivalence from the literature. Section 7 concludes the paper. The proofs of all technical results can be found in the appendix.

Disclaimer. *This work is based on the conference publication (Bengel et al., 2024) published at ECAI 2024. In that paper, we introduced serialisation equivalence and investigated its relation only to standard and strong equivalence. We also considered the computational complexity of deciding serialisation equivalence.*

In this work, we expand on this significantly by considering further equivalence notions from the literature, namely the variants of expansion equivalence (Oikarinen and Woltran, 2011; Baumann, 2012a) and the variants of deletion equivalence (Baumann, 2014a). We fully characterise the relation of serialisation equivalence to these equivalence notions and also provide a

comprehensive overview over the relationship for a total of eleven equivalence notions and ten semantics. In light of this, we also include missing characterisation results, in particular for equivalences wrt. strong admissibility, and complete the complexity results for expansion and deletion equivalences.

2. Background

In Section 2.1 we introduce the relevant background on abstract argumentation. In Section 2.2 we recall the notion of serialisability for argumentation semantics upon which we build our novel semantical equivalence notion and in Section 2.3 we recall the different equivalence notions from the literature that we consider in this work.

2.1. Abstract Argumentation

We consider *abstract argumentation frameworks* due to Dung (1995).

Definition 2.1. An (*abstract*) *argumentation framework* (AF) is a tuple $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ where \mathcal{A} is a finite set of arguments and \mathcal{R} is a relation $\mathcal{R} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{A}$.

With \mathbb{A} we denote the universal set of arguments and \mathbb{AF} denotes the set of all abstract argumentation frameworks. For two arguments $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{A}$, the relation $\mathbf{a}\mathcal{R}\mathbf{b}$ means that \mathbf{a} attacks \mathbf{b} . For a set $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ we also define

$$S_{\mathcal{F}}^{\pm} = \{\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A} \mid \exists \mathbf{b} \in S : \mathbf{b}\mathcal{R}\mathbf{a}\}, \quad S_{\mathcal{F}}^{-} = \{\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A} \mid \exists \mathbf{b} \in S : \mathbf{a}\mathcal{R}\mathbf{b}\}.$$

For a singleton set $\{\mathbf{a}\}$, we omit brackets for readability, i. e., we write $\mathbf{a}_{\mathcal{F}}^{-}$ ($\mathbf{a}_{\mathcal{F}}^{\pm}$), and we omit the reference to \mathcal{F} , when obvious from context. For two sets S and S' we write $S\mathcal{R}S'$ iff $S' \cap S_{\mathcal{F}}^{\pm} \neq \emptyset$. We say that a set $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ is *conflict-free* iff for all $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in S$ we have that $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}$. We denote with $\text{cf}(\mathcal{F})$ the conflict-free sets of \mathcal{F} . A set S *defends* an argument $\mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{A}$ iff for all \mathbf{a} with $\mathbf{a}\mathcal{R}\mathbf{b}$ there is $\mathbf{c} \in S$ with $\mathbf{c}\mathcal{R}\mathbf{a}$. Furthermore, a set S is called *admissible* (**ad**) iff it is conflict-free and S defends all $\mathbf{a} \in S$. We denote with $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F})$ the admissible sets of \mathcal{F} .

In this work, we consider a wide variety of admissibility-based semantics for abstract argumentation. The semantics for argumentation frameworks are defined as functions $\sigma : \mathbb{AF} \mapsto 2^{\mathbb{A}}$, which assign to some argumentation framework $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ a set of extensions. In particular, we consider $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{gr}, \text{pr}, \text{st}, \text{id}, \text{sst}, \text{ea}, \text{sa}\}$ for the complete, grounded, preferred, stable extensions (Dung, 1995), as well as the ideal (Dung et al., 2007), semi-stable (Verheij, 1996; Caminada, 2006), eager extensions (Caminada, 2007)

and strongly admissible sets (Baroni and Giacomin, 2007; Caminada, 2014), respectively. The extensions for these semantics are defined as follows.

Definition 2.2. Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF. An admissible set $E \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ is a

- *complete* (co) extension iff for all $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}$, if E defends \mathbf{a} then $\mathbf{a} \in E$,
- *grounded* (gr) extension iff E is complete and there is no complete E' with $E' \subsetneq E$,
- *preferred* (pr) extension iff there is no admissible E' with $E \subsetneq E'$,
- *stable* (st) extension iff $E \cup E^+ = \mathcal{A}$,
- *strongly admissible* (sa) set iff $E = \emptyset$ or each $\mathbf{a} \in E$ is defended by some strongly admissible $E' \subseteq E \setminus \{\mathbf{a}\}$,
- *ideal* (id) extension iff $E \subseteq \bigcap_{E' \in \text{pr}(\mathcal{F})} E'$ and there is no admissible E'' with $E'' \subseteq \bigcap_{E' \in \text{pr}(\mathcal{F})} E'$ and $E \subsetneq E''$,
- *semi-stable* (sst) extension iff E is complete and there is no complete E' with $E \cup E^+ \subsetneq E' \cup E'^+$,
- *eager* (ea) extension iff $E \subseteq \bigcap_{E' \in \text{sst}(\mathcal{F})} E'$ and there is no admissible E'' with $E'' \subseteq \bigcap_{E' \in \text{sst}(\mathcal{F})} E'$ and $E \subsetneq E''$.

Figure 3: The AF \mathcal{F}_3 from Examples 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4 and 2.5.

Example 2.1. Consider the AF \mathcal{F}_3 depicted in Figure 3. We have that $\{\mathbf{a}\}$, $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{d}\}$, $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}\}$ and $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{e}\}$ are the complete extensions of \mathcal{F}_3 . The former is also the unique grounded and ideal extension, while $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{d}\}$ and $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{e}\}$ are \subseteq -maximal and thus the two preferred extensions of \mathcal{F}_3 . However, only $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{e}\}$ is a stable extension of \mathcal{F}_3 , because $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{d}\}$ does neither attack nor include \mathbf{f} . $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{e}\}$ is then also the only semi-stable and thus eager extension of \mathcal{F}_3 . Finally, the empty set and $\{\mathbf{a}\}$ are the only strongly admissible sets of \mathcal{F}_3 .

To further facilitate working with argumentation frameworks, we consider some additional notions. For a set $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, we denote by $\mathcal{F}|_S = (S, \mathcal{R} \cap (S \times S))$ the *projection* of \mathcal{F} on S . Based on that, we recall the *reduct* of Baumann et al. (2020), which for some set S removes from an argumentation framework all arguments contained in S or attacked by S .

Definition 2.3. For $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ and $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, the *S-reduct* \mathcal{F}^S is defined via $\mathcal{F}^S = \mathcal{F}|_{\mathcal{A} \setminus (S \cup S^+)}$.

Furthermore, for two argumentation frameworks $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ and $\mathcal{F}' = (\mathcal{A}', \mathcal{R}')$, we define the *union* as $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{F}' = (\mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{A}', \mathcal{R} \cup \mathcal{R}')$. Additionally, if \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{F}' possess the same arguments and attacks, we call them syntactically identical, also written as $\mathcal{F} \doteq \mathcal{F}'$. An argument \mathbf{a} with $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}$ is also called self-attacking. If for two arguments \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} there is a sequence $(\mathbf{a}_1, \dots, \mathbf{a}_n)$ with $\mathbf{a}_1 = \mathbf{a}$, $\mathbf{a}_n = \mathbf{b}$, $(\mathbf{a}_n, \mathbf{a}_1)$ and $(\mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{a}_{i+1}) \in \mathcal{R}$ for all $i < n$ and n is odd, then that is considered an *odd cycle*.

2.2. Serialisability in Abstract Argumentation

We consider the notion of serialisability of semantics (Thimm, 2022), which yields a sequence-based representation for extensions. For that, we first recall non-empty minimal admissible sets, which have been coined *initial sets* by Xu and Cayrol (2016, 2018).

Definition 2.4. For $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$, a set $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ with $S \neq \emptyset$ is called an *initial set* if S is admissible and there is no admissible $S' \subsetneq S$ with $S' \neq \emptyset$.

Example 2.2. We continue Example 2.1 and consider again the AF \mathcal{F}_3 depicted in Figure 3. We have two initial sets $\{\mathbf{a}\}$ and $\{\mathbf{d}\}$. While \mathbf{a} is not attacked at all, \mathbf{d} is attacked by \mathbf{c} , but defends itself. Clearly, since both sets contain only one argument they are \subseteq -minimal among the non-empty admissible sets.

With $\text{is}(\mathcal{F})$ we denote the set of initial sets of \mathcal{F} . We differentiate between three types of initial sets (Thimm, 2022).

Definition 2.5. For $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ and $S \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F})$, we say that

1. S is *unattacked* iff $S^- = \emptyset$,
2. S is *unchallenged* iff $S^- \neq \emptyset$ and there is no $S' \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F})$ with $S' \mathcal{R} S$,
3. S is *challenged* iff there is $S' \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F})$ with $S' \mathcal{R} S$.

In the following, we denote with $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F})$, $\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F})$, and $\text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F})$ the set of unattacked, unchallenged, and challenged initial sets, respectively.

Example 2.3. We continue Example 2.2 and consider again the AF \mathcal{F}_3 depicted in Figure 3. We have that $\text{is}(\mathcal{F}_3) = \{\{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{d}\}\}$. The set $\{\mathbf{a}\}$ is clearly an unattacked initial set, because \mathbf{a} is not attacked in \mathcal{F}_3 . On the other hand, $\{\mathbf{d}\}$ is an unchallenged initial set, because it is attacked by \mathbf{c} , but \mathbf{c} is not contained in any initial set of \mathcal{F}_3 . Consider now the reduct $\mathcal{F}_3^{\{\mathbf{a}\}}$, i. e., we remove \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} from \mathcal{F}_3 . In this AF, we have two initial sets, namely $\{\mathbf{c}\}$ and $\{\mathbf{d}\}$. Both attack each other and thus they are both challenged initial sets of $\mathcal{F}_3^{\{\mathbf{a}\}}$.

Now admissible sets can be represented as a series of initial sets of the respective reducts, called *serialisation sequences* (Blümel and Thimm, 2022).

Definition 2.6. A *serialisation sequence* for $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ is a sequence $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n)$ with $S_1 \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F})$ and for each $2 \leq i \leq n$ we have that $S_i \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}})$.

We denote with $\hat{\mathcal{S}} = S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n$ the admissible set induced by a serialisation sequence $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n)$. As shown in (Blümel and Thimm, 2022), a serialisation sequence induces exactly one admissible set and for every admissible set there is at least one such sequence.

Example 2.4. We continue Example 2.3 and consider again the AF \mathcal{F}_3 in Figure 3. We can use serialisability to iteratively construct an admissible set, represented in the form of a serialisation sequence. Recall that we have $\text{is}(\mathcal{F}_3) = \{\{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{d}\}\}$. Let $S_1 = \{\mathbf{a}\}$. Then, in the reduct $\mathcal{F}_3^{\{\mathbf{a}\}}$, we now have $\text{is}(\mathcal{F}_3^{\{\mathbf{a}\}}) = \{\{\mathbf{c}\}, \{\mathbf{d}\}\}$. Let $S_2 = \{\mathbf{c}\}$. Finally, in the reduct $\mathcal{F}_3^{\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}\}}$, we only have the initial set $\{\mathbf{e}\}$. Selecting that gives us the serialisation sequence $\mathcal{S}_1 = (\{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{c}\}, \{\mathbf{e}\})$, which implicitly tells us the order in which the arguments of the corresponding admissible set $\hat{\mathcal{S}}_1 = \{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{e}\}$ are accepted. Note that the sub-sequences $(\{\mathbf{a}\})$ or $(\{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{c}\})$ are also serialisation sequences of \mathcal{F}_3 . Furthermore, $(\{\mathbf{d}\})$, $(\{\mathbf{d}\}, \{\mathbf{a}\})$ and $(\{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{d}\})$ are serialisation sequences of \mathcal{F}_3 .

Utilising the distinction between initial sets from Definition 2.5, one can further restrict the serialisation sequences to characterise a wide variety of admissibility-based semantics (Thimm, 2022).

Theorem 2.1. Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an argumentation framework and $E \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. We have that:

- $E \in \mathbf{ad}(\mathcal{F})$ if and only if there is a serialisation sequence (S_1, \dots, S_n) with $E = S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n$.
- $E \in \mathbf{co}(\mathcal{F})$ if and only if there is a serialisation sequence (S_1, \dots, S_n) with $E = S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n$ and it holds that $\mathbf{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n}) = \emptyset$.
- $E \in \mathbf{pr}(\mathcal{F})$ if and only if there is a serialisation sequence (S_1, \dots, S_n) with $E = S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n$ and it holds that $\mathbf{is}(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n}) = \emptyset$.
- $E \in \mathbf{sa}(\mathcal{F})$ if and only if there is a serialisation sequence (S_1, \dots, S_n) with $E = S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n$ and for all S_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$, it holds that $S_i \in \mathbf{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}})$.
- $E \in \mathbf{gr}(\mathcal{F})$ if and only if there is a serialisation sequence (S_1, \dots, S_n) with $E = S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n$ and for all S_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$, it holds that $S_i \in \mathbf{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}})$ and it holds that $\mathbf{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n}) = \emptyset$.
- $E \in \mathbf{st}(\mathcal{F})$ if and only if there is a serialisation sequence (S_1, \dots, S_n) with $E = S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n$ and it holds that $\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n} = (\emptyset, \emptyset)$.

Furthermore, we also consider the unchallenged (**uc**) semantics (Thimm, 2022; Bengel and Thimm, 2022), which is directly defined in terms of serialisation sequences.

Definition 2.7. Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF and $E \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. Then $E \in \mathbf{uc}(\mathcal{F})$ if and only if there is a serialisation sequence (S_1, \dots, S_n) with $E = S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n$ and for all S_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$, it holds that $S_i \in \mathbf{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}}) \cup \mathbf{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}})$ and it holds that $\mathbf{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n}) \cup \mathbf{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n}) = \emptyset$.

For an argumentation framework \mathcal{F} , we denote with $\mathfrak{S}_\sigma(\mathcal{F})$ the set of all σ -serialisation sequences of \mathcal{F} .

Example 2.5. We continue Example 2.4 and consider again the AF \mathcal{F}_3 in Figure 3. For the complete semantics, we have the **co**-serialisation sequences $(\{\mathbf{a}\})$, $(\{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{c}\})$, $(\{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{d}\})$, $(\{\mathbf{d}\}, \{\mathbf{a}\})$ and $(\{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{c}\}, \{\mathbf{e}\})$. In particular, $(\{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{d}\})$ and $(\{\mathbf{d}\}, \{\mathbf{a}\})$ correspond to the same **co**-extension, representing two different way to arrive there, while for the other **co**-extensions only a single order of construction exists. The latter three sequences are also **pr**-serialisation sequences. Finally, only $(\{\mathbf{a}\})$ and $(\{\mathbf{d}\}, \{\mathbf{a}\})$ are **uc**-serialisation sequences.

Note that all other semantics from Definition 2.2, namely `id`, `sst` and `ea`, are not serialisable (Thimm, 2022). In the context of this work we treat `ad` to be a semantics itself and denote with $\Sigma = \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{pr}, \text{sa}, \text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{uc}, \text{id}, \text{sst}, \text{ea}\}$ the set of all semantics. Moreover, denote with $\Sigma_s = \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{pr}, \text{sa}, \text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{uc}\}$ the set of *serialisable* semantics, as described in Theorem 2.1 and Definition 2.7.

2.3. Equivalence in Abstract Argumentation

We now turn to different notions of semantical equivalence for argumentation frameworks that have been introduced in the literature (Oikarinen and Woltran, 2011; Baumann, 2018; Baumann and Brewka, 2018).

Standard Equivalence. First, we consider *standard equivalence* wrt. some semantics σ , which is simply defined via the equivalence of the set of σ -extensions.

Definition 2.8. Let \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. We say that \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are *equivalent* to each other wrt. a semantics σ , written as $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma} \mathcal{G}$, if and only if we have that $\sigma(\mathcal{F}) = \sigma(\mathcal{G})$.

Example 2.6. Consider the AFs \mathcal{F}_1 and \mathcal{G}_1 in Figure 1. We have that $\mathcal{F}_1 \equiv_{\text{pr}} \mathcal{G}_1$, since $\text{pr}(\mathcal{F}_1) = \text{pr}(\mathcal{G}_1) = \{\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}\}\}$. On the other hand, we have $\mathcal{F}_1 \not\equiv_{\text{ad}} \mathcal{G}_1$ since $\{\mathbf{a}\} \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F}_1)$ and $\{\mathbf{a}\} \notin \text{ad}(\mathcal{G}_1)$.

Strong Equivalence. A more restrictive approach to equivalence is provided by the notion of *strong equivalence* wrt. some semantics σ . It was originally introduced with the intention of providing a notion of equivalence in a dynamic argumentation scenario (Oikarinen and Woltran, 2011). Intuitively, strong equivalence requires that both argumentation frameworks are still equivalent after being conjoined with another framework \mathcal{H} .

Definition 2.9. Let \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. We say that \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are *strongly equivalent* to each other wrt. a semantics σ , written as $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^s \mathcal{G}$, if and only if for every argumentation framework \mathcal{H} , we have that $\sigma(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \sigma(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$.

To facilitate deciding strong equivalence wrt. a semantics σ , so called *kernels* have been introduced, which remove semantically redundant attacks

from an AF (Oikarinen and Woltran, 2011). The different kernels $\kappa \in \{\text{s}\kappa, \text{a}\kappa, \text{g}\kappa, \text{c}\kappa\}$ of an AF $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ are defined as $\mathcal{F}^\kappa = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}^\kappa)$, with

$$\mathcal{R}^{\text{s}\kappa} = \mathcal{R} \setminus \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \mid \mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{b}, (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}\} \quad (1)$$

$$\mathcal{R}^{\text{a}\kappa} = \mathcal{R} \setminus \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \mid \mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{b}, (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}, \{(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}), (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b})\} \cap \mathcal{R} \neq \emptyset\} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathcal{R}^{\text{g}\kappa} = \mathcal{R} \setminus \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \mid \mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{b}, (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}, \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}), (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a})\} \cap \mathcal{R} \neq \emptyset\} \quad (3)$$

$$\mathcal{R}^{\text{c}\kappa} = \mathcal{R} \setminus \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \mid \mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{b}, (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}, (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}\} \quad (4)$$

As the following theorem shows, strong equivalence can be characterised by kernel identity. That also means that strong equivalence is ultimately a syntactic equivalence notion since it can be decided purely based on syntactic criteria.

Theorem 2.2 (Oikarinen and Woltran, 2011). *Let \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that*

1. $\mathcal{F}^{\text{s}\kappa} \doteq \mathcal{G}^{\text{s}\kappa}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{st}}^{\text{s}} \mathcal{G}$,
2. $\mathcal{F}^{\text{a}\kappa} \doteq \mathcal{G}^{\text{a}\kappa}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{s}} \mathcal{G}$ for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{pr}, \text{id}, \text{sst}, \text{ea}\}$,
3. $\mathcal{F}^{\text{g}\kappa} \doteq \mathcal{G}^{\text{g}\kappa}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{gr}}^{\text{s}} \mathcal{G}$,
4. $\mathcal{F}^{\text{c}\kappa} \doteq \mathcal{G}^{\text{c}\kappa}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{co}}^{\text{s}} \mathcal{G}$.

As a side product of the above, we have that the σ -extensions of an AF and its respective kernel framework are the same.

Corollary 2.1. *Let \mathcal{F} be an argumentation framework. It holds that*

1. $\text{st}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{st}(\mathcal{F}^{\text{s}\kappa})$,
2. $\sigma(\mathcal{F}) = \sigma(\mathcal{F}^{\text{a}\kappa})$, for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{pr}, \text{id}, \text{sst}, \text{ea}\}$,
3. $\sigma(\mathcal{F}) = \sigma(\mathcal{F}^{\text{g}\kappa})$, for $\sigma \in \{\text{gr}\}$,
4. $\text{co}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{co}(\mathcal{F}^{\text{c}\kappa})$.

Figure 4: The AFs \mathcal{F}_4 and \mathcal{G}_4 and their ad-kernel framework.

Example 2.7. Consider the AFs \mathcal{F}_4 and \mathcal{G}_4 in Figure 4. For admissibility, the kernel $\mathcal{F}_4^{\text{a}\kappa}$ of \mathcal{F}_4 removes only the attack (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}) , as depicted in Figure 4. For the $\text{a}\kappa$ -kernel $\mathcal{G}_4^{\text{a}\kappa}$ of \mathcal{G}_4 , we remove the attack (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) from \mathcal{G}_4 , thus we have that $\mathcal{F}_4^{\text{a}\kappa} \doteq \mathcal{G}_4^{\text{a}\kappa}$ and it follows that $\mathcal{F}_4 \equiv_{\text{ad}}^{\text{s}} \mathcal{G}_4$. The same holds true for the stable semantics, i.e., we have $\mathcal{F}_4 \equiv_{\text{st}}^{\text{s}} \mathcal{G}_4$. Conversely, we have that $\mathcal{F}_4 \not\equiv_{\text{gr}}^{\text{s}} \mathcal{G}_4$, since $\mathcal{F}_4^{\text{g}\kappa} = (\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}\}, \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}), (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}), (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c})\})$ and $\mathcal{G}_4^{\text{g}\kappa} = (\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}\}, \{(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}), (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}), (\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{b})\})$.

Expansion Equivalences. Strong equivalence considers arbitrary expansions of the AFs \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} , i.e., any argument or attack may be added in the expansion. However, as shown by Baumann and Brewka (2010), there exist several types of reasonable expansions that allow only certain modifications to the AFs.

Definition 2.10. An AF \mathcal{F}^* is an *expansion* of the AF $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$, written as $\mathcal{F} \preceq \mathcal{F}^*$, if and only if $\mathcal{F}^* = (\mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{A}^*, \mathcal{R} \cup \mathcal{R}^*)$, such that $\mathcal{A}^* \cap \mathcal{A} = \mathcal{R}^* \cap \mathcal{R} = \emptyset$ holds. Such an expansion \mathcal{F}^* is called

1. *normal* ($\mathcal{F} \preceq^N \mathcal{F}^*$) iff $\mathcal{A}^* \neq \emptyset \wedge \forall \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} : [(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}^* \rightarrow (\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}^* \vee \mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{A}^*)]$,
2. *strong* ($\mathcal{F} \preceq_S^N \mathcal{F}^*$) iff $\mathcal{F} \preceq^N \mathcal{F}^* \wedge \forall \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} : [(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}^* \rightarrow (\mathbf{a} \notin \mathcal{A} \vee \mathbf{b} \notin \mathcal{A}^*)]$,
3. *weak* ($\mathcal{F} \preceq_W^N \mathcal{F}^*$) iff $\mathcal{F} \preceq^N \mathcal{F}^* \wedge \forall \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} : [(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}^* \rightarrow (\mathbf{a} \notin \mathcal{A}^* \vee \mathbf{b} \notin \mathcal{A})]$,
4. *local* ($\mathcal{F} \preceq^L \mathcal{F}^*$) iff $\mathcal{A}^* = \emptyset$.

Intuitively, in normal expansions new arguments are added and any new attack must concern at least one new argument. Strong expansions are normal and the newly added arguments can never be attacked by former arguments. Conversely, weak expansions are also normal and the new arguments never attack former arguments. Finally, in a local expansion only new attacks may be added.

Figure 5: The AFs \mathcal{F}_5 , \mathcal{G}_5 , \mathcal{H}_5 and \mathcal{I}_5 from Example 2.8, representing different types of expansions, highlighted with dashed outlines.

Example 2.8. Consider the AFs in Figure 5, which illustrate the different types of expansions defined above. In particular, we have the original AF $\mathcal{F} = (\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}\}, \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}), (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b})\})$ and \mathcal{F}_5 is a normal expansion of \mathcal{F} . Similarly, it holds that $\mathcal{F} \preceq_S^N \mathcal{G}_5$ and $\mathcal{F} \preceq_S^N \mathcal{H}_5$. Note that by definition \mathcal{G}_5 and \mathcal{H}_5 are also normal expansions of \mathcal{F} . Finally, \mathcal{I}_5 is a local expansion of \mathcal{F} . In contrast to that, \mathcal{G}_4 in Figure 4 does not satisfy the conditions for any type of expansion and is therefore just an arbitrary expansion of \mathcal{F} .

We can use the different types of expansions to define a corresponding notion of expansion equivalence (Baumann, 2012a; Baumann and Brewka, 2018). Note that the notion of local expansion equivalence has also been introduced by Oikarinen and Woltran (2011) under the name local equivalence. In this context, strong equivalence is also referred to as (arbitrary) expansion equivalence (Baumann, 2012a). We will however use the original name, since it is better known.

Definition 2.11. Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}})$ and $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}})$ be argumentation frameworks and σ is a semantics. We say that \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are

1. *normal expansion equivalent* wrt. σ ($\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^n \mathcal{G}$) iff for each AF \mathcal{H} such that $\mathcal{F} \preceq_N \mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ and $\mathcal{G} \preceq_N \mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$, it holds that $\sigma(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \sigma(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$,
2. *strong expansion equivalent* wrt. σ ($\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$) iff for each AF \mathcal{H} such that $\mathcal{F} \preceq_S \mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ and $\mathcal{G} \preceq_S \mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$, it holds that $\sigma(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \sigma(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$,
3. *weak expansion equivalent* wrt. σ ($\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{G}$) iff for each AF \mathcal{H} such that $\mathcal{F} \preceq_W \mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ and $\mathcal{G} \preceq_W \mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$, it holds that $\sigma(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \sigma(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$,
4. *local expansion equivalent* wrt. σ ($\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^l \mathcal{G}$) iff for each AF $\mathcal{H} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{H}})$ such that $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}} \subseteq \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cup \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$, it holds that $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H} \equiv_{\sigma} \mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$.

Similar to how it has been done for strong equivalence, Baumann (2012a) introduced kernels that characterise strong expansion equivalence wrt. admissible, preferred, ideal, complete and grounded semantics. These kernels $\kappa \in \{\mathbf{a}\kappa^*, \mathbf{g}\kappa^*, \mathbf{c}\kappa^*\}$ of an AF $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ are defined as $\mathcal{F}^{\kappa} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}^{\kappa})$, with

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}^{\mathbf{a}\kappa^*} &= \mathcal{R} \setminus \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \mid \mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{b}, ((\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R} \wedge \{(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}), (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b})\} \cap \mathcal{R} \neq \emptyset) \\ &\quad \vee [(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R} \wedge \forall \mathbf{c}((\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}) \in \mathcal{R} \rightarrow \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}), (\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{a}), (\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{c}), (\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{b})\} \cap \mathcal{R} \neq \emptyset)]\}, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}^{\mathbf{g}\kappa^*} &= \mathcal{R} \setminus \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \mid \mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{b}, ((\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R} \wedge \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}), (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a})\} \cap \mathcal{R} \neq \emptyset) \\ &\quad \vee [(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R} \wedge \forall \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}) \in \mathcal{R} \rightarrow \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}), (\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{a}), (\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{c})\} \cap \mathcal{R} \neq \emptyset)]\}, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}^{\mathbf{c}\kappa^*} &= \mathcal{R} \setminus \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \mid \mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{b}, ((\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}, (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}) \\ &\quad \vee [(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R} \wedge (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R} \wedge \forall \mathbf{c}((\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}) \in \mathcal{R} \rightarrow \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}), (\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{a}), (\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{c})\} \cap \mathcal{R} \neq \emptyset)]\}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Note that there is no new kernel for strong expansion equivalence wrt. stable semantics since this is already characterised by the $\mathfrak{s}\kappa$ -kernel. Similarly, strong expansion equivalence wrt. semi-stable and eager semantics is characterised by the $\mathfrak{a}\kappa$ -kernel.

Theorem 2.3 (Baumann, 2012a). *Let \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that*

1. $\mathcal{F}^{\mathfrak{s}\kappa} \doteq \mathcal{G}^{\mathfrak{s}\kappa}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{st}}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$,
2. $\mathcal{F}^{\mathfrak{a}\kappa} \doteq \mathcal{G}^{\mathfrak{a}\kappa}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{\text{sst}, \text{ea}\}$,
3. $\mathcal{F}^{\mathfrak{a}\kappa*} \doteq \mathcal{G}^{\mathfrak{a}\kappa*}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{pr}, \text{id}\}$,
4. $\mathcal{F}^{\mathfrak{g}\kappa*} \doteq \mathcal{G}^{\mathfrak{g}\kappa*}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{gr}}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$,
5. $\mathcal{F}^{\mathfrak{c}\kappa*} \doteq \mathcal{G}^{\mathfrak{c}\kappa*}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{co}}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$.

Corollary 2.2. *Let \mathcal{F} be an argumentation framework. It holds that*

1. $\sigma(\mathcal{F}) = \sigma(\mathcal{F}^{\mathfrak{a}\kappa*})$, for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{pr}, \text{id}\}$,
2. $\text{gr}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{gr}(\mathcal{F}^{\mathfrak{g}\kappa*})$,
3. $\text{co}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{co}(\mathcal{F}^{\mathfrak{c}\kappa*})$.

Figure 6: The AFs \mathcal{F}_6 , \mathcal{G}_6 and \mathcal{H}_6 from Example 2.9.

Example 2.9. Consider the AFs \mathcal{F}_6 , \mathcal{G}_6 and \mathcal{H}_6 in Figure 6. We have that $\mathcal{F}_6 \equiv_{\text{ad}}^1 \mathcal{G}_6$, while $\mathcal{F}_6 \not\equiv_{\text{co}}^1 \mathcal{G}_6$. For that, examine the local expansion of both AFs via $\mathcal{R}^* = \{(b, c)\}$. In the local expansion of \mathcal{F}_6 , we now have $\{b\}$ as the unique complete extension, while for the local expansion of \mathcal{G}_6 , we have both \emptyset and $\{b\}$ as complete extensions. In contrast to that, \emptyset and $\{b\}$ are the only admissible sets for both expanded AFs. Moreover, the reader may verify that the admissible sets of both AFs are equivalent under any possible local expansion.

Similarly, we have that $\mathcal{F}_6 \equiv_{\text{pr}}^1 \mathcal{G}_6$, which may be verified by considering the $\mathfrak{a}\kappa^*$ -kernels of both AFs. In particular, for both AFs, the $\mathfrak{a}\kappa^*$ -kernel

contains only the self attack (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) , while all other attacks are removed, cf. Equation (5). On the other hand, \mathcal{H}_6 is not strong expansion equivalent wrt. preferred semantics to \mathcal{F}_6 or \mathcal{G}_6 .

For any semantics, the notion of normal expansion equivalence coincides with the corresponding strong equivalence notion wrt. the same semantics σ (Baumann, 2012a). The characterisation of local expansion equivalence partially relies on the above introduced kernels, but usually requires some additional conditions, see Oikarinen and Woltran (2011) for more details. Finally, weak expansion equivalence has been characterised semantically and only for some semantics (Baumann, 2011; Baumann and Brewka, 2018).

Deletion Equivalences. Complementary to expansions, Baumann (2014a) introduced the general notion of *updates* and, in particular, *deletions* of AFs.

Definition 2.12. Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF, \mathcal{A}^* is a set of arguments, \mathcal{R}^* a set of attacks. Given some AF \mathcal{H} , then the AF

$$\mathcal{F}^* = \left((\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R} \setminus \mathcal{R}^*)|_{\mathcal{A} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*} \right) \sqcup \mathcal{H}$$

is called an *update* of \mathcal{F} , written as $\mathcal{F} \succ_U \mathcal{F}^*$. Such an update is called a

1. *deletion* ($\mathcal{F} \succeq_D \mathcal{F}^*$) iff $\mathcal{H} = (\emptyset, \emptyset)$,
2. *normal deletion* ($\mathcal{F} \succeq_{ND} \mathcal{F}^*$) iff $\mathcal{F} \succeq_D \mathcal{F}^*$ and $\mathcal{R}^* = \emptyset$,
3. *local deletion* ($\mathcal{F} \succeq_{LD} \mathcal{F}^*$) iff $\mathcal{F} \succeq_D \mathcal{F}^*$ and $\mathcal{A}^* = \emptyset$.

Essentially, an update is a general modification of an argumentation framework, encompassing both expansions and deletions, i. e., arguments and attacks can be added and removed. The AF \mathcal{H} here represents the expansion part and thus for all types of deletions \mathcal{H} must be empty. The set \mathcal{A}^* contains the arguments that are deleted, and naturally all the attacks related to it must be removed (ensured by the projection of \mathcal{F} onto $\mathcal{A} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*$). Consequently, in a normal deletion, we only delete attacks if one of its arguments is deleted. Finally, in a local deletion only attacks may be deleted.

We can then again define the corresponding equivalence notions for updates and deletions.

Definition 2.13. Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}})$ and $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}})$ be argumentation frameworks and σ is a semantics. We say that \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are

1. *update equivalent* wrt. σ ($\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^u \mathcal{G}$) iff for each pair $[\mathcal{A}^*, \mathcal{R}^*]$ and each AF \mathcal{H} it holds that $\sigma((\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{R}^*)|_{\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \sigma((\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}} \setminus \mathcal{R}^*)|_{\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$,
2. *deletion equivalent* wrt. σ ($\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^d \mathcal{G}$) iff for each pair $[\mathcal{A}^*, \mathcal{R}^*]$ it holds that $\sigma((\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{R}^*)|_{\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*}) = \sigma((\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}} \setminus \mathcal{R}^*)|_{\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*})$,
3. *normal deletion equivalent* wrt. σ ($\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{nd}} \mathcal{G}$) iff for each set \mathcal{A}^* it holds that $\sigma(\mathcal{F}|_{\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*}) = \sigma(\mathcal{G}|_{\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*})$,
4. *local deletion equivalent* wrt. σ ($\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{ld}} \mathcal{G}$) iff for each set \mathcal{R}^* it holds that $\sigma((\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{R}^*)) = \sigma((\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}} \setminus \mathcal{R}^*))$.

Figure 7: The AFs \mathcal{F}_7 , \mathcal{G}_7 and deletions of them from Example 2.10. Deleted attacks $\mathcal{R}^* = \{(a, b)\}$ are highlighted with dashed outlines.

Example 2.10. Consider the AFs \mathcal{F}_7 and \mathcal{G}_7 in Figure 7. Let $\mathcal{R}^* = \{(a, b)\}$ and $\mathcal{A}^* = \{a\}$. With slight abuse of notation, for the local deletion via \mathcal{R}^* , we have $\{a, b\} \in \text{pr}(\mathcal{F}_7 \setminus \mathcal{R}^*)$ while $\{a, b\} \notin \text{pr}(\mathcal{G}_7 \setminus \mathcal{R}^*)$, i. e., $\mathcal{F}_7 \not\equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{ld}} \mathcal{G}_7$. Similarly, for the normal deletion via $[\mathcal{A}^*, \mathcal{R}^*]$, we have $\{b\} \in \text{pr}(\mathcal{F}_7 \setminus (\mathcal{A}^*, \mathcal{R}^*))$ while $\{b\} \notin \text{pr}(\mathcal{G}_7 \setminus (\mathcal{A}^*, \mathcal{R}^*))$ and therefore $\mathcal{F}_7 \not\equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{nd}} \mathcal{G}_7$. The same applies to all other semantics.

In general, update equivalence, deletion equivalence and local deletion equivalence coincide with syntactic identity (Baumann, 2014a). More interesting is normal deletion equivalence, which coincides with strong equivalence in case of the stable semantics. For the semantics $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{gr}\}$, the characterisation relies on the strong expansion kernels $\mathbf{a}\kappa^*$, $\mathbf{c}\kappa^*$ and $\mathbf{g}\kappa^*$ plus some additional conditions. For the other semantics, no characterisation is known so far.

Other Equivalence Notions. Beyond the above introduced equivalence notions, there are several other approaches for abstract argumentation in the literature that we will not consider in detail in this work. Firstly, Baumann (2012b) introduced *minimal change equivalence* wrt. some semantics σ and some form of expansion Θ . As the name suggests, this notion guarantees that

two argumentation frameworks require the same minimal effort to enforce certain extensions. Consequently, the focus of this equivalence notion is very much on the dynamic aspect of modifying the argumentation frameworks, while we are more interested in a static analysis of the underlying reasoning in argumentation frameworks via equivalence. We refer to Baumann and Brewka (2018) for an overview over the relations between minimal change equivalence and the variants of expansion equivalence. A similar focus underlies the *C-relativised equivalence* of Baumann et al. (2019). This equivalence is a parametrised notion that generalises both standard and strong equivalence. More specifically, two argumentation frameworks are *C*-equivalent if they possess the same σ -extensions under any expansion that does not affect the given set of core arguments *C*. The corner cases $C = \mathcal{A}$ and $C = \emptyset$ then represent standard and strong equivalence respectively. Beyond these corner cases, we do not consider a comparison between our notion of serialisation equivalence and *C*-relativised equivalence in this work. Finally, there is also the notion of *attack-defense equivalence* based on so-called attack-defense semantics (Liao and van der Torre, 2024). These semantics make explicit the (partial) defense of arguments through a meta framework. Two argumentation frameworks are then considered equivalent if they possess the same defense structure. This equivalence has so far only been studied for the complete semantics and is located between standard and strong equivalence.

Overview. We conclude this section by taking a look at the status quo of the relations between the above introduced equivalence notions. These results have been established in different works over the years, mainly in Oikarinen and Woltran (2011); Baumann (2014b, 2018); Baumann and Brewka (2018).

Figure 8: General relations between the different equivalence notions wrt. any semantics. An arrow from node *X* to node *Y* means that if two AFs are equivalent wrt. *X*, then they are also equivalent wrt. *Y*.

Figure 8 shows the general relations between equivalences that necessarily hold for any semantics. An arrow from equivalence X to equivalence Y represents the fact that if two argumentation frameworks are equivalent wrt. X , then they are also equivalent wrt. Y . Note that the relations are basically the "common ground" of relationships between equivalences that follow via their definitions and hold independently of the specific characterisations. Overall, update and (local) deletion equivalence is the most strict notion and implies strong equivalence, which coincides with normal expansion equivalence. The remaining expansion equivalences, namely strong normal expansion, local expansion and weak normal expansion equivalence are implied by strong equivalence and, in turn, imply standard equivalence. Interestingly, the same holds for normal deletion equivalence.

Now, taking the characterisations of the equivalences wrt. the different semantics from the literature into account, these relations can be refined further, depending on the semantics. These refined relations are summarised in Figure 9. Note that these figures are exhaustive, i. e., if two nodes are not connected, then there exists no relation between these equivalences and each node represents a unique equivalence notion (under which multiple equivalences may be summarised). Nodes with a dashed outline represent equivalences for which no characterisation result exists as of yet. As we can see, for instance, in many cases local expansion equivalence coincides with strong equivalence and normal expansion equivalence, cf. Figures 9a, 9b and 9f. Another surprising observation is that normal deletion equivalence is implied by strong expansion equivalence for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{gr}\}$ and they even coincide in case of the stable semantics. This is related to their characterisation via the κ^* -kernels (Baumann, 2014a) and we will encounter this relation again later when considering the other semantics as well. Remarkably, the stable semantics is the only semantics for which all equivalence notions are related to each other.

Finally, note that strong admissibility and the unchallenged semantics have not been considered in the context of equivalence at all.

All in all, there is a fairly clear picture of the relations between equivalences wrt. the same semantics. However, the relations between different semantics under the same equivalence notion, or any further relations, have only been partially studied so far. The relations between different semantics under standard equivalence are rather straight-forward and have been shown by Oikarinen and Woltran (2011), for most semantics. They also considered the relation between strong equivalence notions wrt. different semantics and

(a) Relations between the different equivalence notions wrt. admissibility.

(b) Relations between the different equivalence notions wrt. $\sigma \in \{pr, id\}$. Note that for ideal semantics, weak expansion equivalence has not been characterised.

(c) Relations between the different equivalence notions wrt. complete semantics.

(d) Relations between the different equivalence notions wrt. grounded semantics.

(e) Relations between the different equivalence notions wrt. stable semantics.

(f) Relations between the different equivalence notions wrt. $\sigma \in \{sst, ea\}$.

Figure 9: Overview over the relations between different equivalence notions wrt. the same semantics. Equivalence notions within the same node coincide in general. Dashed outlines denote equivalence notions for which no proper characterisation exists as of yet.

did the same for local expansion equivalence. For the remaining equivalence notions there exists, to the best of our knowledge, no comprehensive analysis of the relations between the different semantics. Even more importantly, a complete picture of the whole landscape of argumentation semantics and all equivalence notions is still missing. It will be one of our main contributions in the following to establish the notion of serialisation equivalence, situate it in the landscape of equivalences, and provide this comprehensive overview.

3. Completing the Picture

Before we introduce our novel notion of serialisation equivalence, we turn our attention to the aforementioned expansion and deletion equivalences. More specifically, we establish missing characterisations, in particular for strong admissibility and the unchallenged semantics, and we examine the relations between the semantics within the context of these equivalence notions.

Standard Equivalence. Let us first consider strong admissibility (Caminada, 2014), which has so far not been studied in the context of equivalence at all. The following result follows straight-forwardly from the definition of strong admissibility.

Proposition 3.1. *Let \mathcal{F} , \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sa} \mathcal{G}$, then it follows that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{gr} \mathcal{G}$. *Proof: P. 58**

As the following example shows, for the other semantics, no such relation to strong admissibility exists.

Example 3.1. Consider the AFs \mathcal{F}_8 and \mathcal{G}_8 in Figure 10. We have that $sa(\mathcal{F}_8) = sa(\mathcal{G}_8) = \{\emptyset\}$, i. e., it holds that $\mathcal{F}_8 \equiv_{sa} \mathcal{G}_8$. We also have $\mathcal{F}_8 \equiv_{gr} \mathcal{G}_8$. For all other semantics $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{pr}, \text{st}, \text{uc}, \text{id}, \text{sst}, \text{ea}\}$ we have that $\mathcal{F}_8 \not\equiv_{\sigma} \mathcal{G}_8$.

Figure 10: The argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F}_8 and \mathcal{G}_8 from Example 3.1.

For the other direction, there is no relation at all between standard equivalence wrt. strong admissibility and any other semantics.

Example 3.2. Consider the AFs \mathcal{F}_9 and \mathcal{G}_9 in Figure 12. We have that $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F}_9) = \{\emptyset, \{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{c}\}, \{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}\}\}$ and $\text{sa}(\mathcal{G}_9) = \{\emptyset, \{\mathbf{c}\}, \{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}\}\}$, i. e., it holds that $\mathcal{F}_9 \not\equiv_{\text{sa}} \mathcal{G}_9$. For all other semantics $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{pr}, \text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{uc}, \text{id}, \text{sst}, \text{ea}\}$, we have that $\mathcal{F}_9 \equiv_{\sigma} \mathcal{G}_9$.

Figure 11: The argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F}_9 and \mathcal{G}_9 from Example 3.2.

Let us turn now to the unchallenged semantics. It can be shown that the unchallenged extensions are a subset of the admissible sets and that they are uniquely defined in this way.

Proposition 3.2. *Let \mathcal{F} , \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{ad}} \mathcal{G}$, then it follows that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{uc}} \mathcal{G}$. *Proof: P. 58**

For the other semantics, no connection to standard equivalence wrt. unchallenged semantics exists, as shown by the following two examples. Additionally, Example 3.4 also shows that standard equivalence wrt. unchallenged semantics does not generally coincide with standard equivalence wrt. admissibility.

Example 3.3. Consider the AFs \mathcal{F}_{10} and \mathcal{G}_{10} in Figure 12. We have that $\text{uc}(\mathcal{F}_{10}) = \{\{\mathbf{d}\}\}$ and $\text{uc}(\mathcal{G}_{10}) = \{\{\mathbf{d}\}, \{\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{d}\}\}$, i. e., it holds that $\mathcal{F}_{10} \not\equiv_{\text{uc}} \mathcal{G}_{10}$. We also have $\mathcal{F}_{10} \not\equiv_{\text{ad}} \mathcal{G}_{10}$. For all other semantics $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{pr}, \text{sa}, \text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{id}, \text{sst}, \text{ea}\}$, we have that $\mathcal{F}_{10} \equiv_{\sigma} \mathcal{G}_{10}$.

Example 3.4. Consider the AFs \mathcal{F}_{11} and \mathcal{G}_{11} in Figure 13. We have that $\text{uc}(\mathcal{F}_{11}) = \text{uc}(\mathcal{G}_{11}) = \{\{\mathbf{c}\}\}$, i. e., it holds that $\mathcal{F}_{11} \equiv_{\text{uc}} \mathcal{G}_{11}$. For all other semantics $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{pr}, \text{sa}, \text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{id}, \text{sst}, \text{ea}\}$ we have that $\mathcal{F}_{11} \not\equiv_{\sigma} \mathcal{G}_{11}$.

The following theorem summarises all relations between the semantics in the context of standard equivalence. All relations, apart from the two shown above – in Propositions 3.1 and 3.2 – have already been shown by Oikarinen and Woltran (2011).

Figure 12: The argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F}_{10} and \mathcal{G}_{10} from Example 3.3.

Figure 13: The argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F}_{11} and \mathcal{G}_{11} from Example 3.4.

Theorem 3.1. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that*

1. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ad} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{pr, id, uc\}$,*
2. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{co} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{pr, id, gr\}$,*
3. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sa} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{gr} \mathcal{G}$.*

Proof: P. 58

None of the other relations holds and for the remaining counterexamples we refer to Oikarinen and Woltran (2011).

Strong Equivalence. Let us now turn to strong equivalence. For strong admissibility the following result follows easily. It shows that strong equivalence wrt. strong admissibility is characterised by the grounded kernel $\mathbf{g}\kappa$.

Proposition 3.3. *Let \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that $\mathcal{F}^{\mathbf{g}\kappa} = \mathcal{G}^{\mathbf{g}\kappa}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sa}^s \mathcal{G}$.*

Proof: P. 58

Interestingly, it can also be shown that strong equivalence wrt. unchallenged semantics is characterised via the $\mathbf{a}\kappa$ -kernel and therefore equivalent to strong equivalence wrt. $\sigma \in \{\mathbf{ad}, \mathbf{pr}, \mathbf{id}, \mathbf{sst}, \mathbf{ea}\}$.

Proposition 3.4. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that $\mathcal{F}^{\mathbf{a}\kappa} = \mathcal{G}^{\mathbf{a}\kappa}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{uc}^s \mathcal{G}$.*

Proof: P. 59

We make the following observation, analogously to the other semantics.

Corollary 3.1. *Let \mathcal{F} be an argumentation framework. It holds that*

1. $sa(\mathcal{F}) = sa(\mathcal{F}^{\mathbf{g}\kappa})$,
2. $uc(\mathcal{F}) = uc(\mathcal{F}^{\mathbf{a}\kappa})$.

The relations between all semantics, except strong admissibility and unchallenged semantics, under the notion of strong equivalence, have already been established by Oikarinen and Woltran (2011). Note however that for both of these semantics the relations follow immediately, since they are characterised by existing kernels.

Theorem 3.2 (Oikarinen and Woltran, 2011). *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that*

1. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ad}^s \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{pr}^s \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{uc}^s \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{id}^s \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sst}^s \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ea}^s \mathcal{G}$,
2. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sa}^s \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{gr}^s \mathcal{G}$,
3. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{co}^s \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^s \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, uc, id, sst, ea, sa, gr, st\}$,
4. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^s \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{st}^s \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, uc, id, sst, ea\}$. *Proof: P. 61*

Counterexamples for the remaining relations can be found in Oikarinen and Woltran (2011).

Normal Expansion Equivalence. This equivalence notion has been examined by Baumann (2012a) in detail, with the conclusion that normal expansion equivalence coincides with strong equivalence in general. As expected, the same applies for strong admissibility and the unchallenged semantics, giving us the following overall result for normal expansion equivalence.

Theorem 3.3 (Baumann, 2012a). *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks and $\sigma \in \Sigma$. It holds that*

$$\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^s \mathcal{G} \text{ if and only if } \mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^n \mathcal{G}.$$

Proof: P. 63

Strong Expansion Equivalence. We begin again by examining strong admissibility and the unchallenged semantics, which have not been considered in the context of strong expansion equivalence so far. Similar to the case of strong equivalence, we can show that the equivalence wrt. these semantics is characterised by the existing kernels $\mathbf{g}\kappa^*$ and $\mathbf{a}\kappa^*$, respectively.

Proposition 3.5. *Let \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that $\mathcal{F}^{\mathbf{g}\kappa^*} \doteq \mathcal{G}^{\mathbf{g}\kappa^*}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sa}^s \mathcal{G}$. *Proof: P. 66**

Proposition 3.6. *Let \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that $\mathcal{F}^{\mathbf{a}\kappa^*} \doteq \mathcal{G}^{\mathbf{a}\kappa^*}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{uc}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$. *Proof: P. 66**

That also gives rise to the following observation, analogously to Corollary 2.2.

Corollary 3.2. *Let \mathcal{F} be an argumentation framework. It holds that*

1. $sa(\mathcal{F}) = sa(\mathcal{F}^{\mathbf{g}\kappa^*})$,
2. $uc(\mathcal{F}) = uc(\mathcal{F}^{\mathbf{a}\kappa^*})$.

While strong expansion equivalence has been characterised for most semantics by Baumann (2012a), the relationships between the semantics in this context have not been examined so far. As it turns out, the relations are quite similar to the case of strong equivalence. The only notable difference is that strong expansion equivalence wrt. eager and semi-stable semantics is not equivalent to strong expansion equivalence wrt. admissibility and instead just implies it. Furthermore, they also imply strong expansion equivalence wrt. stable semantics, while none of the other semantics does any more, in contrast to the case of strong equivalence, cf. Theorem 3.2.

Theorem 3.4. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that*

1. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ad}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{pr}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{uc}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{id}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$,
2. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sa}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{gr}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$,
3. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sst}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ea}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$,
4. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{co}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, id, uc, sa, gr\}$,
5. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sst}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, id, uc, st\}$,
6. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ea}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, id, uc, st\}$. *Proof: P. 67*

The remaining relations do not hold, as shown by the following example.

Figure 14: The AFs \mathcal{F}_{12} , \mathcal{G}_{12} , \mathcal{H}_{12} and \mathcal{I}_{12} from Example 3.5.

Example 3.5. Consider the AFs in Figure 14. The following observations can be verified easily under consideration of the strong expansion kernels, cf. Equations (5)-(7). \mathcal{F}_{12} and \mathcal{I}_{12} are strong expansion equivalent wrt. $\sigma \in \{\text{ad, pr, id, uc}\}$, but not wrt. $\sigma' \in \{\text{co, sa, gr, st, sst, ea}\}$. \mathcal{H}_{12} and \mathcal{I}_{12} are strong expansion equivalent wrt. $\sigma \in \{\text{sst, ea}\}$, but not wrt. $\sigma' \in \{\text{co, sa, gr}\}$. \mathcal{F}_{12} and \mathcal{H}_{12} are strong expansion equivalent wrt. co , but not wrt. $\sigma' \in \{\text{st, sst, ea}\}$. \mathcal{G}_{12} and \mathcal{I}_{12} are strong expansion equivalent wrt. $\sigma \in \{\text{sa, gr}\}$, but not wrt. $\sigma' \in \{\text{ad, pr, id, uc, co, st, sst, ea}\}$. \mathcal{F}_{12} and \mathcal{G}_{12} are strong expansion equivalent wrt. st , but not wrt. $\sigma' \in \{\text{ad, pr, id, uc, co, sa, gr, sst, ea}\}$.

Weak Expansion Equivalence. Weak expansion equivalence has only been characterised for admissibility as well as complete, preferred and stable semantics (Baumann, 2011; Baumann and Brewka, 2018). Basically, two AFs \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are weak expansion equivalent iff they possess the same arguments and σ -extensions, and for every extension E , we have that $E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}}^+$ and $E \cup E_{\mathcal{G}}^+$ coincide. As it turns out, we can use the same characterisation for strong admissibility and the grounded semantics. We begin with the latter.

Proposition 3.7. *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}})$, $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}})$ be argumentation frameworks. It holds that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{gr}}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{G}$ if and only if $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$, $\text{gr}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{gr}(\mathcal{G})$ and for the unique grounded extension $E \in \text{gr}(\mathcal{F})$, we have that $\mathbf{a} \notin E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}}^+$ iff $\mathbf{a} \notin E \cup E_{\mathcal{G}}^+$. *Proof:* P. 68*

Since every AF has a uniquely determined grounded extension, the qualifier “for each” trivialises in the above statement. However, we kept it in order to maintain the structure of the other characterisations from (Baumann, 2011; Baumann and Brewka, 2018).

We now turn to strong admissibility. The characterisation relies on the *Directionality*¹ property of argumentation semantics (Baroni and Giacomin, 2007; van der Torre and Vesic, 2018). Since strong admissibility satisfies *Directionality*, we can easily establish the following result, which is necessary for the characterisation.

Lemma 3.1. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{H} be argumentation frameworks such that $\mathcal{F} \prec_S^W \mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$. If $E \in \text{sa}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$, then $E \cap \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \in \text{sa}(\mathcal{F})$. *Proof:* P. 69*

¹A semantics σ satisfies *Directionality* iff the status of each σ -extension only depends on its attackers in \mathcal{F} .

Proposition 3.8. *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}})$, $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}})$ be argumentation frameworks. It holds that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sa}^{wm} \mathcal{G}$ if and only if $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$, $sa(\mathcal{F}) = sa(\mathcal{G})$ and for each $E \in sa(\mathcal{F})$, we have that $\mathbf{a} \notin E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}}^+$ iff $\mathbf{a} \notin E \cup E_{\mathcal{G}}^+$. Proof: P. 70*

For the remaining semantics $\sigma \in \{\text{uc}, \text{id}, \text{sst}, \text{ea}\}$, a characterisation of weak expansion equivalence is still an open question. It was shown that semi-stable, eager and unchallenged semantics violate *Directionality* (Baroni and Giacomin, 2007; van der Torre and Vesic, 2018; Bengel and Thimm, 2022). Hence, a different characterisation is likely needed for these semantics.

For weak expansion equivalence, the relations between different semantics have also not been studied so far. In the following theorem, we state all relations between semantics for which we have a characterisation of weak expansion equivalence. Overall, the obtained relations are quite similar to the relations under standard equivalence, cf. Theorem 3.1. Interestingly, the stricter conditions for weak expansion equivalence, compared to standard equivalence, allow us to establish a relation to the stable semantics.

Theorem 3.5. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that*

1. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ad}^{wm} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{wm} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{\text{pr}, \text{st}\}$,*
2. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{co}^{wm} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{wm} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{\text{pr}, \text{st}, \text{gr}\}$,*
3. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{pr}^{wm} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{st}^{wm} \mathcal{G}$,*
4. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sa}^{wm} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{gr}^{wm} \mathcal{G}$.*

Proof: P. 71

The remaining relations between semantics do not hold, as shown by the following two examples.

Example 3.6. Consider the AFs in Figure 15. We can make the following observations regarding weak expansion equivalence. \mathcal{F}_{13} and \mathcal{G}_{13} are weak expansion equivalent wrt. $\sigma \in \{\text{sa}, \text{gr}\}$, but not wrt. $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{pr}, \text{st}\}$. \mathcal{F}_{13} and \mathcal{H}_{13} are weak expansion equivalent wrt. st , but not wrt. any other semantics. \mathcal{I}_{13} and \mathcal{J}_{13} are weak expansion equivalent wrt. $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{pr}, \text{st}\}$, but not wrt. $\sigma' \in \{\text{co}, \text{sa}, \text{gr}\}$.

Figure 15: The Afs \mathcal{F}_{13} , \mathcal{G}_{13} , \mathcal{H}_{13} , \mathcal{I}_{13} and \mathcal{J}_{13} from Example 3.6.

Example 3.7. Consider the AFs in Figure 16. We can make the following observations regarding weak expansion equivalence. \mathcal{F}_{14} and \mathcal{G}_{14} are weak expansion equivalent wrt. $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{pr}, \text{st}, \text{gr}\}$, but not wrt. $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{sa}\}$. \mathcal{F}_{14} and \mathcal{G}_{14} are weak expansion equivalent wrt. pr , but not wrt. $\sigma' \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{sa}, \text{gr}\}$.

Figure 16: The AFs \mathcal{F}_{14} , \mathcal{G}_{14} and \mathcal{H}_{14} from Example 3.7.

Local Expansion Equivalence. The remaining type of expansion equivalence is local expansion equivalence, which has originally been introduced by Oikarinen and Woltran (2011). We consider first local expansion equivalence wrt. strong admissibility. Local expansion equivalence wrt. grounded semantics has been characterised via the $\mathbf{g}\kappa$ -kernel in combination with some additional conditions (Oikarinen and Woltran, 2011). As it turns out, local expansion equivalence wrt. strong admissibility can be characterised in the same way. First we introduce two properties of argumentation frameworks related to self-attacking arguments.

Definition 3.1. Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an argumentation framework. We say that \mathcal{F} is *self-loop pathological* if $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}$ for all $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}$, and *\mathbf{b} -pathological* if $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}$ and $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}$ for all $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{b}$.

In other words, an argumentation framework is pathological if all arguments attack themselves or if there is a single argument \mathbf{b} , which is the only non-self-attacking argument. Based on the above, together with the $\mathbf{g}\kappa$ -kernel, we can then characterise local expansion equivalence wrt. strong admissibility.

Proposition 3.9. For any two argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F} , \mathcal{G} , we have that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sa}^l \mathcal{G}$ iff jointly $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$, $\Delta_{\mathcal{F}}(\emptyset) = \Delta_{\mathcal{G}}(\emptyset) = S$, and

- $(\mathcal{F}^{\{\mathbf{a}\}})^{\mathbf{g}\kappa} \doteq (\mathcal{G}^{\{\mathbf{a}\}})^{\mathbf{g}\kappa}$ for all $\mathbf{a} \in S$, or
- in case $S = \{\mathbf{a}\}$,

- $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathbf{a}_{\mathcal{F}}^+ = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} \setminus \mathbf{a}_{\mathcal{G}}^+$, both $\mathcal{F}^{\{\mathbf{a}\}}$ and $\mathcal{G}^{\{\mathbf{a}\}}$ are \mathbf{b} -pathological for some \mathbf{b} , and $(\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}^{\{\mathbf{a}\}}}$ iff $(\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}^{\{\mathbf{a}\}}}$ for all \mathbf{d} ; or
- both $\mathcal{F}^{\{\mathbf{a}\}}$ and $\mathcal{G}^{\{\mathbf{a}\}}$ are self-loop pathological. *Proof: P. 72*

Essentially, this characterisation represents the following idea. First, it requires that the two argumentation frameworks have the same arguments and the same set of unattacked arguments (represented by $\Delta_{\mathcal{F}}(\emptyset) = \Delta_{\mathcal{G}}(\emptyset) = S$). In addition to that, they need to have the same $\mathbf{g}\kappa$ -kernel of the reduct wrt. each unattacked argument \mathbf{a} . Alternatively, there must be just a single unattacked argument and the reducts of both frameworks wrt. that argument must be pathological. There is an interesting correspondence here to the serialisation-based characterisation of grounded semantics, where the \mathbf{g} -serialisation sequences consist exclusively of unattacked initial sets of the respective reducts. This will also turn out to be relevant later in Section 4.2 when we consider the connection between local expansion equivalence and serialisation equivalence.

For $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{pr}, \text{id}, \text{sst}, \text{ea}\}$ it was shown by Oikarinen and Woltran (2011) that local expansion equivalence and strong equivalence coincide. We can establish the same result for the unchallenged semantics. Hence, for all of these semantics, both strong and local equivalence are characterised via the $\mathbf{a}\kappa$ -kernel.

Proposition 3.10. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that $\mathcal{F}^{\mathbf{a}\kappa} \doteq \mathcal{G}^{\mathbf{a}\kappa}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{uc}^l \mathcal{G}$.* *Proof: P. 74*

Let us now turn to the case of the complete semantics. Local expansion equivalence wrt. complete semantics was originally characterised by Oikarinen and Woltran (2011) as follows.

First of all, we have the *co-local-kernel* of \mathcal{F} as $\mathcal{F}^{\text{cl}\kappa} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}^{\text{cl}\kappa})$ with

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}^{\text{cl}\kappa} = \mathcal{R} \setminus \{ & (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \mid \mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{b}, (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R} \wedge [(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R} \\ & \vee (\exists \mathbf{c} : \mathbf{c} \neq \mathbf{a} \wedge (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}), (\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R})] \}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Oikarinen and Woltran (2011) also state that $\text{co}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{co}(\mathcal{F}^{\text{cl}\kappa})$, for all argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F} . Secondly, we also need the following definition.

Definition 3.2. For any argumentation framework $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ and some argument $b \in \mathcal{A}$, we say that \mathcal{F} is *b-saturated* if and only if

- $(b, b) \notin \mathcal{R}$,
- $(a, b) \in \mathcal{R}$ for some $a \in \mathcal{A}$ with $a \neq b$,
- $(a, a) \in \mathcal{R}$ for each $a \in \mathcal{A}$ such that $(a, b) \in \mathcal{R}$, and
- $(d, a) \in \mathcal{R}$ for each $a, d \in \mathcal{A}$ such that $(a, b) \in \mathcal{R}$ and $(d, d) \notin \mathcal{R}$.

Together, this leads to the following characterisation of local expansion equivalence wrt. complete semantics.

Theorem 3.6 (Oikarinen and Woltran, 2011). *For any two argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} , it holds that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{co}}^l \mathcal{G}$ if and only if*

1. $\mathcal{F}^{\text{cl}\kappa} \doteq \mathcal{G}^{\text{cl}\kappa}$, or
2. $\mathcal{F}^{\text{a}\kappa} \doteq \mathcal{G}^{\text{a}\kappa}$, $\Delta_{\mathcal{F}}(\emptyset) = \Delta_{\mathcal{G}}(\emptyset)$, and both \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are b -saturated for some $b \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$.

However, this characterisation is not correct. In particular, an argumentation framework and its $\text{cl}\kappa$ -kernel do not necessarily have the same complete extensions, which leads to a contradiction with condition (1) of the above theorem.

Example 3.8. Consider the argumentation frameworks $\mathcal{F}_{15} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ and $\mathcal{F}_{15}^{\text{cl}\kappa}$ in Figure 17. Notice that we have $\text{co}(\mathcal{F}_{15}) = \{\emptyset, \{\mathbf{b}\}\}$ and $\text{co}(\mathcal{F}_{15}^{\text{cl}\kappa}) = \{\{\mathbf{b}\}\}$. Therefore, we immediately have $\mathcal{F}_{15} \not\equiv_{\text{co}}^l \mathcal{F}_{15}^{\text{cl}\kappa}$. Consider the $\text{cl}\kappa$ -kernel from Equation (8) and the attack (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) in \mathcal{F}_{15} . We have that $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{b}$ and also $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}$. We do not have $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}$. However, we have $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}$ and there is the argument \mathbf{c} for which we have $(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}$. Thus, the attack (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) will be removed by the co -local-kernel. It is easy to see that the same is true for the attack (\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{b}) and no other attacks may be removed. The problem here is simply, that when checking the conditions for each attack, in order to decide whether it must be removed or not, we have to remove both (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) and (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}) in the kernel framework. Even if we somehow enforce that only one attack may be removed at a time until some fixpoint is reached, this would not work, since the kernel framework would no longer be uniquely determined and would depend on the order in which the attacks are considered.

Furthermore, the second condition of the above characterisation is also not a sufficient condition for local equivalence wrt. complete semantics.

Figure 17: The argumentation framework \mathcal{F}_{15} and its co-local-kernel from Example 3.8.

Example 3.9. Consider \mathcal{F}_{16} and \mathcal{G}_{16} in Figure 18. We have that $\mathcal{G}_{16}^{\text{a}\kappa} \doteq \mathcal{F}_{16}^{\text{a}\kappa} \doteq \mathcal{F}_{16}$. We also have $\Delta_{\mathcal{F}_{16}}(\emptyset) = \Delta_{\mathcal{G}_{16}}(\emptyset) = \{\mathbf{a}\}$. However we have $\text{co}(\mathcal{F}_{16}) = \{\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}\}\}$ and $\text{co}(\mathcal{G}_{16}) = \{\{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}\}\}$. Hence, \mathcal{F}_{16} and \mathcal{G}_{16} cannot be local expansion equivalent, e. g., given the empty AF $\mathcal{H} = (\emptyset, \emptyset)$ for a local expansion.

Figure 18: The argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F}_{16} and \mathcal{G}_{16} from Example 3.9.

A more involved characterisation is likely needed, which we leave for future work.

The relations between the different semantics in the context of local expansion equivalence have been studied in detail by Oikarinen and Woltran (2011). Note that the relations have been shown independently of the characterisation results and thus hold even in consideration of the missing characterisation of local equivalence wrt. complete semantics. The results for strong admissibility and unchallenged semantics follow again immediately from their characterisation via existing concepts.

Theorem 3.7 (Oikarinen and Woltran, 2011). *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that*

1. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ad}^l \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{pr}^l \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{uc}^l \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{id}^l \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sst}^l \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ea}^l \mathcal{G}$,
2. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sa}^l \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{gr}^l \mathcal{G}$,
3. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{co}^l \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^l \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, uc, id, sst, ea, sa, gr, st\}$,
4. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^l \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{st}^l \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, uc, id, sst, ea\}$. *Proof: P. 74*

The remaining relations do not hold, counterexamples are given in (Oikarinen and Woltran, 2011).

Update and (Local) Deletion Equivalence. As already shown by Baumann (2014a), (local) deletion equivalence as well as update equivalence generally collapse to syntactic identity for many of the semantics that we consider in this work. Only strong admissibility and the unchallenged semantics have not been considered yet, which we rectify in the following. For that, we first recall the principle of *Isolate-Inclusion*.

Definition 3.3 (Baumann, 2014a). Let σ be a semantics. Then σ satisfies *Isolate-Inclusion* iff for any AF \mathcal{F} the set of all isolated arguments is contained in at least one σ -extension.

It is then easy to show that strong admissibility and the unchallenged semantics satisfy this principle for all argumentation frameworks.

Proposition 3.11. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be AFs. It holds for any semantics $\sigma \in \{\text{sa}, \text{uc}\}$ that σ satisfies Isolate-Inclusion.*

Proof: P. 74

It was then shown by Baumann (2014a), that if a semantics satisfies *Conflict-Freeness* and *Isolate-Inclusion*, (local) deletion equivalence and update equivalence collapse to syntactic identity. That gives us the following result for all considered semantics.

Theorem 3.8 (Baumann, 2014a). *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks and $\sigma \in \Sigma$. It holds that*

$$\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^u \mathcal{G} \text{ iff } \mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^d \mathcal{G} \text{ iff } \mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{ld} \mathcal{G} \text{ iff } \mathcal{F} \doteq \mathcal{G}.$$

Proof: P. 75

Normal Deletion Equivalence. The remaining variant of deletion equivalences is normal deletion equivalence, which, in contrast to the other variants, does not collapse to syntactic identity. The quite surprising result of Baumann (2014a) is that normal deletion equivalence is closely related to strong expansion equivalence and in the case of stable semantics, they even coincide. In particular, Baumann (2014a) characterised normal deletion equivalence wrt. admissibility as well as grounded and complete semantics via the κ^* -kernels and some additional conditions. It is also notable that normal deletion equivalence does allow argumentation frameworks with different arguments to be equivalent. The characterisation for the remaining semantics, in particular also the preferred semantics, is still considered an open problem (Baumann and Strass, 2015). Before we get into that, we first introduce

some necessary conditions that we will need for the characterisation. Recall that $A\Delta B$ is the symmetric difference of two sets A and B .

Definition 3.4 (Baumann, 2014a). Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}})$, $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}})$ be argumentation frameworks. We define

1. $Loop(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G}) \Leftrightarrow \forall \mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \Delta \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} : (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}} \vee (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$,
2. $Att^{ad}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G}) \Leftrightarrow \forall \mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} \forall \mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cap \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} : ((\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}} \wedge (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}) \rightarrow (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}} \wedge \forall \mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} \setminus \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \forall \mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cap \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} : ((\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}} \wedge (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}) \rightarrow (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$,
3. $Att^{co}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G}) \Leftrightarrow \forall \mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} \forall \mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cap \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} : (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}} \rightarrow (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}} \wedge \forall \mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} \setminus \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \forall \mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cap \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} : (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}} \rightarrow (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$.

Basically, $Loop(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$ requires that the non-shared arguments of \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are self-attacking. $Att^{ad}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$ enforces that all shared non-self-attacking arguments counterattack against all non-shared arguments. Finally, $Att^{co}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$ states that all shared non-self-attacking arguments are not attacked by any non-shared arguments. Baumann (2014a) then used the above conditions in combination with the $\kappa*$ kernels to characterise normal deletion equivalence for admissibility, grounded and complete semantics.

As it turns out, we can use the same approach to characterise normal deletion equivalence wrt. strong admissibility, with the help of Corollary 3.2. In particular, that also means it coincides with normal deletion equivalence wrt. grounded semantics. This is in line with our other results in this section, showing that these two semantics coincide under many different equivalence notions.

Proposition 3.12. *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}})$, $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}})$ be argumentation frameworks and $I = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cap \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$. It holds that $Loop(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$, $Att^{co}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$ and $(\mathcal{F}|_I)^{g\kappa*} \doteq (\mathcal{G}|_I)^{g\kappa*}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sa}^{nd} \mathcal{G}$. *Proof:* P. 75*

In a similar way, it can be shown that normal deletion equivalence wrt. preferred semantics is characterised in the same way as admissibility. The same applies to unchallenged and ideal semantics.

Proposition 3.13. *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}})$, $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}})$ be argumentation frameworks, $I = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cap \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$ and $\sigma \in \{pr, uc, id\}$. It holds that $Loop(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$, $Att^{ad}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$ and $(\mathcal{F}|_I)^{a\kappa*} \doteq (\mathcal{G}|_I)^{a\kappa*}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{nd} \mathcal{G}$. *Proof:* P. 76*

Further relations between the different semantics in the context of normal deletion equivalence have not been considered so far. Our results show that complete semantics imply most of the other semantics, similar to the situation under many of the expansion equivalences. Normal deletion equivalence under stable semantics turns out to be completely independent of the other semantics.

Theorem 3.9. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that*

1. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ad}^{nd} \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{pr}^{nd} \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{uc}^{nd} \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{id}^{nd} \mathcal{G}$,
2. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sa}^{nd} \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{gr}^{nd} \mathcal{G}$,
3. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{co}^{nd} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{nd} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, uc, id, sa, gr\}$. *Proof: P. 79*

The characterisation of normal deletion equivalence wrt. semi-stable and eager semantics remains an open question. As shown by Examples 3.10 and 3.11 below, they are not implied by any of the other semantics in the context of normal deletion equivalence and do not imply $\sigma \in \{co, sa, gr, st\}$. Furthermore, we conjecture that normal deletion equivalence wrt. semi-stable and eager semantics coincide and that they imply normal deletion equivalence wrt. $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, uc, id\}$. However, a formal proof is missing at the moment.

Conjecture 3.1. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that*

1. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sst}^{nd} \mathcal{G}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ea}^{nd} \mathcal{G}$,
2. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sst}^{nd} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{nd} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, uc, id\}$,
3. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ea}^{nd} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{nd} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, uc, id\}$.

All remaining relations do not hold, as illustrated by the following examples.

Figure 19: The argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F}_{17} , \mathcal{G}_{17} and \mathcal{H}_{17} from Example 3.10.

Example 3.10. Consider the AFs in Figure 19. We can make the following observations regarding normal deletion equivalence. \mathcal{F}_{17} and \mathcal{G}_{17} are normal deletion equivalent wrt. co , but not wrt. $\sigma' \in \{\text{st}, \text{sst}, \text{ea}\}$. \mathcal{F}_{17} and \mathcal{G}_{17} are normal deletion equivalent wrt. $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{pr}, \text{uc}, \text{id}\}$, but not wrt. $\sigma' \in \{\text{co}, \text{sa}, \text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{sst}, \text{ea}\}$.

Figure 20: The argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F}_{18} , \mathcal{G}_{18} and \mathcal{H}_{18} from Example 3.11.

Example 3.11. Consider the AFs in Figure 19. We can make the following observations regarding normal deletion equivalence. \mathcal{F}_{18} and \mathcal{G}_{18} are normal deletion equivalent wrt. $\sigma \in \{\text{sa}, \text{gr}\}$, but not wrt. $\sigma' \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{pr}, \text{uc}, \text{id}, \text{st}, \text{sst}, \text{ea}\}$. \mathcal{F}_{18} and \mathcal{H}_{18} are normal deletion equivalent wrt. st , but not wrt. $\sigma' \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{pr}, \text{sa}, \text{gr}, \text{uc}, \text{id}, \text{sst}, \text{ea}\}$. \mathcal{G}_{18} and \mathcal{H}_{18} are normal deletion equivalent wrt. $\sigma \in \{\text{sst}, \text{ea}\}$, but not wrt. $\sigma' \in \{\text{co}, \text{sa}, \text{gr}, \text{st}\}$.

4. Characterising Serialisation Equivalence for Abstract Argumentation

We now finally come back to our original goal outlined in Section 1 – introducing an equivalence notion for abstract argumentation that properly takes into account the underlying reasoning represented in an argumentation framework. For that, we will utilise the serialisation sequences as the semantical representation of reasoning. Note that we therefore focus on semantics that are serialisable, i. e., the semantics $\Sigma_s = \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{pr}, \text{sa}, \text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{uc}\}$. As the remaining semantics cannot be characterised via serialisation sequences (Thimm, 2022), we do not consider them in the following. Consequently, we define serialisation equivalence as follows.

Definition 4.1. Let \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks and $\sigma \in \Sigma_s$ is a semantics. We say that \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are *serialisation equivalent* wrt. σ , written as $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$, if and only if we have that $\mathfrak{S}_{\sigma}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\sigma}(\mathcal{G})$.

Intuitively, under serialisation equivalence we take into account every possible sequence in which the arguments of each extension E can be accepted in

Figure 21: The AFs \mathcal{F}_{19} , \mathcal{G}_{19} and \mathcal{H}_{19} from Example 4.2.

order to construct the extension. That is, we are considering more dialectical information, in the form of the order in which arguments of an extension may be accepted, when comparing argumentation frameworks.

With this new notion of serialisation equivalence, we can now appropriately handle the argumentation frameworks from Section 1, as shown by the following example.

Example 4.1. With $\equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{se}}$, we can now distinguish between the AFs \mathcal{F}_1 and \mathcal{G}_1 from the introduction, depicted in Figure 1. We have that $\mathcal{F}_1 \not\equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}_1$ for any $\sigma \in \Sigma_s$. For instance, the only preferred serialisation sequence of \mathcal{F}_1 is $(\{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{c}\})$, while the only preferred sequence of \mathcal{G}_1 is $(\{\mathbf{c}\}, \{\mathbf{a}\})$, highlighting that the underlying reasoning of the extension $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}\}$ is different in both frameworks.

In contrast to that, consider the AFs \mathcal{F}_2 and \mathcal{G}_2 in Figure 2. We have that $\mathcal{F}_2 \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}_2$ for any semantics, with $(\{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{d}\})$ as the only preferred serialisation sequence of both \mathcal{F}_2 and \mathcal{G}_2 . Meaning, that in these AFs the underlying reasoning of the single extension $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{d}\}$ is the same.

The following examples further illustrates the capabilities of serialisation equivalence.

Example 4.2. Consider the AFs \mathcal{F}_{19} , \mathcal{G}_{19} and \mathcal{H}_{19} in Figure 21. For the complete semantics, we have that $\mathcal{F}_{19} \equiv_{\text{co}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}_{19}$. For both AFs there exist two serialisation sequences: the empty sequence \mathcal{S}_0 and $\mathcal{S}_1 = (\{\mathbf{d}\}, \{\mathbf{a}\})$. Meaning, in both AFs \mathbf{d} is required to defend \mathbf{a} . On the other hand, we have $\mathcal{F}_{19} \not\equiv_{\text{co}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{H}_{19}$, because the AF \mathcal{H}_{19} has, besides \mathcal{S}_0 and \mathcal{S}_1 , the complete serialisation sequences $\mathcal{S}_2 = (\{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{d}\})$ and $\mathcal{S}_3 = (\{\mathbf{a}\})$. Note that we also have $\mathcal{F}_{19} \not\equiv_{\text{co}} \mathcal{H}_{19}$, since $\{\mathbf{a}\} \notin \text{co}(\mathcal{F}_{19})$. Hence, in \mathcal{H}_{19} Clearly, the same holds for \mathcal{G}_{19} and \mathcal{H}_{19} .

Figure 22: The AFs \mathcal{F}_{20} and \mathcal{G}_{20} from Example 4.3.

Example 4.3. Consider the AFs \mathcal{F}_{20} and \mathcal{G}_{20} depicted in Figure 22. We have that, for instance, $\mathcal{F}_{20} \equiv_{\text{pr}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}_{20}$. In particular, both AFs have the following preferred serialisation sequences: $(\{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{c}\}, \{\mathbf{d}\}, \{\mathbf{f}\})$, $(\{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{c}\}, \{\mathbf{f}\}, \{\mathbf{d}\})$, $(\{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{d}\}, \{\mathbf{c}\}, \{\mathbf{f}\})$ and $(\{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{d}\}, \{\mathbf{f}\}, \{\mathbf{c}\})$. As we can see, the arguments \mathbf{g} and \mathbf{h} , which are unique to \mathcal{F}_{20} and \mathcal{G}_{20} respectively, are insignificant, from a semantical perspective. Overall, the underlying reasoning is the same in both AFs: we have that \mathbf{a} defends \mathbf{c} and \mathbf{d} , which both defend \mathbf{f} against \mathbf{e} . Let us take a closer look at the argument \mathbf{f} in particular. In \mathcal{F}_{20} \mathbf{f} is simply defended against \mathbf{e} by both \mathbf{c} and \mathbf{d} . On the other hand, in \mathcal{G}_{20} , \mathbf{f} is additionally attacked by \mathbf{h} . Furthermore, \mathbf{f} defends itself against \mathbf{h} , but it is also defended by \mathbf{c} against \mathbf{h} . However, in terms of the preferred serialisation sequences, this is inconsequential, i. e. it does not matter (within this particular AF) whether \mathbf{f} defends itself against \mathbf{h} or not. Notably, this does play a role when considering a different semantics. We have for instance that \mathcal{F}_{20} and \mathcal{G}_{20} are not serialisation equivalent wrt. grounded semantics, precisely due to the above discussed difference.

Finally, note that for the above considered AFs strong equivalence, and most expansion and deletion equivalences, are not useful since neither AFs contains self-attacks which means these equivalence notions collapse to syntactic identity.

4.1. Semantical Relations under Serialisation Equivalence

In the following, we analyse in detail the relationships between serialisation equivalence wrt. the different semantics in Σ_s . In particular, we investigate for which semantics σ_1 the serialisation equivalence wrt. σ_1 of two argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} implies serialisation equivalence of \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} wrt. another semantics σ_2 .

Table 1 and Theorem 4.1 summarise our results on the relations between all semantics wrt. serialisation equivalence. Interestingly, we have that serialisation equivalence wrt. admissibility and preferred semantics coincide. The same holds true for the strong admissibility and grounded semantics. Analogously to strong equivalence, serialisation equivalence wrt. complete semantics implies serialisation equivalence wrt. admissibility and preferred semantics, a relation that does not hold for standard equivalence. Serialisation equivalence wrt. the unchallenged semantics is implied by admissibility and preferred semantics and thus, by transitivity, also by the complete semantics. This is in contrast to many of the expansion equivalences, where equivalence wrt. unchallenged semantics coincides with admissibility and preferred semantics.

Theorem 4.1. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that*

1. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ad}^{se} \mathcal{G}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{pr}^{se} \mathcal{G}$,
2. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sa}^{se} \mathcal{G}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{gr}^{se} \mathcal{G}$,
3. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ad}^{se} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{uc}^{se} \mathcal{G}$,
4. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{pr}^{se} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{uc}^{se} \mathcal{G}$,
5. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{co}^{se} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{pr}^{se} \mathcal{G}$,
6. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{co}^{se} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ad}^{se} \mathcal{G}$,
7. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{co}^{se} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{uc}^{se} \mathcal{G}$.

Proof: P. 80

All other relations do not hold in general for serialisation equivalence, as shown by the following series of examples. Most notably, while standard (strong) equivalence wrt. grounded semantics is implied by standard (strong) equivalence wrt. complete semantics, this relation does not hold for serialisation equivalence (see also Example 4.5).

In general, the non-implications between semantics come down to how the different types of initial sets are treated by the semantics (see Theorem 2.1). In particular, in Examples 4.4 and 4.5 we have an unattacked initial set in the first AF which is only unchallenged initial in the second AF. That then leads to different serialisation sequences for the semantics where initial sets of these two types are actually treated differently. The grounded and strongly admissible semantics allow only unattacked initial sets to be selected and a serialisation sequence is only in $\mathfrak{S}_{co}(\mathcal{F})$ iff there are no unattacked initial sets left.

\Rightarrow	ad	co	pr	uc	gr	sa	st
ad	✓	✗ ^{4.4}	✓	✓	✗ ^{4.4}	✗ ^{4.4}	✗ ^{C.1}
co	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗ ^{4.5}	✗ ^{4.5}	✗ ^{C.1}
pr	✓	✗ ^{4.4}	✓	✓	✗ ^{4.4}	✗ ^{4.4}	✗ ^{C.1}
uc	✗ ^{4.6}	✗ ^{4.4}	✗ ^{4.6}	✓	✗ ^{4.4}	✗ ^{4.4}	✗ ^{C.1}
gr	✗ ^{4.6}	✗ ^{4.6}	✗ ^{4.6}	✗ ^{4.7}	✓	✓	✗ ^{4.6}
sa	✗ ^{4.6}	✗ ^{4.6}	✗ ^{4.6}	✗ ^{4.7}	✓	✓	✗ ^{4.6}
st	✗ ^{C.2}	✓					

Table 1: Relations between serialisation equivalences wrt. different semantics. For line σ_1 and column σ_2 , the table reads as ‘serialisation equivalence wrt. σ_1 implies serialisation equivalence wrt. σ_2 ’. ✓ indicates that the relation holds for all AFs, as shown in Theorem 4.1, while ✗ indicates that it does not hold and the corresponding superscript refers to the counterexample below.

Example 4.4. Consider the AFs \mathcal{F}_{21} and \mathcal{G}_{21} in Figure 23. We have that \mathcal{F}_{21} and \mathcal{G}_{21} are serialisation equivalent wrt. $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{pr}, \text{uc}\}$, but not serialisation equivalent wrt. $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{gr}, \text{sa}\}$. In particular, the **ad**, **pr** and **uc** serialisation sequences for \mathcal{F}_{21} and \mathcal{G}_{21} are the empty sequence and $(\{a\})$. On the other hand, $(\{a\})$ is a serialisation sequence for **gr** and **sa** in \mathcal{F}_{21} , but not in \mathcal{G}_{21} . Similarly, the empty sequence is complete in \mathcal{G}_{21} but not in \mathcal{F}_{21} .

Figure 23: The AFs \mathcal{F}_{21} and \mathcal{G}_{21} from Example 4.4.

Example 4.5. Consider the AFs \mathcal{F}_{22} and \mathcal{G}_{22} in Figure 24. We have that \mathcal{F}_{22} and \mathcal{G}_{22} are serialisation equivalent wrt. $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{pr}, \text{uc}\}$, but not serialisation equivalent wrt. $\sigma \in \{\text{sa}, \text{gr}\}$. Both AFs have two complete sequences: $(\{c\}, \{b\})$ and $(\{b\}, \{c\})$. However, we have that $(\{b\}) \in \text{is}^{\#}(\mathcal{G}_{22})$ and thus $(\{b\}, \{c\})$ is not a grounded sequence of \mathcal{G}_{22} . Note that $(\{c\}, \{b\})$ is still a grounded serialisation sequence of \mathcal{G}_{22} since in the reduct $\mathcal{G}_{22}^{\{c\}}$ the set $\{b\}$ is then unattacked initial. This highlights nicely the difference that in a complete extension an argument may defend itself, while for the grounded (and

every strongly admissible) extension arguments must always be defended by other arguments in the extension. This information is intrinsically contained in the grounded and strongly admissible serialisation sequences.

Figure 24: The AFs \mathcal{F}_{22} and \mathcal{G}_{22} from Example 4.5.

As the following example shows, for the semantics **gr**, **sa** and **uc** the fact that they disregard challenged initial sets comes into play and rules out an implication to serialisation equivalence wrt. the other semantics.

Example 4.6. Consider the AFs \mathcal{F}_{23} and \mathcal{G}_{23} in Figure 25. We have that \mathcal{F}_{23} and \mathcal{G}_{23} are serialisation equivalent wrt. $\sigma \in \{\mathbf{gr}, \mathbf{uc}, \mathbf{sa}\}$, but not serialisation equivalent wrt. $\sigma \in \{\mathbf{ad}, \mathbf{co}, \mathbf{pr}, \mathbf{st}\}$. \mathcal{F}_{23} has only two **ad** serialisation sequences: the empty sequence and $(\{a\})$. Clearly, for \mathcal{G}_{23} we additionally have multiple sequences containing the challenged initial sets $\{b\}$ or $\{c\}$, e. g., $(\{a\}, \{b\})$ or $(\{c\})$. The same holds for all semantics that allow challenged initial sets to be included.

Figure 25: The AFs \mathcal{F}_{23} and \mathcal{G}_{23} from Example 4.6.

Since the grounded and strongly admissible semantics also disregard unchallenged initial sets, that rules out an implication onto the unchallenged semantics as shown in the following example.

Example 4.7. Consider the AFs \mathcal{F}_{24} and \mathcal{G}_{24} in Figure 26. We have that \mathcal{F}_{24} and \mathcal{G}_{24} are serialisation equivalent wrt. $\sigma \in \{\mathbf{gr}, \mathbf{sa}\}$, but not serialisation equivalent wrt. $\sigma \in \{\mathbf{ad}, \mathbf{co}, \mathbf{pr}, \mathbf{st}, \mathbf{uc}\}$. Note that $\{b\} \in \text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{G}_{24})$ but $\{b\} \notin \text{is}(\mathcal{F}_{24})$. That allows all semantics besides **gr** and **sa** to select it as the first

set in a serialisation sequence. So $(\{c\}, \{b\})$ is a sequence for all semantics, while $(\{b\}, \{c\})$ is a serialisation sequence of \mathcal{G}_{24} but not \mathcal{F}_{24} for *ad*, *co*, *pr*, *st* and *uc*.

Figure 26: The AFs \mathcal{F}_{24} and \mathcal{G}_{24} from Example 4.7.

In summary, we have that serialisation equivalence wrt. strong admissibility coincides with serialisation equivalence wrt. grounded semantics. Dual to that, serialisation equivalence wrt. admissibility and the preferred semantics also coincide. This latter pair of equivalences is also generally implied by serialisation equivalence wrt. complete semantics and also implies serialisation equivalence wrt. the unchallenged semantics. Only serialisation equivalence wrt. stable semantics is completely independent of all other serialisation equivalences. The counterexamples for that can be found in Appendix C.

Finally, a side note on argumentation frameworks without self-attacks or odd cycles is in order. Observe that the counterexamples for all semantics (except stable semantics) do not require any self-attacking arguments or odd cycles. That means, the distinction between the different classes of serialisation equivalence also holds in these restricted classes of argumentation frameworks. Only serialisation equivalence wrt. stable semantics collapses to serialisation equivalence wrt. admissibility. Conversely, strong equivalence (or most other expansion and deletion equivalences) wrt. any semantics $\sigma \in \Sigma$ collapses to syntactic identity in this case. More specifically, without self-attacks strong equivalence does not provide a proper equivalence notion in these AFs at all, while serialisation equivalence still provides a full range of different equivalence classes. The same applies to most of the other expansion and deletion equivalences.

4.2. Relations to other Equivalence Notions

Let us now examine the relationships between serialisation equivalence and the other equivalence notions introduced in Section 2.3. We consider first standard equivalence. As one might expect, since serialisation sequences

are a more fine-grained view into extensions, serialisation equivalence implies standard equivalence in general.

Theorem 4.2. *Let $\sigma \in \Sigma_s$ be a semantics. For any two argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} , if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{se} \mathcal{G}$, then it follows that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma} \mathcal{G}$. Proof: P. 84*

Importantly, the other direction does not hold in general for almost all serialisable semantics, as shown by the following example.

Example 4.8. Consider the argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F}_1 and \mathcal{G}_1 from Figure 1. We have that $\text{pr}(\mathcal{F}_1) = \text{gr}(\mathcal{F}_1) = \text{co}(\mathcal{F}_1) = \text{st}(\mathcal{F}_1) = \text{uc}(\mathcal{F}_1) = \{\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}\}\} = \text{pr}(\mathcal{G}_1) = \text{gr}(\mathcal{G}_1) = \text{co}(\mathcal{G}_1) = \text{st}(\mathcal{G}_1) = \text{uc}(\mathcal{G}_1)$. Thus \mathcal{F}_1 and \mathcal{G}_1 are equivalent wrt. co , pr , gr , st and uc semantics. However, they are not serialisation equivalent wrt. any of those semantics. For all of the above semantics we only have one serialisation sequence for the extension $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}\}$ in \mathcal{F}_1 , namely $(\{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{c}\})$. On the other hand, for \mathcal{G}_1 the only serialisation sequence is $(\{\mathbf{c}\}, \{\mathbf{a}\})$ for all of the above semantics. Thus, $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma} \mathcal{G}$ does not imply $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{se} \mathcal{G}$ in general for $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{pr}, \text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{uc}\}$.

Notably, only for (strong) admissibility does the reverse direction also hold, as stated in Propositions 4.1 and 4.2. This means, standard equivalence and serialisation equivalence wrt. admissibility coincide, along with serialisation equivalence wrt. preferred semantics. The same is true for standard and serialisation equivalence wrt. strong admissibility and serialisation equivalence wrt. grounded semantics.

Proposition 4.1. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. Then it holds that $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{G})$ if and only if $\mathfrak{S}_{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{ad}(\mathcal{G})$. Proof: P. 85*

Proposition 4.2. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. Then it holds that $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{sa}(\mathcal{G})$ if and only if $\mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{G})$. Proof: P. 86*

Before we examine the relations between serialisation equivalence and the expansion and deletion equivalences, we take another look at the different kernels from Equations (1) - (7), that are the basis of many characterisation result for these equivalence notions. As established by Oikarinen and Woltran (2011), an argumentation framework and its kernel possess the same σ -extensions, under the corresponding semantics σ . As it turns out, we can obtain an even stronger result, i. e., an argumentation framework and its κ -kernel even possess the same σ -serialisation sequences.

Lemma 4.1. *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an argumentation framework. Then the following statements hold*

1. $\mathfrak{S}_\sigma(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_\sigma(\mathcal{F}^{\mathfrak{a}\kappa}),$ for $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, uc\},$
2. $\mathfrak{S}_\sigma(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_\sigma(\mathcal{F}^{\mathfrak{g}\kappa}),$ for $\sigma \in \{sa, gr\},$
3. $\mathfrak{S}_{co}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{co}(\mathcal{F}^{c\kappa}).$

Proof: P. 86

The same result can be established for the stronger κ^* -kernels introduced by Baumann (2012a).

Lemma 4.2. *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an argumentation framework. Then the following statements hold*

1. $\mathfrak{S}_\sigma(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_\sigma(\mathcal{F}^{\mathfrak{a}\kappa^*}),$ for $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, uc\},$
2. $\mathfrak{S}_\sigma(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_\sigma(\mathcal{F}^{\mathfrak{g}\kappa^*}),$ for $\sigma \in \{sa, gr\},$
3. $\mathfrak{S}_{co}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{co}(\mathcal{F}^{c\kappa^*}).$

Proof: P. 88

Based on these observations, we can now establish the following relation to serialisation equivalence: In general, the expansion and deletion equivalences imply serialisation equivalence, with some notable exceptions. For the stable semantics, this only holds for update and (local) deletion equivalence. For weak expansion equivalence, this only holds for (strong) admissibility.

Theorem 4.3. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks and $\Sigma' = \Sigma_s \setminus \{st\},$ $\Sigma'' = \Sigma_s \setminus \{co, st\}.$ Then, the following statements hold*

1. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_\sigma^s \mathcal{G},$ then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_\sigma^{se} \mathcal{G},$ for $\sigma \in \Sigma',$*
2. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_\sigma^n \mathcal{G},$ then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_\sigma^{se} \mathcal{G},$ for $\sigma \in \Sigma',$*
3. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_\sigma^{sn} \mathcal{G},$ then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_\sigma^{se} \mathcal{G},$ for $\sigma \in \Sigma',$*
4. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_\sigma^l \mathcal{G},$ then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_\sigma^{se} \mathcal{G},$ for $\sigma \in \Sigma'',$*
5. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_\sigma^{um} \mathcal{G},$ then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_\sigma^{se} \mathcal{G},$ for $\sigma \in \{ad, sa\},$*
6. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_\sigma^{nd} \mathcal{G},$ then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_\sigma^{se} \mathcal{G},$ for $\sigma \in \Sigma',$*
7. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_\sigma^\eta \mathcal{G},$ then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_\sigma^{se} \mathcal{G},$ for $\sigma \in \Sigma_s$ and $\eta \in \{u, d, ld\}.$ *Proof: P. 90**

The reverse directions or the relations for the excluded semantics do not hold, as shown in the following. In particular, serialisation equivalence does not imply strong equivalence or any expansion and deletion equivalence, for any semantics, as illustrated by the following example.

Figure 27: The AFs \mathcal{F}_{25} and \mathcal{G}_{25} which are serialisation equivalent wrt. any $\sigma \in \Sigma_s$, but not strongly equivalent wrt. those semantics.

Example 4.9. We consider the AFs \mathcal{F}_{25} and \mathcal{G}_{25} shown in Figure 27. Note that for any semantics $\sigma \in \Sigma_s$, we have that $\mathcal{F}_{25} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}_{25}$. In particular, the empty sequence, $(\{\mathbf{a}\})$, $(\{\mathbf{c}\})$, $(\{\mathbf{c}\}, \{\mathbf{a}\})$ and $(\{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{c}\})$ are (strongly) admissible for both AFs. The latter two sequences are the only serialisation sequences for the remaining semantics.

For the other equivalence notions, consider the following. Let $\mathcal{H} = (\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{d}\}, \{(\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{a})\})$, representing a strong expansion of \mathcal{F}_{25} and \mathcal{G}_{25} . The reader may verify that $\{\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{d}\} \in \sigma(\mathcal{F}_{25} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$ but $\{\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{d}\} \notin \sigma(\mathcal{G}_{25} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$. Since a strong expansion is by definition a normal expansion and, hence, also an arbitrary expansion, we obtain $\mathcal{F}_{25} \not\equiv_{\sigma}^{\eta} \mathcal{G}_{25}$, for $\eta \in \{\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{sn}\}$. Let $\mathcal{H}' = (\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}\}, \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})\})$, which is a local expansion of $\mathcal{F}_{25} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}_{25}$. We then have $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}\} \in \sigma(\mathcal{G}_{25} \sqcup \mathcal{H}')$ while $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}\} \notin \sigma(\mathcal{F}_{25} \sqcup \mathcal{H}')$, i. e., $\mathcal{F}_{25} \not\equiv_{\sigma}^1 \mathcal{G}_{25}$. For weak expansion equivalence, consider \mathcal{F}_{25} and $\mathcal{G}' = (\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}\}, \{(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b})\})$, for which we have $\mathcal{F}_{25} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}'$. Consider $\mathcal{H}'' = (\{\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{d}\}, \{(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{d})\})$. We then have that these weak expansions of \mathcal{F}_{25} and \mathcal{G}' are not σ -equivalent, i. e., $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{d}\} \in \sigma(\mathcal{F}_{25} \sqcup \mathcal{H}'')$ while $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{d}\} \notin \sigma(\mathcal{G}' \sqcup \mathcal{H}'')$.

Consider the normal deletion of \mathcal{F}_{25} and \mathcal{G}_{25} via $\mathcal{A}^* = \{\mathbf{a}\}$. We have $\{\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}\} \in \sigma(\mathcal{F}_{25}|_{\mathcal{A}_F \setminus \mathcal{A}^*})$ while $\{\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}\} \notin \sigma(\mathcal{G}_{25}|_{\mathcal{A}_G \setminus \mathcal{A}^*})$. Therefore, we have $\mathcal{F}_{25} \not\equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{nd}} \mathcal{G}_{25}$.

Finally, we consider the local deletion of \mathcal{F}_{25} and \mathcal{G}_{25} via $\mathcal{R}^* = \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})\}$. In this case, we have that $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}\}$ is a σ -extension in the deletion of \mathcal{F}_{25} but not of \mathcal{G}_{25} . Since a local deletion is by definition also an update and a general deletion, it follows directly that \mathcal{F}_{25} and \mathcal{G}_{25} are not equivalent wrt. either of these notions.

As the following example shows, for the case of stable semantics strong equivalence does not necessarily imply serialisation equivalence wrt. stable semantics.

Example 4.10. Consider the AFs \mathcal{F}_{26} and \mathcal{G}_{26} in Figure 28. \mathcal{G}_{26} is the $\mathbf{s}\kappa$ -kernel of \mathcal{F}_{26} , thus both AFs are strongly equivalent wrt. stable semantics. However, they are not serialisation equivalent wrt. stable semantics. The only stable serialisation sequence for \mathcal{F}_{26} is $\mathcal{S}_1 = (\{\mathbf{c}\}, \{\mathbf{a}\})$, while \mathcal{G}_{26} has

Figure 28: The AFs \mathcal{F}_{26} and \mathcal{G}_{26} are strongly equivalent wrt. stable semantics but not serialisation equivalent.

two stable serialisation sequences \mathcal{S}_1 and $\mathcal{S}_2 = (\{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{c}\})$. In other words, under strong equivalence, the information that \mathbf{c} defends \mathbf{a} gets lost in the kernel framework while serialisation equivalence takes this into account.

The same applies also to all variants of expansion equivalence as well as normal deletion equivalence, since they are all implied by strong equivalence, in the case of stable semantics, cf. Figure 9e. The only exceptions are update equivalence and (local) deletion equivalence, which do imply serialisation equivalence wrt. stable semantics, simply due to the fact that they coincide with syntactic identity.

For weak expansion equivalence, in Theorem 4.3 we only have a relation to serialisation equivalence for (strong) admissibility. For the remaining semantics no such relation holds, as illustrated in the following example.

Example 4.11. Consider the AFs \mathcal{F}_1 and \mathcal{G}_1 from Figure 1. The reader may verify that \mathcal{F}_1 and \mathcal{G}_1 are weak expansion equivalent wrt. $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{pr}, \text{gr}, \text{st}\}$ since they possess the same σ -extension under every weak expansion. Alternatively, this may also be verified via the characterisation in Proposition 3.8. On the other hand, as already discussed in Example 4.1, \mathcal{F}_1 and \mathcal{G}_1 are not serialisation equivalent wrt. these semantics.

Finally, notice that the above result for local expansion equivalence does not include the complete semantics. This is related to the fact that there exists no characterisation of local expansion equivalence wrt. complete semantics, which makes establishing a relation to serialisation equivalence more difficult. We believe that this relation does also hold for complete semantics, however a formal proof of this is missing at the moment.

Conjecture 4.1. For any two argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} , if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{co}}^1 \mathcal{G}$, then it follows that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{co}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$.

(a) Relations between the different equivalence notions wrt. admissibility.

(b) Relations between the different equivalence notions wrt. $\sigma \in \{\text{pr}, \text{uc}\}$. Note that for unchallenged semantics, weak expansion equivalence has not been characterised.

(c) Relations between the different equivalence notions wrt. strong admissibility.

(d) Relations between the different equivalence notions wrt. grounded semantics.

(e) Relations between the different equivalence notions wrt. stable semantics.

(f) Relations between the different equivalence notions wrt. complete semantics.

Figure 29: Updated overview over the relations between different equivalence notions wrt. the same semantics. Equivalence notions within the same node coincide in general. Dashed outlines denote equivalence notions for which no proper characterisation exists as of yet.

5. The Landscape of Equivalence in Abstract Argumentation

After characterising missing equivalence notions and introducing the novel serialisation equivalence, let us now take a look at the overall picture of the relations between all of these equivalence notions and semantics.

First, we consider the relations between the equivalence notions under each semantics individually, like already shown in Figure 9 earlier in Section 2.3. Figure 29 shows updated diagrams for these relations, now also including serialisation equivalence. Additionally, we provide an overview for the relations under strong admissibility and the unchallenged semantics (see Figures 29c and 29b respectively), based on our analysis in Section 3.

In general, we can say that serialisation equivalence is situated between strong expansion and normal deletion equivalence on the one hand, and standard equivalence on the other hand. That is quite remarkable, given the fact that, on a conceptual level, serialisation equivalence does not really have any connection to normal deletions or strong expansions. The only exception to the above observation is the stable semantics (cf. Figure 29e), for which serialisation equivalence is completely independent of the expansion equivalences as well as normal deletion equivalence. Here, we only have the obvious relation to the trivial update and (local) deletion equivalence. Notably, the relations under strong admissibility are nearly the same as under the grounded semantics, the only difference can be found in the even closer connection between serialisation and standard equivalence, as follows from Proposition 4.2. The unchallenged semantics turns out to have the same relations as the preferred semantics, cf. Figure 29b (besides the fact that weak expansion equivalence for unchallenged is not characterised yet, the relations shown here hold nonetheless).

Putting all of this together, we can construct a comprehensive picture of the whole landscape of equivalence notions and semantics considered in this work. This overview is depicted in Figure 30. Note that we leave out most cases of uncharacterised equivalences to improve readability, namely weak expansion equivalence wrt. $\sigma \in \{\text{uc}, \text{id}, \text{sst}, \text{ea}\}$, since we cannot feasibly investigate their relations to other equivalences. Most counterexamples for the remaining relations have been discussed over the course of this work already, in particular, in Sections 3, 4.1 and 4.2 and the remaining counterexamples can be found in Appendix C.

In Figure 30, we have at the top the strictest equivalence notion in form of update and (local) expansion equivalence wrt. any semantics. This is

expected, since these equivalences collapse to syntactic identity in general. Strong equivalence wrt. complete semantics is then the first non-trivial equivalence notion which also implies all other equivalence notions (except serialisation equivalence wrt. stable semantics).

From left to right, we then have the different semantics grouped by their inter-semantical relations. On the left, the stable semantics which is mostly independent of the other semantics. Only for weak expansion equivalence and strong equivalence do we have an interconnection to other semantics. Next, semi-stable and eager semantics generally behave quite similarly, and in many cases also coincide with the equivalences for admissibility and the related semantics. The next group of semantics consists of admissibility, preferred, unchallenged and ideal semantics which all coincide under most equivalence notions. Only for weak expansion and standard equivalence are these semantics distinguishable. It is also interesting to note that most equivalence notions wrt. admissibility are implied by the same equivalence notion wrt. complete semantics. In particular, this holds for strong, local, strong expansion, normal deletion and serialisation equivalence while it disappears for weak expansion and standard equivalence. This is quite interesting, given the fact that the complete extensions are only a subset of the admissible sets. In other words, under a restrictive enough equivalence notion it is sufficient to verify that the complete extensions are the same in order to conclude that even the admissible sets are equivalent. The implication from complete to preferred semantics does however hold for all equivalence notions, which is to be expected given their definition. The same is true for complete and ideal semantics. For the unchallenged semantics, we can also observe that it can only be distinguished from admissibility under serialisation and standard equivalence. On the right, we then have strong admissibility and the grounded semantics. Again, for both semantics the equivalences coincide for most notions and are only distinct for weak expansion and standard equivalence. There are also strong connections to the complete semantics for most of the equivalence notions.

There is one more fascinating observation that we can make regarding the semantical relationships. For that, consider Figure 31 which shows an excerpt of Figure 30, focused on (strong) admissibility and the preferred and grounded semantics, highlighting the duality between them. Observe that we can basically mirror this on the central column of the equivalence wrt. complete semantics, with some notable exceptions. In other words, admissibility and preferred semantics together behave nearly exactly the same

Figure 30: Comprehensive overview over all equivalence notions and semantics. The nodes represent equivalence notions and multiple notions within the same node means the coincide. An arrow from node X to node Y means that if two AFs are equivalent wrt. X , then they are also equivalent wrt. Y . Dashed outlines denote that the equivalence notion and its relations have not been fully characterised yet.

as strong admissibility and the grounded semantics. This is quite sensible, given the fact that the preferred extensions are the maximal admissible sets, while the grounded extension is the (unique) maximal strongly admissible set (Caminada, 2014). This is also reflected in the definition of the respective serialisation sequences, where the preferred and grounded serialisation sequences are directly defined as the maximal admissible and strongly admissible serialisation sequences respectively, cf. Definition 2.6.

We can however observe two particular differences in Figure 31. For admissibility, local expansion equivalence coincides with strong and normal expansion equivalence, while it is only implied in the case of strong admissibility. Therefore local equivalence does also not imply strong/weak expansion and normal deletion equivalence for strong admissibility. The second interesting difference can be found under our notion of serialisation equivalence, where we do not have an implication between complete semantics and strong admissibility as well as grounded semantics (recall Example 4.5 for a discussion of this). Basically, this comes down to the fact that grounded and strongly admissible serialisation sequences properly take into account the fact that no argument may defend itself, while this cannot necessarily be distinguished in complete extensions.

6. Computational Complexity

To round up our contribution, we consider the computational complexity of equivalence for abstract argumentation. In particular, we first present results for the complexity of deciding the novel notion of serialisation equivalence. Furthermore, we also give results for the complexity of deciding the other equivalence notions, many of which have not been explicitly considered in the literature so far.

In the following, we assume familiarity with the basic concepts of computational complexity, in particular with the basic complexity classes L , P , NP and $coNP$, cf. (Papadimitriou, 1994). We also consider the classes Σ_2^P and Π_2^P . The class $\Sigma_2^P = NP^{NP}$ denotes decision problems that are solvable in polynomial time by a non-deterministic algorithm that has access to an NP -oracle and Π_2^P is the complementary class, i. e., $\Pi_2^P = coNP^{NP}$.

We focus on the complexity of deciding whether two argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} are η -equivalent wrt. a semantics $\sigma \in \Sigma$, where η is some equivalence notion.

Figure 31: View of the relations between equivalences for $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{ad}, \text{pr}, \text{sa}, \text{gr}\}$, highlighting the duality between admissibility and preferred semantics on the one hand, and strong admissibility and the grounded semantics on the other hand.

EQ_σ^η Given $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}_\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{R}_\mathcal{F})$ and $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{A}_\mathcal{G}, \mathcal{R}_\mathcal{G})$,
decide whether $\mathcal{F} \equiv_\sigma^\eta \mathcal{G}$.

We examine first the case of our notion of serialisation equivalence. For that, consider the decision problem coCRED_σ , i. e., deciding whether a given argument \mathbf{a} is not part of any σ -extension of \mathcal{F} .

coCRED_σ Given $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ and $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}$,
decide whether there is no set $S \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ with $\mathbf{a} \in S$.

Note that this is the complement problem of the well-known credulous acceptance problem in argumentation (Dvorák and Dunne, 2018). As it turns out, the problem coCRED_σ can be reduced to the problem of deciding serialisation equivalence wrt. some semantics σ . This puts the problem $\text{EQ}_\sigma^{\text{se}}$ for the grounded semantics and strong admissibility in P , while it is coNP -complete for admissible, preferred, complete and stable semantics, cf. Dunne and Bench-Capon (2002). Additionally, in accordance to Bengel and Thimm (2022), we have that $\text{EQ}_{\text{uc}}^{\text{se}}$ is Π_2^{P} -complete. The results of our analysis are summarised in the following theorem.

Theorem 6.1.

1. $\text{EQ}_\sigma^{\text{se}}$ is coNP -complete, for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{pr}, \text{co}, \text{st}\}$.
2. $\text{EQ}_\sigma^{\text{se}}$ is in P , for $\sigma \in \{\text{sa}, \text{gr}\}$.
3. $\text{EQ}_{\text{uc}}^{\text{se}}$ is Π_2^{P} -complete.

Proof: P. 93

For comparison, we consider the complexity of deciding the other equivalence notions wrt. the relevant semantics. For standard equivalence, most results have already been established in Baumann et al. (2019). Determining standard equivalence wrt. grounded semantics is P -complete, while it is coNP -complete for admissible, complete and stable semantics. Finally, standard equivalence wrt. preferred semantics is Π_2^{P} -complete. The complexity of deciding standard equivalence wrt. strong admissibility (Caminada and Dunne, 2019) and unchallenged semantics (Bengel and Thimm, 2022) have not been considered yet, which we rectify with the following result.

Proposition 6.1.

1. EQ_{sa} is in P ,
2. EQ_{uc} is in Π_2^{P} .

Proof: P. 96

EQ_{uc} is likely to be Π_2^P -hard as well, however a formal proof is missing at the moment.

For strong equivalence, the corresponding decision problem is in L , for any semantics $\sigma \in \Sigma$ (Oikarinen and Woltran, 2011; Baumann et al., 2019). In a similar way, normal, strong and local expansion equivalence are also defined syntactically and can therefore be decided in polynomial time, in almost all cases.

Proposition 6.2.

1. EQ_σ^n is in L ,
2. EQ_σ^s is in L ,
3. EQ_σ^l is in L , for $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, uc, id, sst, ea\}$,
4. EQ_σ^l is in P , for $\sigma \in \{sa, gr\}$,
5. EQ_{st}^l is in $coNP$.

Proof: P. 99

The only exception is local equivalence wrt. stable semantics, which is defined differently (see Oikarinen and Woltran (2011) for more details) and therefore in $coNP$. The computational complexity of deciding local expansion equivalence wrt. complete semantics remains an open question, since a characterisation of this notion is still missing as of yet.

In contrast to that, weak expansion equivalence is characterised semantically and therefore we obtain the same complexity as deciding standard equivalence.

Proposition 6.3.

1. EQ_σ^{wn} is $coNP$ -complete, for $\sigma \in \{ad, co, st\}$,
2. EQ_σ^{wn} is in P , for $\sigma \in \{sa, gr\}$,
3. EQ_{pr}^{wn} is Π_2^P -complete.

Proof: P. 100

Note that since weak expansion equivalence wrt. unchallenged, ideal, eager and semi-stable have not been characterised, the complexity of deciding these equivalences is still an open question.

Finally, update and (local) deletion equivalence coincides with syntactic equivalence and can therefore obviously be decided in polynomial time (with logarithmic space). Only normal deletion equivalence is a bit more interesting, but can still be decided in polynomial time.

Proposition 6.4.

1. EQ_σ^u is in L .
2. EQ_σ^d is in L .
3. EQ_σ^{ld} is in L .
4. EQ_σ^{nd} is in P .

Proof: P. 103

For semi-stable and eager semantics, no characterisation of normal deletion equivalence exists as of yet and therefore the computational complexity remains an open problem.

Table 2 summarises our complexity analysis. All in all, deciding serialisation equivalence is generally as hard as deciding standard equivalence. Only for the preferred semantics, we have that deciding serialisation equivalence is actually easier than deciding standard equivalence. So, while serialisation equivalence is on the same (or better) level of complexity as standard equivalence, it still provides a more fine-grained, semantical equivalence notion that takes the order of argument acceptance into account. On the other hand, strong equivalence and most expansion and deletion equivalences can be decided in polynomial time, which is simply due to the fact that they only rely on syntactical criteria and do not actually take semantical information into account. Weak expansion equivalence is intractable for several semantics and has the same complexity as standard equivalence for any applicable semantics.

7. Conclusion

In this work, we considered equivalence in abstract argumentation. To that end, we introduced the notion of *serialisation equivalence* under which two argumentation frameworks are equivalent if they possess the same set of serialisation sequences wrt. some semantics σ . That enables us to better take into account the procedural aspect of dialectical argumentation by explicitly considering the order in which the conflicts in the argumentation framework must be resolved for an extension to be accepted. Thus, serialisation equivalence represents an equivalence notion based on the actual reasoning inside the argumentation framework and not just the conclusions of this reasoning. Most importantly, we analysed the relationships between several equivalence notions, including serialisation equivalence, standard and strong equivalence (Oikarinen and Woltran, 2011) as well as all variants of expansion and deletion equivalences (Baumann, 2012a, 2014a; Baumann and Brewka, 2018). As it turns out, serialisation equivalence is generally more

	\equiv_{σ}	\equiv_{σ}^{se}	$\equiv_{\sigma}^s, \equiv_{\sigma}^n$	\equiv_{σ}^1	\equiv_{σ}^{sn}	\equiv_{σ}^{wn}	\equiv_{σ}^{nd}	\doteq
ad	coNP-c	coNP-c	in L	in L	in L	coNP-c	in P	in L
co	coNP-c	coNP-c	in L	?	in L	coNP-c	in P	in L
pr	Π_2^P -c	coNP-c	in L	in L	in L	Π_2^P -c	in P	in L
gr	P-c	in P	in L	in P	in L	in P	in P	in L
sa	in P	in P	in L	in P	in L	in P	in P	in L
st	coNP-c	coNP-c	in L	in coNP	in L	coNP-c	in P	in L
uc	in Π_2^P	Π_2^P -c	in L	in L	in L	?	in P	in L
id	?	–	in L	in L	in L	?	in P	in L
sst	?	–	in L	in L	in L	?	?	in L
ea	?	–	in L	in L	in L	?	?	in L

Table 2: Overview over the complexity of deciding the different equivalence notions wrt. the different semantics. A ‘?’ denotes that the corresponding equivalence notion has not been characterised yet, while ‘–’ denotes that the equivalence is not defined for σ . ‘ \doteq ’ represents syntactic identity and thus also the update and (local) deletion equivalences wrt. all semantics. Contributions of this work are highlighted with gray background color.

strict than standard equivalence and less strict than strong equivalence and most of the expansion and deletion equivalences. More specifically, serialisation equivalence is located between normal deletion equivalence and standard equivalence, for all semantics except stable semantics (see Figure 29). The only exception is weak expansion equivalence, which is generally situated in parallel to serialisation equivalence. Notably, for admissibility we have an accordance between serialisation and standard equivalence along with serialisation equivalence wrt. preferred semantics. We can observe exactly the same behaviour for strong admissibility and the grounded semantics. Furthermore, even in argumentation frameworks without self-attacks or odd-cycles, serialisation equivalence yields distinct equivalence notions wrt. the different semantics, which is not the case for strong equivalence. In terms of complexity, we showed that deciding serialisation equivalence wrt. some semantics σ is as hard as deciding whether some argument is not credulously accepted wrt. σ . That means deciding serialisation equivalence is just as complex as standard equivalence, while providing a more fine-grained semantical equivalence notion.

For future work, there remain a couple of open questions regarding the characterisation of some of the expansion and deletion equivalences. In particular, the characterisation of weak expansion equivalence wrt. unchallenged, ideal, semi-stable and eager semantics remains open. The same is true for normal deletion equivalence wrt. semi-stable and eager semantics. Finally, a correct characterisation of local expansion equivalence wrt. complete semantics is also missing. In terms of complexity, there remain open questions regarding the not yet characterised equivalences as well as the hardness results for standard unchallenged equivalence and local stable equivalence. Another promising direction would be extending the approach to other argumentation formalisms. A particularly interesting target would be abstract dialectical frameworks (ADFs) (Brewka and Woltran, 2010; Brewka et al., 2013). Serialisability has recently been introduced for ADFs (Bengel and Thimm, 2025). Therefore, it would be interesting to define serialisation equivalence for ADFs and compare it to the corresponding strong equivalence notion of Heyninck et al. (2022).

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Appendix A. Proofs for Section 3

Standard Equivalence.

Proposition 3.1. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sa} \mathcal{G}$, then it follows that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{gr} \mathcal{G}$.*

Proof. Follows directly from the definition of both semantics. The unique grounded extension is exactly the \subseteq -maximal strongly admissible set. Thus, if \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} possess the same strongly admissible sets, they must also have the same grounded extension. \square

Proposition 3.2. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ad} \mathcal{G}$, then it follows that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{uc} \mathcal{G}$.*

Proof. We utilize results from Section 4 to prove that this result holds. In particular, Proposition 4.1 states that standard equivalence wrt. admissibility coincides with serialisation equivalence wrt. admissibility. As is then shown by Theorem 4.1, every **uc**-serialisation sequence is also an **ad**-serialisation sequence. Hence, $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ad} \mathcal{G}$ implies $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{uc}^{se} \mathcal{G}$. Finally, via Theorem 4.2, we know that serialisation equivalence implies standard equivalence wrt. the same semantics in general. Thus, the claim follows. \square

Theorem 3.1. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that*

1. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ad} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{pr, id, uc\}$,*
2. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{co} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{pr, id, gr\}$,*
3. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sa} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{gr} \mathcal{G}$.*

Proof. Most relations have been shown by Oikarinen and Woltran (2011), Proposition 1. The relation between admissibility and unchallenged semantics is shown in Proposition 3.2 and the relation between strong admissibility and grounded semantics is shown in Proposition 3.1. \square

Strong Equivalence.

Proposition 3.3. *Let \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that $\mathcal{F}^{gk} \doteq \mathcal{G}^{gk}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sa}^s \mathcal{G}$.*

Proof. This follows easily from the proofs of Lemma 6 and Theorem 3 of Oikarinen and Woltran (2011). Their proof shows that $\text{gr}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{gr}(\mathcal{F}^{\text{g}\kappa})$ by demonstrating that (1) $\text{cf}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{cf}(\mathcal{F}^{\text{g}\kappa})$ and (2) for the characteristic functions of \mathcal{F} and $\mathcal{F}^{\text{g}\kappa}$ we have that $\Delta_{\mathcal{F}}(S_i) = \Delta_{\mathcal{F}^{\text{g}\kappa}}(S_i)$ for all i , where $S_0 = \emptyset$ and $S_i = \Delta_{\mathcal{F}}(S_{i-1})$. In particular, that also means we have $\Delta_{\mathcal{F}}(\emptyset) = \Delta_{\mathcal{F}^{\text{g}\kappa}}(\emptyset)$. From the proof of the above statement, it follows directly that the same holds for any $S' \subseteq S_i$, i. e., $\Delta_{\mathcal{F}}(S') = \Delta_{\mathcal{F}^{\text{g}\kappa}}(S')$. Clearly, this implies that the strongly admissible sets are also the same for \mathcal{F} and $\mathcal{F}^{\text{g}\kappa}$. The proof of Theorem 3 from Oikarinen and Woltran (2011) can then directly be applied to the sa semantics. It follows that strong equivalence wrt. strong admissibility is characterised by the grounded kernel. \square

Proposition 3.4. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that $\mathcal{F}^{\text{a}\kappa} \doteq \mathcal{G}^{\text{a}\kappa}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{uc}}^{\text{s}} \mathcal{G}$.*

Proof. We show both directions individually as follows.

“ \Rightarrow ” Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. $\mathcal{F}^{\text{a}\kappa} \doteq \mathcal{G}^{\text{a}\kappa}$ implies $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{ad}}^{\text{s}} \mathcal{G}$ by Theorem 2.2. From $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{ad}}^{\text{s}} \mathcal{G}$, it follows per Definition 2.9 that $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$, for all AFs \mathcal{H} . In other words, we have that $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H} \equiv_{\text{ad}} \mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ for all AFs \mathcal{H} . Per Theorem 4.1, it follows directly that $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H} \equiv_{\text{uc}} \mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ and thus $\text{uc}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \text{uc}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$. Clearly, it follows $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{uc}}^{\text{s}} \mathcal{G}$.

“ \Leftarrow ” Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}), \mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}})$ be argumentation frameworks. From $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{uc}}^{\text{s}} \mathcal{G}$ it follows that $\text{uc}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \text{uc}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$, for every AF \mathcal{H} . Let $\mathcal{H} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{H}})$ be some arbitrary AF. We show that for every $S \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$ it follows that $S \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$ (the other direction follows analogously). Note that this then implies $\mathcal{F}^{\text{a}\kappa} = \mathcal{G}^{\text{a}\kappa}$ via Theorem 2.2. So, for some $S \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$ we have to show the following two conditions hold for S in $\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$:

- (1) S is conflict-free in $\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$, and
- (2) S defends all its members in $\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$.

In the following, we will show that for every case: if the statement $S \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$ does not hold then there exists a construction for some AF \mathcal{H}' such that $\text{uc}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}') \neq \text{uc}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}')$ which contradicts the initial assumption $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{uc}}^{\text{s}} \mathcal{G}$.

to (1): Assume the contrary, i. e., S is not conflict-free in $\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$. That means there exist arguments $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in S$ with $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}}$. We distinguish between two cases:

$$(1.1) \quad \mathbf{a} = \mathbf{b},$$

$$(1.2) \quad \mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{b}.$$

to (1.1): We have that $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}}$ and $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}}$. It follows directly that $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_G$ and $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_F$. Consider the AF $\mathcal{H}' = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}'}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{H}'})$ with

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}'} &= \mathcal{A}_F \cup \mathcal{A}_G \\ \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{H}'} &= \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}'), (\mathbf{a}', \mathbf{a}') \mid \mathbf{a}' \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}'} \setminus \{\mathbf{a}\}\} \end{aligned}$$

In words, in the AF \mathcal{H}' every argument of \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} , except \mathbf{a} , attacks itself and is also attacked by \mathbf{a} . Clearly, we have $\text{uc}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}') = \{\{\mathbf{a}\}\}$ and $\text{uc}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}') = \{\emptyset\}$, which contradicts the assumption that \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are strongly equivalent wrt. unchallenged semantics.

to (1.2): We have $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}}$ since $S \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$. Furthermore, it follows directly that $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}_F$ and $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_G$. Consider the AF $\mathcal{H}' = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}'}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{H}'})$ with

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}'} &= \mathcal{A}_F \cup \mathcal{A}_G \\ \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{H}'} &= \{(\mathbf{a}', \mathbf{a}'), (\mathbf{a}', \mathbf{a}) \mid \mathbf{a}' \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}'} \setminus \{\mathbf{a}\}\} \\ &\quad \cup \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}') \mid \mathbf{a}' \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}'} \setminus \{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}\}\} \end{aligned}$$

In words, in the AF \mathcal{H}' every argument of \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} , except \mathbf{a} , attacks itself and \mathbf{a} , while \mathbf{a} attacks every other argument except \mathbf{b} (and itself). Now we have that $\text{uc}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}') = \{\emptyset\}$ and because of $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_G$ we have $\text{uc}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}') = \{\{\mathbf{a}\}\}$, which contradicts the assumption that \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are strongly equivalent wrt. unchallenged semantics. Hence, S must be conflict-free in $\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$.

to (2): Assume the contrary, i. e., there is some $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}}$ with $\mathbf{a} \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}} S$ and $S \not\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}} \mathbf{a}$. Clearly, if $\mathbf{a} \in S$ it follows from the construction for (1) that we have a contradiction. So, we have that $\mathbf{a} \notin S$. Let $\mathbf{b} \in S$ be the undefended argument. We have that $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}}$ and $(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}}$ for all $\mathbf{c} \in S$.

Now, one of two cases must apply:

(2.1) $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}}$, or

(2.2) $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}}$.

to (2.1): Because of $S \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$, there exists some $\mathbf{c} \in S$ with $(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}}$. Recall that $(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}}$. It follows directly that $(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_G$ and $(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_F$. Clearly, a construction of \mathcal{H}' analogous to that in (1.2) leads to a contradiction.

to (2.2): We have that $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}}$. We have $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}_F$ since $\mathbf{b} \in S$ and $S \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$. We further distinguish between two cases:

(2.2.1) $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}}$,

(2.2.2) $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}}$.

to (2.2.1): We have that $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_G$ and $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}_F$. Clearly, if $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_F$, we can construct some \mathcal{H}' like in (1.1) to arrive at a contradiction. So we assume $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_F$. Consider the AF $\mathcal{H}' = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}'}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{H}'})$ with

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}'} &= \mathcal{A}_F \cup \mathcal{A}_G \\ \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{H}'} &= \{(\mathbf{a}', \mathbf{a}'), (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}') \mid \mathbf{a}' \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}'} \setminus \{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}\}\} \end{aligned}$$

In words, in \mathcal{H}' all arguments, except \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} attack themselves and are attacked by \mathbf{b} . We have that $\text{uc}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}') = \{\{\mathbf{b}\}\}$ and $\text{uc}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}') = \{\emptyset\}$ since \mathbf{b} does not defend itself against \mathbf{a} in $\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}'$.

to (2.2.2): Here, a construction of \mathcal{H}' , analogous to that of (1.2), leads to a contradiction since $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_G$ and $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}_F$.

It follows that S must defend all its members in $\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ and thus S is admissible in $\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$.

Therefore, we have that from $\text{uc}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \text{uc}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$ it follows necessarily that $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$. \square

Theorem 3.2. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that*

1. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ad}^s \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{pr}^s \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{uc}^s \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{id}^s \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sst}^s \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ea}^s \mathcal{G}$,
2. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sa}^s \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{gr}^s \mathcal{G}$,
3. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{co}^s \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^s \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, uc, id, sst, ea, sa, gr, st\}$,
4. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^s \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{st}^s \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, uc, id, sst, ea\}$.

Proof. Item 1 follows directly from Proposition 3.4 and Theorem 2 of Oikarinen and Woltran (2011). Item 2 follows from Proposition 3.3 and Theorem 3 of Oikarinen and Woltran (2011). Items 3 and 4 follow from item 2 (resp. item 1) and Oikarinen and Woltran (2011), Theorem 5, item 2. \square

Normal Expansion Equivalence.

Lemma A.1. Let \mathcal{F} be an argumentation framework. It holds that if $\text{pr}(\mathcal{F}) = \{E\}$, then $\text{uc}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{id}(\mathcal{F}) = \{E\}$.

Proof. We show the statement by considering the characterisation of preferred and unchallenged semantics via serialisation sequences, cf. Theorem 2.1. Recall that preferred serialisation sequences allow any type of initial set to be selected, while unchallenged sequences do not allow challenged initial sets to be selected. Since $E \in \text{pr}(\mathcal{F})$, there must exist a serialisation sequence $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n)$ with $\hat{\mathcal{S}} = E$. Consider first the case $n = 0$, i. e., we have $E = \emptyset$. It follows that $\text{is}(\mathcal{F}) = \emptyset$ and therefore the only unchallenged serialisation sequence is also the empty sequence. Hence, \emptyset is the only unchallenged extension. Assume now that $n > 0$. Let $0 < i \leq n$ be any step of the serialisation sequence \mathcal{S} of E . Assume now that $S_i \in \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}})$, i. e., S_i is a challenged initial set at the point of its selection. That directly implies that there must be some $S' \in \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}})$ with $S_i \neq S'$ and $S_i \mathcal{R} S'$, cf. Thimm (2022). By definition, the initial set S' must then also be selectable for the serialisation sequence. Then, we either have that $(S_1, \dots, S_{i-1}, S')$ is a preferred serialisation sequence, or there must be a continuation of that sequence that will correspond to a preferred extension, which is a superset of $S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1} \cup S'$. Clearly, since S_i and S' attack each other, this must be a different preferred extension, which contradicts the assumption that $\text{pr}(\mathcal{F}) = \{E\}$. Hence, any serialisation sequence \mathcal{S} for the unique preferred extension E only consists of unattacked or unchallenged initial sets. Consequently, this sequence \mathcal{S} is by definition also an unchallenged serialisation sequence and thus $E \in \text{uc}(\mathcal{F})$.

Now, it remains to show that there cannot be another unchallenged extension of \mathcal{F} . Assume that there is an unchallenged extension E' with $E' \subsetneq E$. Then, E' is not a preferred extension, meaning there must exist a challenged initial set $S \in \mathcal{F}^{E'}$. As shown before, this would imply the existence of at least two preferred extensions, which contradicts the assumption. Assume now that $E' \supsetneq E$. It is then easy to see that this contradicts the assumption that $E \in \text{pr}(\mathcal{F})$, since E' represents an admissible superset of E . Finally,

consider the case that neither $E' \subsetneq E$ nor $E' \supsetneq E$. Then it follows immediately that E' or a superset of E' must also be a preferred extension, which again contradicts our assumption.

Finally, $\text{id}(\mathcal{F}) = \{E\}$ follows directly by definition, since the ideal extension is the maximal admissible set contained in each preferred extension (since there is only one preferred extension, the ideal extension must coincide with it). \square

Theorem 3.3. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks and $\sigma \in \Sigma$. It holds that*

$$\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^s \mathcal{G} \text{ if and only if } \mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^n \mathcal{G}.$$

Proof. For the semantics $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{pr}, \text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{id}, \text{sst}, \text{ea}\}$, this was already shown by Baumann (2012a). For the remaining semantics **sa** and **uc**, consider the following.

sa Recall that strong equivalence wrt. strong admissibility coincides with strong equivalence wrt. grounded semantics. The statement follows then easily from the definition of normal expansions and the above observation via the proof of Theorem 11 of Baumann (2012a).

“ \Rightarrow ” Follows directly from the definitions, i. e., a normal expansion is always an expansion and therefore, if two AFs are equivalent under any arbitrary expansion, then they must clearly be equivalent under all normal expansions.

“ \Leftarrow ” We show that $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\text{sa}}^s \mathcal{G}$ implies $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\text{sa}}^n \mathcal{G}$. Assume that $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\text{sa}}^s \mathcal{G}$. Then via Theorem 3.2), we know that $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\text{gr}}^s \mathcal{G}$. Since the above statement holds for **gr**, it follows that $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\text{gr}}^n \mathcal{G}$. Consequently, there exists a normal expansion via \mathcal{H} for \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} , such that $\text{gr}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) \neq \text{gr}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$. By definition, the grounded extension is always a strongly admissible set, hence if two AFs have different grounded extensions, then they must have different strongly admissible sets. It follows directly that $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\text{sa}}^n \mathcal{G}$.

uc Note that in the following we refer to Lemma A.1, which shows that if an AF has a unique preferred extension, then that extension is also the unique unchallenged extension. We show both directions as follows.

“ \Rightarrow ” We have that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^s \mathcal{G}$, i. e., \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are equivalent under any arbitrary expansion. Consequently, they are also equivalent under all normal expansions.

“ \Leftarrow ” Assume that $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{uc}^s \mathcal{G}$. Then, via Proposition 3.4 it follows that $\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa} \neq \mathcal{G}^{a\kappa}$. We show that this implies $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{uc}^n \mathcal{G}$. For that, we follow the proof outline of Theorems 5 and 11 of Baumann (2012a), who showed this for the preferred semantics. We will then utilise Lemma A.1 to easily show that the same holds for the unchallenged semantics. We proceed case by case, as follows.

- (1) $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa}} \neq \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}^{a\kappa}}$. Hence, $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \neq \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$ and w.l.o.g., there exists an argument $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$. Let \mathbf{c} be a fresh argument and denote $B = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cup \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}) \setminus \{\mathbf{a}\}$. We consider the AF \mathcal{H} with

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}} &= B \cup \{\mathbf{c}\}, \\ \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{H}} &= \{(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{b}) \mid \mathbf{b} \in B\}.\end{aligned}$$

Note that $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ and $\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ represent normal expansions of \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} , respectively. If \mathbf{a} is contained in some unchallenged extension E of $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$, then it follows directly that $E \notin \text{uc}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$, since $\mathbf{a} \notin \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} \cup \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}}$ was assumed. If that is not the case, consider $\mathcal{H}' = \mathcal{H} \sqcup (\{\mathbf{a}\}, \emptyset)$. We obtain the unique preferred extension $E = \{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}\}$ of $\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}'$, which is then also the unique unchallenged extension by Lemma A.1. On the other hand, E cannot be an unchallenged extension in $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}'$, since $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H} = \mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}'$. Hence, $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{uc}^n \mathcal{G}$.

- (2) Consider now the case $\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}} \neq \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$ and $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa}} = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}^{a\kappa}}$. Then, w.l.o.g. let $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa}} \setminus \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}^{a\kappa}}$. Let \mathbf{c} be a fresh argument and we define the AF \mathcal{I} with

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{I}} &= \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cup \{\mathbf{c}\}, \\ \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{I}} &= \{(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{c}') \mid \mathbf{c}' \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}\}\}.\end{aligned}$$

- (2.1) Assume $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{b}$. Then, $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$ by definition of the $a\kappa$ -kernel. We then have the unique preferred extension $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}\}$ for $\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{I}$ and the unique preferred extension $\{\mathbf{c}\}$ for $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{I}$. Via Lemma A.1 it then follows that $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{uc}^n \mathcal{G}$. Note that we can assume from now on that \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} (and their kernels) contain the same self-loops.

(2.2) Let $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{b}$ and we have $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}^{\mathbf{a}\kappa}} \setminus \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}^{\mathbf{a}\kappa}}$ and $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$. We distinguish between four cases regarding the presence/absence of the self-loops of \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} in \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} .

(2.2.1) Suppose $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}), (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$. This is impossible, since by definition of the $\mathbf{a}\kappa$ -kernel the attack (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) would have to be deleted in $\mathcal{F}^{\mathbf{a}\kappa}$.

(2.2.2) Suppose $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$ and $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$. Observe that $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$, cf. Equation (2). Hence, $\text{pr}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{I}) = \{\{\mathbf{c}\}\} = \text{uc}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{I})$. For \mathcal{G} , we have three possibilities. First, $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$ and therefore $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$, because of the assumption $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}^{\mathbf{a}\kappa}}$. Second and third, $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$ and (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) may or may not be present in \mathcal{G} . In any case, we have that $\text{pr}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{I}) = \{\{\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}\}\}$ and via Lemma A.1 also $\text{uc}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{I}) = \{\{\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}\}\}$. Consequently, we have $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\text{uc}}^{\mathbf{n}} \mathcal{G}$.

(2.2.3) Suppose $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}), (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$. We deduce $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$ from $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$ and $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}^{\mathbf{a}\kappa}}$. We have to consider four cases regarding the attack (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) . If $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$, then $\text{uc}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{I}) = \{\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}\}\}$. If $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$, then $\text{uc}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{I}) = \{\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}\}\}$ and otherwise $\text{uc}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{I}) = \{\{\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}\}\}$. In both cases we have $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\text{uc}}^{\mathbf{n}} \mathcal{G}$. If $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$, then we have $\text{uc}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{I}) = \{\{\mathbf{c}\}\}$ and therefore $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\text{uc}}^{\mathbf{n}} \mathcal{G}$.

(2.2.4) Suppose $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$ and $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$. Given some fresh argument \mathbf{c} and $B = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}\}$, we consider the AF \mathcal{J} with

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{J}} &= \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cup \{\mathbf{c}\}, \\ \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{J}} &= \{(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{c}') \mid \mathbf{c}' \in B\} \cup \{(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c})\}. \end{aligned}$$

Independently of the attack (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) in \mathcal{F} , we obtain $\text{uc}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{J}) = \{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}\}$. If $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$, we get $\text{uc}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{J}) = \{\emptyset\}$. In case $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$, the unique extension depends on whether \mathbf{a} defends itself in $\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{J}$ or not. If yes, then we have $\text{uc}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{J}) = \{\{\mathbf{a}\}\}$, otherwise we get $\text{uc}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{J}) = \{\emptyset\}$. In any case, we get $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\sigma}^{\mathbf{n}} \mathcal{G}$, concluding the case distinction. \square

Strong Expansion Equivalence.

Proposition 3.5. *Let \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that $\mathcal{F}^{\mathbf{g}\kappa^*} \doteq \mathcal{G}^{\mathbf{g}\kappa^*}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{sa}}^s \mathcal{G}$.*

Proof. This follows from the proofs of Lemma 5 and Theorem 7 of Baumann (2012a). In particular, the proof of Lemma 5 shows that $\text{gr}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{gr}(\mathcal{F}^{\mathbf{g}\kappa^*})$ via the characteristic function, showing that $\Delta_{\mathcal{F}}(S_i) = \Delta_{\mathcal{F}^{\mathbf{g}\kappa^*}}(S_i)$, for $S_0 = \emptyset$ and $S_i = \Delta_{\mathcal{F}}(S_{i-1})$ with $i = 0, \dots, n$. In addition to that, it is easy to see that $\text{cf}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{cf}(\mathcal{F}^{\mathbf{g}\kappa^*})$ holds by definition of the $\mathbf{g}\kappa^*$ kernel. It is then clear that the strongly admissible sets of \mathcal{F} and $\mathcal{F}^{\mathbf{g}\kappa^*}$ are also the same, analogously to Proposition 3.3. The proof of Theorem 7 from Baumann (2012a) can then directly be applied to the **sa** semantics. More specifically, the “ \Rightarrow ” direction follows directly from the above discussed case. The “ \Leftarrow ” direction is then shown via a construction for the case $\mathcal{F}^{\mathbf{g}\kappa^*} \neq \mathcal{G}^{\mathbf{g}\kappa^*}$. The construction then shows that $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\text{gr}}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$, cf. Theorem 7 of Baumann (2012a). Since the grounded extension is per definition a strongly admissible set, it follows immediately that in this case we also have $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\text{sa}}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$. \square

Proposition 3.6. *Let \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that $\mathcal{F}^{\mathbf{a}\kappa^*} \doteq \mathcal{G}^{\mathbf{a}\kappa^*}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{uc}}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$.*

Proof. We show each direction as follows.

“ \Rightarrow ” As follows from Theorem 2.3, that $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$, for any AF \mathcal{H} , such that $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ ($\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$) is a strong normal expansion of \mathcal{F} (\mathcal{G}). It follows then directly via Theorem 3.1 that $\text{uc}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \text{uc}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$.

“ \Leftarrow ” Consider first the following observation: It holds for all AFs \mathcal{F} that $\text{uc}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{uc}(\mathcal{F}^{\mathbf{a}\kappa^*})$. This follows directly from the fact that $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{F}^{\mathbf{a}\kappa^*})$ (see Corollary 2.2) and that in the case of equivalence wrt. admissible sets, it follows that the AFs also possess the same unchallenged extensions, cf. Theorem 3.1. This directions follows via the same construction as in the proof of Baumann (2012a), Theorem 6 with the help of Lemma A.1 and the above observation. More specifically, Baumann (2012a) showed that from $\mathcal{F}^{\mathbf{a}\kappa^*} \neq \mathcal{G}^{\mathbf{a}\kappa^*}$ it follows that $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{pr}, \text{id}\}$. For that they provide a case distinction, and for each case the construction of a strong normal expansion via an AF \mathcal{H} , such that $\sigma(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) \neq \sigma(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$. Importantly, in almost all instances, we have that $\text{pr}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \{E\}$ and $\text{pr}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \{E'\}$ with $E \neq E'$. In

those cases, it follows then via Lemma A.1 that $\text{uc}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \{E\}$ and $\text{uc}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \{E'\}$. Consequently, this means directly $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\text{uc}}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$, in these cases. In the following, we will only discuss those cases, where the above does not apply fully:

- (1) cf. (Baumann, 2012a), Theorem 6, 1st case. We consider the AF $\mathcal{H} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cup \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}, \emptyset)$, under the assumption that there is some $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$ and $\mathbf{a} \notin E$, for any $E \in \text{uc}(\mathcal{F})$. It follows that $\mathbf{a} \notin E'$ for any $E' \in \text{uc}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$. However, $\{\mathbf{a}\} \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$, and since $\{\mathbf{a}\}$ is unattacked in $\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$, it follows directly that it must be contained in every unchallenged extension of $\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ and it follows $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\text{uc}}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$.
- (2) cf. (Baumann, 2012a), Theorem 6, case 2.2.2. We have $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$, \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} contain the same self-loops and we have some attack $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}^{\text{ak}^*}} \setminus \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}^{\text{ak}^*}}$ with $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{b}$. Furthermore we have $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}), (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$ (and the same for $\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$). Then it holds by definition that $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$. We consider the AF \mathcal{I} with

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{I}} &= \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cup \{\mathbf{c}\}, \\ \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{I}} &= \{(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{d}) \mid \mathbf{d} \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}\}\}, \end{aligned}$$

where \mathbf{c} is a fresh argument. We then have to consider two scenarios: $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$, then $\text{pr}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{I}) = \text{uc}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{I}) = \{\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}\}\}$. Otherwise, if $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$, then $\text{pr}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{I}) = \{\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}\}, \{\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}\}\}$. In that case, $\{\mathbf{a}\}$ and $\{\mathbf{b}\}$ are challenged initial sets, and therefore cannot be part of any unchallenged extension. Furthermore \mathbf{c} is unattacked, and attacks all arguments besides \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} . It follows easily that $\{\mathbf{c}\}$ is the only unchallenged extension of $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{I}$. On the other hand, if $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$, then $\text{pr}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{I}) = \text{uc}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{I}) = \{\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}\}\}$. If $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$, then we have $\text{pr}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{I}) = \text{uc}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{I}) = \{\{\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}\}\}$. Thus, in any case we have different unchallenged extensions for the strong normal expansions of \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} and it follows that $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\text{uc}}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$. \square

Theorem 3.4. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that*

1. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{ad}}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{pr}}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{uc}}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{id}}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$,
2. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{sa}}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{gr}}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$,
3. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{sst}}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{ea}}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$,
4. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{co}}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{sn}} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{pr}, \text{id}, \text{uc}, \text{sa}, \text{gr}\}$,

5. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sst}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, id, uc, st\}$,
6. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ea}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, id, uc, st\}$.

Proof. Item 1 follows from the characterisation of strong expansion equivalence wrt. these semantics via the $\mathbf{a}\kappa^*$ kernel, cf. Proposition 3.6 and Theorem 6 of Baumann (2012a). Item 2 follows from the characterisation of strong expansion equivalence wrt. these semantics via the $\mathbf{g}\kappa^*$ kernel, cf. Proposition 3.5 and Theorem 7 of Baumann (2012a). Item 3 was shown in Theorem 5 of Baumann (2012a). We show each of the remaining items as follows.

- (4) If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{co}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, id, uc, sa, gr\}$:

We have that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{co}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$, i. e., it holds that $\text{co}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \text{co}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$ for any AF \mathcal{H} , such that $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ and $\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ are strong normal expansions of \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} respectively. From Theorem 3.1, we know that if two AFs possess the same complete extensions, then they must also possess the same preferred, grounded and ideal extensions. Hence, for these semantics the claim follows. Furthermore, we have that strong expansion equivalence wrt. admissibility, preferred, unchallenged and ideal semantics are all characterised with the same kernel $\mathbf{a}\kappa^*$, cf. Theorem 2.3 and Proposition 3.6. Thus, the claim holds for these semantics. Strong admissibility is characterised with the same kernel $\mathbf{g}\kappa^*$ as the grounded semantics, hence the statement also holds for that.

- (5) **and** (6): Items 5 and 6 follow from the characterisation of strong expansion equivalence wrt. semi-stable (eager) semantics, which is characterised via the $\mathbf{a}\kappa$ -kernel, i. e., it coincides with strong equivalence wrt. admissibility. By definition, strong equivalence wrt. a semantics σ implies strong expansion equivalence wrt. the same semantics, thus the statement holds for admissibility, cf. Figure 9. The same applies to preferred and ideal semantics, for which strong equivalence is also characterised via the $\mathbf{a}\kappa$ -kernel. Strong equivalence wrt. stable semantics coincides with strong expansion equivalence wrt. stable semantics, cf. Figure 9e, which is implied by strong equivalence wrt. admissibility, cf. Theorem 3.2. □

Weak Expansion Equivalence.

Proposition 3.7. *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}})$, $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}})$ be argumentation frameworks. It holds that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{gr}^{wn} \mathcal{G}$ if and only if $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$, $\text{gr}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{gr}(\mathcal{G})$*

and for the unique grounded extension $E \in \text{gr}(\mathcal{F})$, we have that $\mathbf{a} \notin E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}}^+$ iff $\mathbf{a} \notin E \cup E_{\mathcal{G}}^+$.

Proof. The proof follows is analogously to that of the semantics **ad**, **co** and **pr** shown in Theorem 1 of Baumann and Brewka (2018). This proof shows that the statement holds based on splitting results, cf. Baumann (2011), Theorem 2. These results already include the grounded semantics and thus, the proof of Theorem 1 of Baumann and Brewka (2018) can straight-forwardly be applied for the grounded semantics, as follows.

“ \Rightarrow ” In particular, for any AF \mathcal{H} such that $\mathcal{F} \prec_S^W \mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ and $\mathcal{G} \prec_S^N \mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ it follows from Theorem 2 of Baumann (2011) that $E \in \text{gr}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$ implies $E \in \text{gr}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$ and vice versa.

“ \Leftarrow ” For the other direction, assume the contrary, i. e., we first assume that $\text{gr}(\mathcal{F}) \neq \text{gr}(\mathcal{G})$. Consider $E \in \text{gr}(\mathcal{F})$ with $E \notin \text{gr}(\mathcal{G})$. Then, for $\mathcal{H} = (\{\mathbf{d}\}, \emptyset)$, we have that $E \cup \{\mathbf{d}\} \in \text{gr}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$ but $E \cup \{\mathbf{d}\} \notin \text{gr}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$, for some fresh argument \mathbf{d} . Thus, it follows that $\text{gr}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{gr}(\mathcal{G})$.

Assume now that $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \neq \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$ and $\text{gr}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{gr}(\mathcal{G})$. W.l.o.g. let $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$. Then, we know that \mathbf{a} is not contained in the grounded extension. Consider $\mathcal{H} = (\{\mathbf{a}\}, \emptyset)$, then $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H} = \mathcal{F}$ and therefore \mathbf{a} is also not contained in the grounded extension of $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$. On the other hand, $\{\mathbf{a}\}$ is admissible in $\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ and also unattacked and must therefore be contained in the grounded extension of $\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$. Hence, we know that $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$ must hold.

Finally, assume that for the grounded extension $E \in \text{gr}(\mathcal{F})$, the undecided arguments in \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} do not coincide, while the other two conditions hold. W.l.o.g. let $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}$ such that $\mathbf{a} \in E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}}^+$ and $\mathbf{a} \notin E \cup E_{\mathcal{G}}^+$. It is clear that $\mathbf{a} \notin E$, thus we have $\mathbf{a} \in E_{\mathcal{F}}^+$. Consider the AF $\mathcal{H} = (\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}\}, \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})\})$, where \mathbf{b} is a fresh argument. It is easy to see that \mathbf{b} is now defended by E in $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ and thus $E \cup \{\mathbf{b}\} \in \text{gr}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$. On the other hand, since \mathbf{a} is not attacked by E in \mathcal{G} , \mathbf{b} cannot be defended by E , hence we have that $E \cup \{\mathbf{b}\} \notin \text{gr}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$. It follows that $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\text{gr}}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{G}$. \square

Lemma 3.1. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{H} be argumentation frameworks such that $\mathcal{F} \prec_S^W \mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$. If $E \in \text{sa}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$, then $E \cap \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \in \text{sa}(\mathcal{F})$.*

Proof. Follows immediately from the fact that strong admissibility satisfies *Directionality*, cf. Theorem 1 of Baumann (2011). In particular, recall that a weak expansion of \mathcal{F} only adds new arguments and attacks from old arguments to new arguments. It is then clear that $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}$ is an unattacked set within $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ and therefore $E \cap \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}$ is strongly admissible in \mathcal{F} according to the definition of *Directionality* (Baroni and Giacomin, 2007). \square

Proposition 3.8. *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}})$, $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}})$ be argumentation frameworks. It holds that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{sa}}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{G}$ if and only if $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$, $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{sa}(\mathcal{G})$ and for each $E \in \text{sa}(\mathcal{F})$, we have that $\mathbf{a} \notin E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}}^+$ iff $\mathbf{a} \notin E \cup E_{\mathcal{G}}^+$.*

Proof. We show both directions as follows.

“ \Leftarrow ” We have to show that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{sa}}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{G}$, i. e., for any AF \mathcal{H} such that $\mathcal{F} \prec_S^W \mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ and $\mathcal{G} \prec_S^N \mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ we have $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \text{sa}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$. It follows from $E \in \text{sa}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$, via Lemma 3.1, that $E_1 = E \cap \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \in \text{sa}(\mathcal{F})$. From that it follows from our assumption directly that $E_1 \in \text{sa}(\mathcal{G})$. Given the fact that \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} possess the same arguments and that E_1 attacks the same arguments in \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} , in conjunction with the fact that the weak expansion via \mathcal{H} is the same for both AFs, it is then clear that $E \in \text{sa}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$ follows. The other direction follows analogously.

“ \Rightarrow ” For the other direction, assume the contrary, i. e., we first assume that $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F}) \neq \text{sa}(\mathcal{G})$. Consider $E \in \text{sa}(\mathcal{F})$ with $E \notin \text{sa}(\mathcal{G})$. Then, for $\mathcal{H} = (\{\mathbf{d}\}, \emptyset)$, we have that $E \cup \{\mathbf{d}\} \in \text{sa}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$ but $E \cup \{\mathbf{d}\} \notin \text{sa}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$, for some fresh argument \mathbf{d} . Thus, it follows that $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F}) \neq \text{sa}(\mathcal{G})$.

Assume now that $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \neq \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$ and $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{sa}(\mathcal{G})$. W.l.o.g. let $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$. Then, we know that \mathbf{a} is not contained in any strongly admissible set. Consider $\mathcal{H} = (\{\mathbf{a}\}, \emptyset)$, then $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H} = \mathcal{F}$ and therefore \mathbf{a} is also not contained in any strongly admissible set of $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$. On the other hand, $\{\mathbf{a}\}$ is admissible in $\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ and also unattacked and must therefore be strongly admissible in $\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$. Hence, we know that $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$ must hold.

Finally, assume that for some $E \in \text{sa}(\mathcal{F})$, the undecided arguments in \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} do not coincide, while the other two conditions hold. W.l.o.g. let $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}$ such that $\mathbf{a} \in E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}}^+$ and $\mathbf{a} \notin E \cup E_{\mathcal{G}}^+$. It is clear that $\mathbf{a} \notin E$, thus we have $\mathbf{a} \in E_{\mathcal{F}}^+$. Consider the AF $\mathcal{H} = (\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}\}, \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})\})$, where \mathbf{b} is a fresh argument. It is easy to see that \mathbf{b} is now defended by E in $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ and thus $E \cup \{\mathbf{b}\} \in \text{sa}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$. On the other hand,

since \mathbf{a} is not attacked by E in \mathcal{G} , \mathbf{b} cannot be defended by E , hence we have that $E \cup \{\mathbf{b}\} \notin \text{sa}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$. It follows that $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\text{sa}}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{G}$. \square

Theorem 3.5. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that*

1. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{ad}}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{\text{pr}, \text{st}\}$,*
2. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{co}}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{\text{pr}, \text{st}, \text{gr}\}$,*
3. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{pr}}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{st}}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{G}$,*
4. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{sa}}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{gr}}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{G}$.*

Proof. We show each statement individually as follows.

1. Consider first the case of preferred semantics. The statement follows more or less directly from the definition of preferred semantics and the characterisation of weak expansion equivalence due to Baumann and Brewka (2013, 2018). To recall, two AFs \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} are weak expansion equivalent wrt. $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{pr}\}$ iff they share the same set of arguments, have the same σ -extensions and for every σ -extension E , the set of arguments neither included nor rejected by E in \mathcal{F} (resp. \mathcal{G}) is the same (these are also called the undecided arguments in the labeling-based formulation of semantics (Caminada and Gabbay, 2009)). Now, that means we have $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{G})$, which implies directly that $\text{pr}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{pr}(\mathcal{G})$ via Theorem 3.1. Furthermore, it is also easy to see, that the undecided arguments wrt. to each pr -extension are then also the same for \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} . If this were not the case, then, for some $E \in \text{pr}(\mathcal{F})$, there would be some argument $\mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$, such that $\mathbf{b} \notin E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}}^+$, but $\mathbf{b} \in E_{\mathcal{G}}^+$. However, since $E \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{G})$, this contradicts the assumption that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{ad}}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{G}$. Thus, it follows that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{pr}}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{G}$.

For the stable semantics, two AFs \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are weak expansion equivalent iff they have no stable extensions at all, or share the same arguments and the same st -extensions (Baumann, 2011). Let \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} be weak expansion equivalent wrt. admissibility. Then, \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} possess the same arguments, the same admissible sets and for every admissible set E , the set of undecided arguments is the same in \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} . Assume that there is at least one undecided argument for the admissible set E , i. e., we have $E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}}^+ \neq \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$. It follows directly that E is not a stable extension in \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} . On the other hand, if E has no undecided arguments in \mathcal{F} , then it also has no undecided arguments in \mathcal{G} . Hence, E is a stable extension in \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} . Since every stable extension is

by definition an admissible set, no further sets to consider exists and thus it follows that \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are weak expansion equivalent wrt. stable semantics.

2. For the preferred semantics, the statement follows analogously to statement (1), since we have by definition also that $\text{pr}(\mathcal{F}) \subseteq \text{co}(\mathcal{F})$ for any AF \mathcal{F} .

For the stable semantics, it also follows analogously to item (1) since every stable extension is by definition also complete.

For the grounded semantics we can also use the same proof scheme, since from $\text{co}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{co}(\mathcal{G})$ it follows that $\text{gr}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{gr}(\mathcal{G})$ via Theorem 3.1.

3. Follows analogously to item (1) since every stable extension is by definition also preferred.
4. Follows analogously to item (1) since the grounded extension is by definition also strongly admissible. \square

Local Expansion Equivalence.

Proposition 3.9. *For any two argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F} , \mathcal{G} , we have that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{sa}}^l \mathcal{G}$ iff jointly $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$, $\Delta_{\mathcal{F}}(\emptyset) = \Delta_{\mathcal{G}}(\emptyset) = S$, and*

- $(\mathcal{F}^{\{\mathbf{a}\}})^{\text{g}\kappa} \doteq (\mathcal{G}^{\{\mathbf{a}\}})^{\text{g}\kappa}$ for all $\mathbf{a} \in S$, or
- in case $S = \{\mathbf{a}\}$,
 - $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathbf{a}_{\mathcal{F}}^+ = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} \setminus \mathbf{a}_{\mathcal{G}}^+$, both $\mathcal{F}^{\{\mathbf{a}\}}$ and $\mathcal{G}^{\{\mathbf{a}\}}$ are \mathbf{b} -pathological for some \mathbf{b} , and $(\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}^{\{\mathbf{a}\}}}$ iff $(\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}^{\{\mathbf{a}\}}}$ for all \mathbf{d} ; or
 - both $\mathcal{F}^{\{\mathbf{a}\}}$ and $\mathcal{G}^{\{\mathbf{a}\}}$ are self-loop pathological.

Proof. We show both directions as follows, similar to the approach in the proof of Theorem 10 of Oikarinen and Woltran (2011).

“ \Leftarrow ” Consider two AFs $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ and $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}})$. Assume that $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$ and $\Delta_{\mathcal{F}}(\emptyset) = \Delta_{\mathcal{G}}(\emptyset) = S$. If $S = \emptyset$, then $\Delta_{\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}}(\emptyset) = \Delta_{\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}}(\emptyset) = \emptyset$ for any AF $\mathcal{H} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{H}})$ such that $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}} \subseteq \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}$ and thus $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \text{sa}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \{\emptyset\}$. Consequently, it follows that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{sa}}^1 \mathcal{G}$.

Next, assume that $S \neq \emptyset$ and $(\mathcal{F}^{\{\mathbf{a}\}})^{\text{g}\kappa} \doteq (\mathcal{G}^{\{\mathbf{a}\}})^{\text{g}\kappa}$ for all $\mathbf{a} \in S$. Consider some arbitrary $\mathcal{H} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{H}})$ such that $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}} \subseteq \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}$, and $\Delta_{\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}}(\emptyset) = \Delta_{\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}}(\emptyset) = T \subseteq S$. If $T = \emptyset$, then $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \text{sa}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) =$

$\{\emptyset\}$. Therefore, assume $T \neq \emptyset$. By Lemmas 14 and 15 of Oikarinen and Woltran (2011) it follows that

$$\left(\prod_{a \in T} (\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H})^{\{a\}} \right)^{\mathfrak{g}^\kappa} \doteq \left(\prod_{a \in T} (\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})^{\{a\}} \right)^{\mathfrak{g}^\kappa}.$$

Thus $\text{sa}(\prod_{a \in T} (\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H})^{\{a\}}) = \text{sa}(\prod_{a \in T} (\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})^{\{a\}})$ follows from Corollary 3.1. It is easy to see that $\mathcal{F}^S \doteq \prod_{a \in S} \mathcal{F}^{\{a\}}$ (see also Lemma 13 of Oikarinen and Woltran (2011)). Hence, we obtain $\text{sa}((\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})^T) = \text{sa}((\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H})^T)$, for any $T \subseteq S$. Recalling that the arguments defended by T in F are exactly those unattacked in \mathcal{F}^T , it is then clear that $\Delta_{\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}}(\emptyset) = \Delta_{\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}}(\emptyset) = T$ and $\text{sa}((\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})^T) = \text{sa}((\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H})^T)$ imply $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \text{sa}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$ and therefore $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{sa}}^1 \mathcal{G}$, cf. proof of Lemma 13 of Oikarinen and Woltran (2011).

So, suppose $S = \{\mathbf{a}\}$ and assume first that $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathbf{a}_{\mathcal{F}}^+ = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} \setminus \mathbf{a}_{\mathcal{G}}^+$ and both $\mathcal{F}^{\{a\}}$ and $\mathcal{G}^{\{a\}}$ are \mathbf{b} -pathological for some $\mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}$. Then the only argument which is not self-attacking in $\mathcal{F}^{\{a\}}$ and $\mathcal{G}^{\{a\}}$ is \mathbf{b} . Let us consider $\mathcal{H} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{H}})$ such that $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}} \subseteq \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}$. Since $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$ and $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathbf{a}_{\mathcal{F}}^+ = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} \setminus \mathbf{a}_{\mathcal{G}}^+$, the set of arguments attacked by \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{F} is the same as the set of arguments attacked by \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{G} . Now, if \mathbf{a} is attacked in \mathcal{H} , then $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \text{sa}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \{\emptyset\}$. In case \mathbf{a} is not attacked in \mathcal{H} , there are two possibilities:

- (1) \mathbf{a} defends \mathbf{b} in both $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ and $\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$. Then, $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \text{sa}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \{\emptyset, \{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}\}\}$.
- (2) \mathbf{b} is not defended by \mathbf{a} in neither AF and $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \text{sa}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \{\emptyset, \{\mathbf{a}\}\}$.

Finally, we assume that both $\mathcal{F}^{\{a\}}$ and $\mathcal{G}^{\{a\}}$ are self-loop pathological. Now, all arguments in \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} other than \mathbf{a} and those attacked by \mathbf{a} are self-attacking. Given $\mathcal{H} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{H}})$ with $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{H}} \subseteq \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}$, there are two possibilities:

- (1) $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \text{sa}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \{\emptyset, \{\mathbf{a}\}\}$, if \mathbf{a} is not attacked in \mathcal{H} , or
- (2) $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \text{sa}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \{\emptyset\}$, if \mathbf{a} is attacked in \mathcal{H} .

Hence, it follows that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{sa}}^1 \mathcal{G}$.

“ \Rightarrow ” This direction follows immediately from the proof of Oikarinen and Woltran (2011), Theorem 10. They show the inverse direction, i. e. if the conditions are not satisfied, then \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are not local expansion equivalent wrt. grounded semantics. In their proof, they show for any scenario that there exists an AF \mathcal{H} such that $\text{gr}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) \neq \text{gr}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$. Thus, since the grounded extension is also by definition strongly admissible, it follows directly that $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) \neq \text{sa}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$ and therefore $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\text{sa}}^1 \mathcal{G}$. \square

Proposition 3.10. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that $\mathcal{F}^{\text{ak}} \doteq \mathcal{G}^{\text{ak}}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{uc}}^l \mathcal{G}$.*

Proof. The statement follows directly from the proof of Proposition 3.4. For the “ \Rightarrow ”-direction, it follows that $\text{uc}(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}) = \text{uc}(\mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H})$, for any arbitrary expansion via the AF \mathcal{H} . Thus, that also holds for any local expansion $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ of \mathcal{F} .

For the “ \Leftarrow ”-direction, notice that in the proof of Proposition 3.4 every considered expansion $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$ is a local expansion, i. e., no new arguments are added. It follows then that strong equivalence and local expansion equivalence wrt. unchallenged semantics coincide. \square

Theorem 3.7. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that*

1. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{ad}}^l \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{pr}}^l \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{uc}}^l \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{id}}^l \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{sst}}^l \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{ea}}^l \mathcal{G}$,
2. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{sa}}^l \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{gr}}^l \mathcal{G}$,
3. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{co}}^l \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^l \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{pr}, \text{uc}, \text{id}, \text{sst}, \text{ea}, \text{sa}, \text{gr}, \text{st}\}$,
4. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^l \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{st}}^l \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{pr}, \text{uc}, \text{id}, \text{sst}, \text{ea}\}$.

Proof. Item 1 follows from Proposition 3.10 and Theorem 8 of Oikarinen and Woltran (2011). Item 2 follows from Proposition 3.9 and Theorem 10 of Oikarinen and Woltran (2011). Items 3 and 4 follow from items 1 and 2 together with Theorem 12 of Oikarinen and Woltran (2011). \square

Update and (Local) Deletion Equivalence.

Proposition 3.11. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be AFs. Then it holds for any semantics $\sigma \in \{\text{sa}, \text{uc}\}$ that σ satisfies Isolate-Inclusion.*

Proof. This follows easily from the serialisability-based characterisation of both semantics, cf. Theorem 2.1. First of all, it is clear that each isolated

argument $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}$ is unattacked and thus constitutes an unattacked initial set $\{\mathbf{a}\}$ in \mathcal{F} and every possible reduct of \mathcal{F} .

For strong admissibility, only unattacked initial sets may be selected. Since there is no termination criterion, i. e., every sequence of unattacked initial sets is strongly admissible, we can simply create a sequence of unattacked initial sets of all isolated arguments, in arbitrary order, which represents a strongly admissible set containing all isolated arguments.

For the unchallenged semantics, cf. Definition 2.7, unattacked initial sets are also selectable. Furthermore, the termination criterion explicitly requires that $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n}) = \emptyset$. Thus it follows directly that every uc -extension contains all isolated arguments. \square

Theorem 3.8. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks and $\sigma \in \Sigma$. It holds that*

$$\mathcal{F} \equiv_\sigma^u \mathcal{G} \text{ iff } \mathcal{F} \equiv_\sigma^d \mathcal{G} \text{ iff } \mathcal{F} \equiv_\sigma^{ld} \mathcal{G} \text{ iff } \mathcal{F} \doteq \mathcal{G}.$$

Proof. For all semantics, except uc and sa , this has been shown by Baumann (2014a), Theorem 2. For uc and sa the claim follows then from Proposition 3.11 in combination with the fact that uc and sa satisfy *Conflict-Freeness* and *Isolate-Inclusion*, cf. (Bengel and Thimm, 2022) and (Baroni and Giacomin, 2007), and Theorem 2 of Baumann (2014a). \square

Normal Deletion Equivalence.

Proposition 3.12. *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}_\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{R}_\mathcal{F})$, $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{A}_\mathcal{G}, \mathcal{R}_\mathcal{G})$ be argumentation frameworks and $I = \mathcal{A}_\mathcal{F} \cap \mathcal{A}_\mathcal{G}$. It holds that $\text{Loop}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$, $\text{Att}^{\text{co}}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$ and $(\mathcal{F}|_I)^{\text{g}\kappa^*} \doteq (\mathcal{G}|_I)^{\text{g}\kappa^*}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{sa}}^{\text{nd}} \mathcal{G}$.*

Proof. We show both directions as follows.

“ \Rightarrow ” We have that $\text{Loop}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$, $\text{Att}^{\text{co}}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$ and $(\mathcal{F}|_I)^{\text{g}\kappa^*} = (\mathcal{G}|_I)^{\text{g}\kappa^*}$ with $I = \mathcal{A}_\mathcal{F} \cap \mathcal{A}_\mathcal{G}$.

Consider first the case $\mathcal{A}_\mathcal{F} = \mathcal{A}_\mathcal{G}$. Then, we have that $\mathcal{F} = \mathcal{F}|_I$ and $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{G}|_I$. Hence, we have that $\mathcal{F}^{\text{g}\kappa^*} = \mathcal{G}^{\text{g}\kappa^*}$ it follows then via Lemma 13 of Baumann (2014a) that $(\mathcal{F}|_{\mathcal{A}_\mathcal{F} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*})^{\text{g}\kappa^*} = (\mathcal{G}|_{\mathcal{A}_\mathcal{G} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*})^{\text{g}\kappa^*}$, for all \mathcal{A}^* such that $\mathcal{F}|_{\mathcal{A}_\mathcal{F} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*}$ and $\mathcal{G}|_{\mathcal{A}_\mathcal{G} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*}$ are normal deletions of \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} . Then, it follows that $\text{sa}((\mathcal{F}|_{\mathcal{A}_\mathcal{F} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*})^{\text{g}\kappa^*}) = \text{sa}((\mathcal{G}|_{\mathcal{A}_\mathcal{G} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*})^{\text{g}\kappa^*})$ and therefore, via Corollary 3.2, that $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F}|_{\mathcal{A}_\mathcal{F} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*}) = \text{sa}(\mathcal{G}|_{\mathcal{A}_\mathcal{G} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*})$, for all sets \mathcal{A}^* that induce normal deletions for \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} . Hence, we have $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{sa}}^{\text{nd}} \mathcal{G}$.

Thus, we assume now that $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \neq \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$. We denote $\mathcal{F}' = \mathcal{F}|_I$ and $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{G}|_I$. Note first that we have $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{sa}((\mathcal{F}'|_{\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*})^{\mathbf{g}^{\kappa^*}}) = \text{sa}(\mathcal{G}) = \text{sa}((\mathcal{G}'|_{\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*})^{\mathbf{g}^{\kappa^*}})$ for all sets \mathcal{A}^* that constitute a normal deletion. In other words, when considering only the shared arguments, both AFs and all normal deletions of them possess the same strongly admissible sets. Now recall that, by assumption, all non-shared arguments are self-attacking and do not attack any non-self-attacking shared argument. It is then easy to see that no non-shared argument can be accepted and thus defend any argument. Furthermore, the non-shared arguments do not pose any proper attack, since they can only attack self-attacking arguments by assumption. From that, it follows that in any case the strongly admissible sets of \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are the same as those of $\mathcal{F}|_I$ and $\mathcal{G}|_I$. The same applies to all normal deletions. Hence, we have that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{sa}}^{\text{nd}} \mathcal{G}$.

“ \Leftarrow ” We have that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{sa}}^{\text{nd}} \mathcal{G}$, i. e., we have $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F}^*) = \text{sa}(\mathcal{G}^*)$ for every normal deletion \mathcal{F}^* and \mathcal{G}^* of \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} . Via Theorem 3.1, it follows then that $\text{gr}(\mathcal{F}^*) = \text{gr}(\mathcal{G}^*)$ and hence $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{gr}}^{\text{nd}} \mathcal{G}$. From Theorem 16 of Baumann (2014a) it follows then that $\text{Loop}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$, $\text{Att}^{\text{co}}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$ and $(\mathcal{F}|_I)^{\mathbf{g}^{\kappa^*}} = (\mathcal{G}|_I)^{\mathbf{g}^{\kappa^*}}$. \square

Proposition 3.13. *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}})$, $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}})$ be argumentation frameworks, $I = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cap \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$ and $\sigma \in \{\text{pr}, \text{uc}, \text{id}\}$. It holds that $\text{Loop}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$, $\text{Att}^{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$ and $(\mathcal{F}|_I)^{\mathbf{a}^{\kappa^*}} = (\mathcal{G}|_I)^{\mathbf{a}^{\kappa^*}}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{nd}} \mathcal{G}$.*

Proof. We show both directions as follows.

“ \Rightarrow ” We have that $\text{Loop}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$, $\text{Att}^{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$ and $(\mathcal{F}|_I)^{\mathbf{a}^{\kappa^*}} = (\mathcal{G}|_I)^{\mathbf{a}^{\kappa^*}}$. From Theorem 16 of Baumann (2014a) it follows then that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{ad}}^{\text{nd}} \mathcal{G}$, i. e., $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F}^*) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{G}^*)$ for every normal deletion \mathcal{F}^* and \mathcal{G}^* of \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} . Via Theorem 3.1, it follows then that $\sigma(\mathcal{F}^*) = \sigma(\mathcal{G}^*)$, for $\sigma \in \{\text{pr}, \text{id}, \text{uc}\}$, and hence $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{nd}} \mathcal{G}$.

“ \Leftarrow ” We have that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{nd}} \mathcal{G}$. Consider first the case that $\text{Loop}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$ does not hold. W.l.o.g. let $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$ such that $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$. Consider then $\mathcal{A}^* = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cup \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}) \setminus \{\mathbf{a}\}$. Applying this as a normal deletion gives us $\mathcal{F}|_{\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*} = (\{\mathbf{a}\}, \emptyset)$, which means $\sigma(\mathcal{F}') = \{\{\mathbf{a}\}\}$. While for \mathcal{G} , since \mathbf{a} is not contained in \mathcal{G} , we obtain $\mathcal{G}|_{\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*}$ and therefore \emptyset as the unique σ -extension. Hence, we have that $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{nd}} \mathcal{G}$, which is a contradiction.

Secondly, we assume $Loop(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$ holds, but $Att^{ad}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$ does not hold. Then, w.l.o.g. there is some argument $\mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$ and some argument $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cup \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$ with $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$ and $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$. Furthermore, we must have $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$ and $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$. We know by assumption that $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$. Consider then the set $\mathcal{A}^* = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cup \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}) \setminus \{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}\}$, representing a normal deletion. Then, we have that $\mathcal{G}|_{\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*} = (\{\mathbf{a}\}, \emptyset)$ and therefore $\sigma(\mathcal{G}|_{\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*}) = \{\{\mathbf{a}\}\}$. On the other hand, for $\mathcal{F}|_{\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*} = (\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}\}, \{(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}), (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b})\})$. It follows that $\sigma(\mathcal{F}|_{\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*}) = \{\emptyset\}$. Note that for the second conjunct of $Att^{ad}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$ the claim follows analogously. Hence, we have $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{nd}} \mathcal{G}$, which is a contradiction.

Finally, assume that $Loop(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$ and $Att^{ad}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$ hold, but we have $(\mathcal{F}|_I)^{\text{ak}^*} \neq (\mathcal{G}|_I)^{\text{ak}^*}$ with $I = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cap \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$. W.l.o.g. consider some arguments \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} such that $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{(\mathcal{F}|_I)^{\text{ak}^*}} \setminus \mathcal{R}_{(\mathcal{G}|_I)^{\text{ak}^*}}$. We will now show that in any possible attack configuration regarding \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} , this difference regarding the attack (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) will necessarily allow some normal deletion such that the resulting AFs possess different σ -extensions. For, that we follow the general construction of the proof of Theorem 6 in (Baumann, 2012a), which shows that this holds for the case of strong expansions.

- (1) $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{b}$ That means directly that $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$ but $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$, since the kernel never removes self-attacks, cf. Equation (5). Consider then $\mathcal{A}^* = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cup \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} \setminus \{\mathbf{a}\}$. It is then easy to see, that $\{\mathbf{a}\}$ is the unique σ -extension of $\mathcal{G}|_{\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*}$ for all considered semantics. However, since \mathbf{a} is self-attacking in $\mathcal{F}|_{\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*}$, the unique σ -extension is the empty set.
- (2) $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{b}$ We have that $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$ and $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$. We now have to distinguish four cases of the presence and absence of the self-attacks (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) and (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) . Keep in mind that $\mathcal{F}|_I, \mathcal{G}|_I$ and both ak^* -kernels contain the same self-loops.
 - (2.1) $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}), (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$: This case is not possible, because the definition of the ak^* -kernel enforces the deletion of the attack (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) from $\mathcal{F}|_I$ in that case.
 - (2.2) $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}), (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$: Note that $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$ holds, because \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} are not self-attacking and $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}^{\text{ak}^*}}$ was assumed. We have two further distinguish between two scenarios for both \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} :
 - $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$ resp. $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$ Consider the set $\mathcal{A}^* = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cup$

$\mathcal{A}_G \setminus \{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}\}$, i. e., only \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} will remain in the normal deletion of \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} . More specifically, we obtain $\mathcal{F}|_{\mathcal{A}_F \setminus \mathcal{A}^*} = (\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}\}, \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}), (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a})\})$ and $\mathcal{G}|_{\mathcal{A}_G \setminus \mathcal{A}^*} = (\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}\}, \{(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a})\})$. That gives us $\sigma(\mathcal{F}|_{\mathcal{A}_F \setminus \mathcal{A}^*}) = \{\{\mathbf{a}\}, \{\mathbf{b}\}\}$ and $\sigma(\mathcal{G}|_{\mathcal{A}_G \setminus \mathcal{A}^*}) = \{\{\mathbf{b}\}\}$.

$(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_F$ resp. $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_G$ Consider again $\mathcal{A}^* = \mathcal{A}_F \cup \mathcal{A}_G \setminus \{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}\}$. It is then clear that $\{\mathbf{a}\}$ is the only σ -extension of $\mathcal{F}|_{\mathcal{A}_F \setminus \mathcal{A}^*}$, while $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}\}$ is the unique σ -extension for $\mathcal{G}|_{\mathcal{A}_G \setminus \mathcal{A}^*}$.

Thus, in any combination of the above scenarios, we obtain different σ -extensions for the same normal deletion applied to \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} , which shows that \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are not normal deletion equivalent.

(2.3) **$(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_F$ and $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}_F$:** First, we note that $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_F$, because $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_F$ would enforce the deletion of (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) in the $\mathbf{a}\kappa^*$ -kernel of $\mathcal{F}|_I$, contrary to our assumption. Consider again $\mathcal{A}^* = \mathcal{A}_F \cup \mathcal{A}_G \setminus \{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}\}$. We obtain $\{\emptyset\} = \sigma(\mathcal{F}|_{\mathcal{A}_F \setminus \mathcal{A}^*})$. For \mathcal{G} , we have three different configurations wrt. the attacks (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) and (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) to consider: $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}), (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_G$ or $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}), (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_G$ or $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}_G$ and $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_G$. In any case, we obtain $\{\mathbf{b}\} = \sigma(\mathcal{G}|_{\mathcal{A}_G \setminus \mathcal{A}^*})$.

(2.4) **$(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_F$ and $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_F$:** Since $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}\mathbf{a}\kappa^*}$ is assumed, we deduce the existence of some argument $\mathbf{c} \in \mathcal{A}_F$ such that $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}) \in \mathcal{R}_F$ and $\{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}), (\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{a}), (\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{c}), (\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{b})\} \cap \mathcal{R}_F = \emptyset$, cf. the definition of the $\mathbf{a}\kappa^*$ -kernel. Since $(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{c}) \notin \mathcal{R}_F$ it also follows directly that $\mathbf{c} \in \mathcal{A}_G$ and thus $\mathbf{c} \in I$. We have to consider two possibilities for \mathcal{F} : $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_F$ or $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_F$. For the purpose of illustration, both versions of \mathcal{F} are shown in Figure A.32. We consider now the possible configuration of the attacks between $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}$ in \mathcal{G} . If $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) \in \mathcal{R}_G$ or $(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}_G$, this holds since $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}\}$ would not be conflict-free in $\mathcal{G}|_{\mathcal{A}_G \setminus \mathcal{A}^*}$. Hence, we assume $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}), (\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_G$. Since the self-attacks are fixed, four potential attacks and therefore 16 possible configurations remain, as shown in Figure A.33. Note that we can ignore any additional arguments or attacks from those outside arguments, since we will only consider normal deletion which remove all arguments besides $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}$ anyway.

First, we note that \mathcal{G}_6 and \mathcal{G}_{14} are impossible, since $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{G}^{\mathbf{a}\kappa^*}$ was assumed.

Now, we consider the cases \mathcal{G}_2 , \mathcal{G}_9 and \mathcal{G}_{10} . Let $\mathcal{A}^* = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cup \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}) \setminus \{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}\}$. It is then easy to see that $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}\}$ is the unique σ -extension for \mathcal{F}_1 and \mathcal{F}_2 . On the other hand, we have $\{\{\mathbf{a}\}\} = \sigma(\mathcal{G}_2)$, $\{\{\mathbf{c}\}\} = \sigma(\mathcal{G}_9)$ and $\{\emptyset\} = \sigma(\mathcal{G}_{10})$. Hence, under this normal deletion, \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} would have different σ -extensions.

For the remaining cases, we consider $\mathcal{A}^* = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cup \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}) \setminus \{\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}\}$. For \mathcal{F} we obtain that $\{\emptyset\} = \sigma(\mathcal{F}_1|_{\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*}) = \sigma(\mathcal{F}_2|_{\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*})$. On the other hand, we have $\{\{\mathbf{c}\}\} = \sigma(\mathcal{G}_i|_{\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} \setminus \mathcal{A}^*})$ for $i \in \{1, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 11, 12, 13, 15, 16\}$. It follows for all cases that \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} possess different σ -extensions under the normal deletion via \mathcal{A}^* and hence $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{nd}} \mathcal{G}$. \square

Figure A.32: Possible attack configurations for \mathcal{F} in the proof of Proposition 3.13.

Figure A.33: Possible attack configurations for \mathcal{G} in the proof of Proposition 3.13.

Theorem 3.9. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that*

1. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ad}^{\text{nd}} \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{pr}^{\text{nd}} \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{uc}^{\text{nd}} \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{id}^{\text{nd}} \mathcal{G}$,
2. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sa}^{\text{nd}} \mathcal{G}$ iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{gr}^{\text{nd}} \mathcal{G}$,

3. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{co}^{nd} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{nd} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, uc, id, sa, gr\}$.

Proof. Item 1 follows from Proposition 3.13 and Theorem 16 of Baumann (2014a). Item 2 follows from Proposition 3.12 and Theorem 16 of Baumann (2014a). Item 3 follows from items 1 and 2 in combination with Theorem 3.1. In particular, $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{co}^{nd} \mathcal{G}$ implies by definition that $co(\mathcal{F}^*) = co(\mathcal{G}^*)$, for any normal deletion \mathcal{F}^* (\mathcal{G}^*) of \mathcal{F} (\mathcal{G}). Via Theorem 3.1, it follows then directly that $pr(\mathcal{F}^*) = pr(\mathcal{G}^*)$ and $gr(\mathcal{F}^*) = gr(\mathcal{G}^*)$, i. e., it follows that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{pr}^{nd} \mathcal{G}$ and $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{gr}^{nd} \mathcal{G}$. With items 1 and 2, the other relations then follow as well. \square

Appendix B. Proofs for Section 4

Theorem 4.1. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be AFs. It holds that*

1. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ad}^{se} \mathcal{G}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{pr}^{se} \mathcal{G}$,
2. $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{sa}^{se} \mathcal{G}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{gr}^{se} \mathcal{G}$,
3. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ad}^{se} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{uc}^{se} \mathcal{G}$,
4. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{pr}^{se} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{uc}^{se} \mathcal{G}$,
5. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{co}^{se} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{pr}^{se} \mathcal{G}$,
6. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{co}^{se} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ad}^{se} \mathcal{G}$,
7. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{co}^{se} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{uc}^{se} \mathcal{G}$.

Proof. We proof each statement individually as follows:

- $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ad}^{se} \mathcal{G}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{pr}^{se} \mathcal{G}$.

We show both directions of the above statement as follows.

“ \Rightarrow ” It follows from Theorem 2.1, that $\mathfrak{S}_{pr}(\mathcal{F})$ is the subset of $\mathfrak{S}_{ad}(\mathcal{F})$, containing exactly those sequences $(S_1, \dots, S_n) \in \mathfrak{S}_{ad}(\mathcal{F})$ where $is(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n}) = \emptyset$. Taking Definition 4.1 into account, it follows from $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ad}^{se} \mathcal{G}$ that $\mathfrak{S}_{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{ad}(\mathcal{G})$. This results in $\mathfrak{S}_{pr}(\mathcal{F}) \subseteq \mathfrak{S}_{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{ad}(\mathcal{G}) \supseteq \mathfrak{S}_{pr}(\mathcal{G})$.

Let us assume $\mathfrak{S}_{pr}(\mathcal{F}) \neq \mathfrak{S}_{pr}(\mathcal{G})$. This would mean, w.l.o.g., there exists some serialisation sequence $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n) \in \mathfrak{S}_{pr}(\mathcal{F})$ with $\mathcal{S} \notin \mathfrak{S}_{pr}(\mathcal{G})$. Then, one of the following two cases must apply:

- (1) \mathcal{S} is not an admissible serialisation sequence in \mathcal{G} .

That, however, contradicts our initial assumption of $\mathfrak{S}_{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{ad}(\mathcal{G})$.

- (2) \mathcal{S} is not a maximal serialisation sequence in \mathcal{G} , i. e., we have that $\text{is}(\mathcal{G}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n}) \neq \emptyset$. Then, there is some $S' \in \text{is}(\mathcal{G}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n})$ such that (S_1, \dots, S_n, S') is an admissible serialisation sequence of \mathcal{G} . Clearly, because of $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{G})$ it follows that (S_1, \dots, S_n, S') is an admissible serialisation sequence of \mathcal{F} and thus (S_1, \dots, S_n) cannot be a preferred serialisation sequence of \mathcal{F} contradicting our initial assumption.

Therefore, it always holds that $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{G})$ and hence $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{ad}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$ implies $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{pr}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$ for all AFs.

“ \Leftarrow ” If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{pr}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$ it follows from Definition 4.1 that $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{G})$. We now show that for some arbitrary serialisation sequence $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n) \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F})$ it follows that $\mathcal{S} \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{G})$. From $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n) \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F})$ it follows that either

- (1) we have that $\mathcal{S} \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{F})$, or
- (2) there is some $\mathcal{S}' = (S_1, \dots, S_n, T_1, \dots, T_m) \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{F})$.

For (1), it follows directly that $\mathcal{S} \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{G})$ and thus $\mathcal{S} \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{G})$.

For (2), consider the following statement which follows directly from Theorem 1. It holds that $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}) = \{(S_1, \dots, S_i) \mid 1 \leq i \leq n \wedge (S_1, \dots, S_n) \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{F})\}$, i. e., every sub-sequence of a preferred serialisation sequence is an admissible serialisation sequence. Clearly, from $\mathcal{S}' \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{F})$ it follows that $\mathcal{S}' \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{G})$. Together with the above statement and since \mathcal{S} is a sub-sequence of \mathcal{S}' , it follows that $\mathcal{S} \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{G})$.

Therefore, $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{G})$ has to be true and it follows that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{pr}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$ implies $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{ad}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$ for all AFs.

- $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{sa}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{gr}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$.

We show both directions of the above statement as follows.

“ \Rightarrow ” It follows from Theorem 2.1, that $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{gr}}(\mathcal{F})$ is a subset of $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{sa}}(\mathcal{F})$, containing all sequences corresponding to the subset-maximal extensions. Taking Definition 4.1 into account, it follows from $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{sa}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$ that $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{sa}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{sa}}(\mathcal{G})$. This results in $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{gr}}(\mathcal{F}) \subseteq \mathfrak{S}_{\text{sa}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{sa}}(\mathcal{G}) \supseteq \mathfrak{S}_{\text{gr}}(\mathcal{G})$.

Let us assume $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{gr}}(\mathcal{F}) \neq \mathfrak{S}_{\text{gr}}(\mathcal{G})$. Then, w.l.o.g., there must be some serialisation sequence $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n) \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{gr}}(\mathcal{F})$ with $\mathcal{S} \notin$

$\mathfrak{S}_{\text{gr}}(\mathcal{G})$. From $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{sa}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{sa}}(\mathcal{G})$ it follows that \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} have the same strongly admissible extensions and thus also the same grounded extension E_{gr} which means $S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n = E_{\text{gr}}$. Due to $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{sa}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{sa}}(\mathcal{G})$ we also know that $\mathcal{S} \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{sa}}(\mathcal{G})$. Thus, \mathcal{S} must also be a grounded serialisation sequence in \mathcal{G} .

Therefore, it holds that $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{gr}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{gr}}(\mathcal{G})$ and hence $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{sa}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{sa}}(\mathcal{G})$ implies $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{gr}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$ for all AFs.

“ \Leftarrow ” Consider the following statement which follows directly from Theorem 1. It holds that $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{sa}}(\mathcal{F}) = \{(S_1, \dots, S_i) \mid i \leq n \wedge (S_1, \dots, S_n) \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{gr}}(\mathcal{F})\}$, i. e., every sub-sequence of a grounded serialisation sequence is a strongly admissible serialisation sequence. If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{gr}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$ it follows with Definition 4.1 that $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{gr}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{gr}}(\mathcal{G})$.

Let us assume that $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{sa}}(\mathcal{F}) \neq \mathfrak{S}_{\text{sa}}(\mathcal{G})$. In this case, w.l.o.g., there exists some serialisation sequence $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n) \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{sa}}(\mathcal{F})$ with $\mathcal{S} \notin \mathfrak{S}_{\text{sa}}(\mathcal{G})$. Then there must exist a serialisation sequence $\mathcal{S}' = (S_1, \dots, S_n, \dots, S_m) \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{gr}}(\mathcal{F})$ which is maximal. That means we have $\text{is}^\#(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n \cup \dots \cup S_m}) = \emptyset$. Since $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{gr}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{gr}}(\mathcal{G})$ it follows that $\mathcal{S}' \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{gr}}(\mathcal{G})$. Together with the previously stated observation, it follows that \mathcal{S} must be in $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{sa}}(\mathcal{G})$. Therefore, $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{sa}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{sa}}(\mathcal{G})$ must hold and it follows that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{gr}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$ implies $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{sa}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$ for all AFs.

- If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{ad}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{uc}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$.

Consider any two argumentation frameworks $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}})$ and $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}})$ with $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{ad}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$. Then we have that $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{G})$ and due to Proposition 4.1 also $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{G})$. We show now, w.l.o.g., that for any serialisation sequence $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n)$ if $\mathcal{S} \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{uc}}(\mathcal{F})$ then $\mathcal{S} \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{uc}}(\mathcal{G})$. We prove inductively for a sequence (S_1, \dots, S_n) over its length plus 1, i. e., for $i = 1, \dots, n$. Note that for each i we show that the corresponding initial set is either unattacked/unchallenged or challenged in both \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} . This shows, simultaneously, that in each step of the sequence we have an unchallenged serialisation sequence and also that in the final reduct, the termination condition for unchallenged semantics is satisfied in both AFs.

- Consider the base case $i=1$. From $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{G})$ it directly follows that $\text{is}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{is}(\mathcal{G})$. Per definition of the unchallenged semantics, we have that $S_1 \in \text{is}^\#(\mathcal{F}) \cup \text{is}^\#(\mathcal{G})$. Assume the contrary, i. e.,

$S_1 \notin \text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{G}) \cup \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{G})$. Then we must have $S_1 \in \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{G})$ because of $\text{is}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{is}(\mathcal{G})$. That means, there exists some $S' \in \text{is}(\mathcal{G})$ such that $S' \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}} S_1$. Since both S_1 and S' are admissible, it follows that S_1 defends itself against S' in \mathcal{G} , i. e., we have $S_1 \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}} S'$ and thus $S' \in \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{G})$. Because of $\text{is}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{is}(\mathcal{G})$, it follows that $S' \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F})$. Since $S_1 \notin \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F})$ it also follows that $S'_{\mathcal{F}}^+ \cap S_1 = \emptyset$. Consider now the sequence (S', S_1) . We have that $S' \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F})$ and because of $S'_{\mathcal{F}}^+ \cap S_1 = \emptyset$ it also holds that $S_1 \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F}^{S'})$. Thus, (S', S_1) is an admissible serialisation sequence of \mathcal{F} , i. e., $(S', S_1) \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F})$. That means we must have $(S', S_1) \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{G})$. However, we know that $S' \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}} S_1$ which leads to $S_1 \notin \text{is}(\mathcal{G}^{S'})$ and thus a contradiction because of $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{G})$.

- Now consider some arbitrary i with $2 \leq i \leq n$. It holds that $S_i \in \text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}}) \cup \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}})$. Assume this does not hold for \mathcal{G} , i. e., we have $S_i \in \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{G}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}})$. Like in the base case, it follows there exists some $S' \in \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{G}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}})$ which attacks S_i in $\mathcal{G}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}}$. Then, one of the following two cases must apply: (1) $S' \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}})$, or (2) $S' \notin \text{is}(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}})$.

For (1), the contradiction can be shown like in the base case.

For (2), consider the sequence $(S_1, \dots, S_{i-1}, S')$. Clearly, it holds that $S_j \in \text{is}(\mathcal{G}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_j})$ for all j with $1 \leq j < i$ and also that $S' \in \text{is}(\mathcal{G}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}})$. Thus, $(S_1, \dots, S_{i-1}, S')$ is an admissible serialisation sequence of \mathcal{G} . However, because of $S' \notin \text{is}(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}})$ it follows that $(S_1, \dots, S_{i-1}, S') \notin \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F})$ which is a contradiction.

All in all, it follows that if $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{G})$ then $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{uc}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{uc}}(\mathcal{G})$.

- If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{pr}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{uc}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$.

Follows directly from the two proofs above, i. e., serialisation equivalence wrt. admissible and preferred semantics coincide and serialisation equivalence wrt. admissible semantics implies serialisation equivalence wrt. unchallenged semantics.

- If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{co}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{pr}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$.

Consider any two argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} with $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{co}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$. It follows from Theorem 2.1, that $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{F})$ is a subset of $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{F})$, containing

all sequences $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n)$ with $\text{is}(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n}) = \emptyset$. Taking Definition 4.1 into account, it follows from $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{co}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$ that $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{G})$. This results in $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{F}) \subseteq \mathfrak{S}_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{G}) \supseteq \mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{G})$.

Let us assume $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{F}) \neq \mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{G})$. This means, w.l.o.g., there exists some serialisation sequence $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n) \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{F})$ with $\mathcal{S} \notin \mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{G})$. That implies there is some serialisation sequence $\mathcal{S}' \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{G})$ such that \mathcal{S} is a sub-sequence of \mathcal{S}' . However, that also implies $\mathcal{S}' \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{G})$ and thus $\mathcal{S}' \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{F})$. That contradicts our assumption of $\mathcal{S} \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{F})$. Therefore, it holds that $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{G})$ and hence $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{pr}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$.

- If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{co}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{ad}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$.

Follows directly from the fact that serialisation equivalence wrt. admissible and preferred semantics coincide and that serialisation equivalence wrt. complete semantics implies serialisation equivalence wrt. preferred semantics.

- If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{co}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{uc}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$.

Follows directly via transitivity, i. e., serialisation equivalence wrt. complete semantics implies serialisation equivalence wrt. admissible semantics which in turn implies serialisation equivalence wrt. unchallenged semantics. \square

Theorem 4.2. *Let $\sigma \in \Sigma_s$ be a semantics. For any two argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} , if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$, then it follows that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma} \mathcal{G}$.*

Proof. Let σ be a serialisable semantics. We will show that if two argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are serialisation equivalent wrt. σ , then they are also standard equivalent wrt. σ , i. e., it follows from $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$, that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma} \mathcal{G}$.

Assume that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$. From Definition 4.1 it follows directly that $\mathfrak{S}_{\sigma}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\sigma}(\mathcal{G})$. Now, assume the theorem does not hold and we have that $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\sigma} \mathcal{G}$. Per Definition 2.8, that means we have $\sigma(\mathcal{F}) \neq \sigma(\mathcal{G})$. Thus, there must exist some $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ with $E \notin \sigma(\mathcal{G})$, or vice versa. However, since σ is serialisable, it follows from Theorem 2.1 that for any serialisable semantics σ , if we have that $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ then there must exist a serialisation sequence $(S_1, \dots, S_n) \in \mathfrak{S}_{\sigma}(\mathcal{F})$ with $E = S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n$. Since we have that $\mathfrak{S}_{\sigma}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\sigma}(\mathcal{G})$, it follows that $(S_1, \dots, S_n) \in \mathfrak{S}_{\sigma}(\mathcal{G})$ and thus $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{G})$, which contradicts our earlier assumption. Clearly, the same holds for any $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{G})$ with $E \notin \sigma(\mathcal{F})$.

Thus, we have shown that serialisation equivalence implies standard equivalence for every serialisable semantics σ . \square

Proposition 4.1. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{G})$ if and only if $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{G})$.*

Proof. We show both directions of the above statement as follows.

“ \Leftarrow ” This follows directly from Theorem 4.2.

“ \Rightarrow ” For this direction we show, w.l.o.g, that from $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n) \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F})$ it follows that $\mathcal{S} \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{G})$, inductively by the length of the sequence \mathcal{S} . Note that for $n = 0$ this trivially holds because the empty sequence and the empty set are always admissible. Hence, we start with $n = 1$ as the base case.

$n=1$: For a serialisation sequence $(S_1) \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F})$, we know that $S_1 \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F})$ and thus $S_1 \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F})$. Because of $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{G})$, it follows that $S_1 \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{G})$. Clearly, we must have $S_1 \in \text{is}(\mathcal{G})$ because there cannot exist any $S' \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{G})$ with $S' \subsetneq S_1$ and $S' \notin \text{ad}(\mathcal{F})$. Then, we must have that $(S_1) \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{G})$.

$n \Rightarrow n+1$: Let $(S_1, \dots, S_n) \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F})$ be an admissible serialisation sequence of \mathcal{F} . It holds that $(S_1, \dots, S_n) \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{G})$. Consider the serialisation sequence $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_{n+1}) \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F})$. Assume that $\mathcal{S} \notin \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{G})$. Because of $(S_1, \dots, S_n) \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{G})$ it follows that we must have $S_{n+1} \notin \text{is}(G^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n})$. However, since $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{G})$ we know that $S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{G})$ and also $S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{n+1} \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{G})$. That means there exists some admissible serialisation sequence $(S_1, \dots, S_n, T_1, \dots, T_m)$ in \mathcal{G} with $T_1 \cup \dots \cup T_m = S_{n+1}$. It follows that $(S_1, \dots, S_n, T_1) \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{G})$ and thus $S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n \cup T_1 \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{G})$. Via $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{G})$ it follows that $S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n \cup T_1 \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F})$. However, then we must have $T_1 \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n})$. This leads to a contradiction because $T_1 \subsetneq S_{n+1}$ and $S_{n+1} \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n})$. Hence, we have that $\mathcal{S} \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{G})$.

To summarise, we have shown it follows from $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{G})$ that $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{G})$. Together with the other direction, that means it holds that $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{G})$ if and only if $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{G})$. \square

Proposition 4.2. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks. It holds that $sa(\mathcal{F}) = sa(\mathcal{G})$ if and only if $\mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{G})$.*

Proof. Analogously to the proof of Proposition 4.1, we show both directions as follows.

“ \Leftarrow ” This follows directly from Theorem 4.2.

“ \Rightarrow ” For this direction we show, w.l.o.g, that from $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n) \in \mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{F})$ it follows that $\mathcal{S} \in \mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{G})$, inductively by the length of the sequence \mathcal{S} . Note that for $n = 0$ this trivially holds because the empty sequence and the empty set are always strongly admissible. Hence, we start with $n = 1$ as the base case.

$n=1$: For a serialisation sequence $(S_1) \in \mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{F})$, we know that $S_1 \in is^\neq(\mathcal{F})$ and thus $S_1 \in sa(\mathcal{F})$. Because of $sa(\mathcal{F}) = sa(\mathcal{G})$, it follows that $S_1 \in sa(\mathcal{G})$. Clearly, we must have $S_1 \in is^\neq(\mathcal{G})$ because there cannot exist any $S' \in sa(\mathcal{G})$ with $S' \subsetneq S_1$ and $S' \notin sa(\mathcal{F})$. Then, we must have that $(S_1) \in \mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{G})$.

$n \Rightarrow n+1$: Let $(S_1, \dots, S_n) \in \mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{F})$ be a strongly admissible serialisation sequence of \mathcal{F} . It holds that $(S_1, \dots, S_n) \in \mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{G})$. Consider the serialisation sequence $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_{n+1}) \in \mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{F})$. Because of $sa(\mathcal{F}) = sa(\mathcal{G})$ we know that $S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n \in sa(\mathcal{G})$ and also $S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{n+1} \in sa(\mathcal{G})$. Recall that for all unattacked initial sets $S \in is^\neq(H)$ for any AF \mathcal{H} it holds that $|S| = 1$. Because of $(S_1, \dots, S_n) \in \mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{G})$ it now follows directly that we must have $S_{n+1} \in is^\neq(G^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n})$, since there can exist no $S' \in is^\neq(G^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n})$ with $S' \subseteq S_{n+1}$. Hence, it follows that $(S_1, \dots, S_{n+1}) \in \mathfrak{S}_{ad}(\mathcal{G})$.

To summarise, we have shown it follows from $sa(\mathcal{F}) = sa(\mathcal{G})$ that $\mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{G})$. Together with the other direction, that means it holds that $sa(\mathcal{F}) = sa(\mathcal{G})$ if and only if $\mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{G})$. \square

Lemma 4.1. *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an argumentation framework. Then the following statements hold*

1. $\mathfrak{S}_\sigma(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_\sigma(\mathcal{F}^{ak})$, for $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, uc\}$,
2. $\mathfrak{S}_\sigma(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_\sigma(\mathcal{F}^{gk})$, for $\sigma \in \{sa, gr\}$,
3. $\mathfrak{S}_{co}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{co}(\mathcal{F}^{ck})$.

Proof. We show each of the above statements individually as follows:

- $\mathfrak{S}_{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{ad}(\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa})$.

Per Corollary 2.1, we know that $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa})$ holds. Thus, together with Proposition 4.1 it follows directly that $\mathfrak{S}_{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{ad}(\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa})$.

- $\mathfrak{S}_{pr}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{pr}(\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa})$.

We operate under the ad-kernel, thus from Corollary 1 it follows that $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa})$ and $\text{pr}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{pr}(\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa})$. From the above proof, we know that $\mathfrak{S}_{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{ad}(\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa})$. Recall that every preferred serialisation sequence (S_1, \dots, S_n) of \mathcal{F} is also by definition an admissible serialisation sequence of \mathcal{F} . Thus, (S_1, \dots, S_n) is an admissible serialisation sequence in the kernel framework $\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa}$. Assume (S_1, \dots, S_n) were not a preferred serialisation sequence in the kernel framework $\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa}$. That would mean there exists a superset $E' \supset S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n$ which is a preferred extension of the kernel framework $\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa}$, but not of \mathcal{F} . That is not possible, since we have $\text{pr}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{pr}(\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa})$ and thus the lemma holds for the preferred semantics.

- $\mathfrak{S}_{uc}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{uc}(\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa})$.

Per Corollary 2.1 we have that $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa})$. From Proposition 4.1, it follows directly that $\mathfrak{S}_{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{ad}(\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa})$, i. e., we have $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ad}^{se} \mathcal{F}^{a\kappa}$. It follows further from Theorem 4.1 that we have $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{uc}^{se} \mathcal{F}^{a\kappa}$ and thus $\mathfrak{S}_{uc}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{uc}(\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa})$.

- $\mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{F}^{g\kappa})$.

Per Corollary 3.1, we know that $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{sa}(\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa})$ holds. Thus, together with Proposition 4.2 it follows directly that $\mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{F}^{g\kappa})$.

- $\mathfrak{S}_{gr}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{gr}(\mathcal{F}^{g\kappa})$.

Follows directly from the above proofs. From $\mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{F}^{g\kappa})$ we can show analogously to the proof for the preferred semantics that the statement holds. In particular, from the fact that the set of grounded serialisation sequences is exactly the set of those strongly admissible serialisation sequences corresponding to the subset-maximal strongly admissible extension (which is the grounded extension).

- $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{F}^{\text{c}\kappa})$.

Consider the complete kernel $\text{c}\kappa$ from Equation (4). We now show that any attack that is removed in the kernel framework $\mathcal{F}^{\text{c}\kappa}$ does not influence the set of complete serialisation sequences $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{F}^{\text{c}\kappa})$. Assume there exist arguments $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{A}$ with $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}$ such that $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{b}$, $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}$ and $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}$. For the kernel framework $\mathcal{F}^{\text{c}\kappa}$ we then have that $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}^{\text{c}\kappa}$, $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}^{\text{c}\kappa}$ while $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}^{\text{c}\kappa}$. Since \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} are self-attacking, it follows directly that for all complete extensions $E \in \text{co}(\mathcal{F})$ we have that $\mathbf{a} \notin E$ and $\mathbf{b} \notin E$. The same holds for all $E \in \text{co}(\mathcal{F}^{\text{c}\kappa})$. Then, there can exist no S_i with $\mathbf{a} \in S_i$ or $\mathbf{b} \in S_i$ with $1 \leq i \leq n$ such that (S_1, \dots, S_n) is a complete serialisation sequence. Furthermore, this means while \mathbf{a} attacks \mathbf{b} in \mathcal{F} it can never defend some argument $\mathbf{c} \in \mathcal{A}$ in \mathcal{F} . Thus, the removal of (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) in $\mathcal{F}^{\text{c}\kappa}$ does not remove any possible defense between \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{c} . It follows, that the statement holds for the complete semantics. \square

Lemma 4.2. *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an argumentation framework. Then the following statements hold*

1. $\mathfrak{S}_{\sigma}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\sigma}(\mathcal{F}^{\text{a}\kappa*})$, for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{pr}, \text{uc}\}$,
2. $\mathfrak{S}_{\sigma}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\sigma}(\mathcal{F}^{\text{g}\kappa*})$, for $\sigma \in \{\text{sa}, \text{gr}\}$,
3. $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{F}^{\text{c}\kappa*})$.

Proof. We show each of the above statements individually as follows:

1. $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}^{\text{a}\kappa*})$.

Per Corollary 2.2, we know that $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{F}^{\text{a}\kappa*})$ holds. Thus, together with Proposition 4.1 it follows directly that $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}^{\text{a}\kappa*})$.

2. $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{F}^{\text{a}\kappa*})$.

We operate under the $\text{a}\kappa*$ -kernel, thus from item (1) of Corollary 2.2 it follows that $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{F}^{\text{a}\kappa*})$ and $\text{pr}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{pr}(\mathcal{F}^{\text{a}\kappa*})$. From item (1), we know that $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}^{\text{a}\kappa*})$. Recall that every preferred serialisation sequence (S_1, \dots, S_n) of \mathcal{F} is also by definition an admissible serialisation sequence of \mathcal{F} . Thus, (S_1, \dots, S_n) is an admissible serialisation sequence in the kernel framework $\mathcal{F}^{\text{a}\kappa*}$. Assume (S_1, \dots, S_n) were not a preferred serialisation sequence in the kernel framework $\mathcal{F}^{\text{a}\kappa*}$. That would mean there exists a superset $E' \supset S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n$ which is a preferred extension of the kernel framework $\mathcal{F}^{\text{a}\kappa*}$, but not of \mathcal{F} . That is not possible, since we have $\text{pr}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{pr}(\mathcal{F}^{\text{a}\kappa*})$ and thus the lemma holds for the preferred semantics.

$$3. \mathfrak{S}_{uc}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{uc}(\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa*}).$$

Per item (1) of Corollary 2.2 we have that $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa*})$. From Proposition 4.1, it follows directly that $\mathfrak{S}_{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{ad}(\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa*})$, i. e., we have $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{ad}^{se} \mathcal{F}^{a\kappa*}$. It follows further from Theorem 4.1, item (2) that we have $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{uc}^{se} \mathcal{F}^{a\kappa*}$ and thus $\mathfrak{S}_{uc}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{uc}(\mathcal{F}^{a\kappa*})$.

$$4. \mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{F}^{g\kappa*}).$$

Per Corollary 2.2, item (2), we know that $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{sa}(\mathcal{F}^{g\kappa*})$ holds. Thus, together with Proposition 4.2 it follows directly that $\mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{F}^{g\kappa*})$.

$$5. \mathfrak{S}_{gr}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{gr}(\mathcal{F}^{g\kappa*}).$$

Follows directly from the above proofs for items (4) and (2). From $\mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{sa}(\mathcal{F}^{g\kappa*})$ we can show analogously to the proof for the preferred semantics that the statement holds. In particular, from the fact that the set of grounded serialisation sequences is exactly the set of those strongly admissible serialisation sequences corresponding to the subset-maximal strongly admissible extension (which is the grounded extension).

$$6. \mathfrak{S}_{co}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{co}(\mathcal{F}^{c\kappa*}).$$

Consider the $c\kappa*$ -kernel from Equation (7). We now show that any attack that is removed in the kernel framework $\mathcal{F}^{c\kappa*}$ does not influence the set of complete serialisation sequences $\mathfrak{S}_{co}(\mathcal{F}^{c\kappa*})$. Assume there exist arguments $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{A}$ with $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}$ and $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{b}$ such that (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) gets removed by the $c\kappa*$ -kernel. Then, one of the following must apply:

- (1) $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{b}$ and $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}$ and $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}$, or
- (2) $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}$ and $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}$ and for all $\mathbf{c} \in \mathcal{A}$ if $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}) \in \mathcal{R}$ then $\{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}), (\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{a}), (\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{c})\} \cap \mathcal{R} \neq \emptyset$

Case (1) is exactly the $c\kappa$ -kernel described in Equation (4), thus it follows directly from item (3) of Lemma 4.1 that the statement holds. Consider now case (2): We have that $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}^{c\kappa*}$ and also $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}^{c\kappa*}$. Clearly, since \mathbf{b} is self-attacking, there can be no complete extension of $\mathcal{F}^{c\kappa*}$ and also no co-serialisation sequence that contains \mathbf{b} . Assume that \mathbf{a} defends some $\mathbf{c} \in \mathcal{A}$ against \mathbf{b} . We know that $\mathbf{c} \neq \mathbf{a}$ because $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}$. However, by the above condition we must have either (i) \mathbf{a} attacks \mathbf{c} , (ii) \mathbf{c} attacks \mathbf{a} , or (iii) \mathbf{c} attacks itself. In each of these three cases it follows immediately that any set $S \supset \{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}\}$ is not conflict-free and thus cannot be a complete extension. Moreover, the attack (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) can never defend some argument $c \in \mathcal{A}$ and thus does

not influence any defense from \mathbf{a} . It follows that \mathcal{F} and $\mathcal{F}^{c\kappa*}$ must possess the same co-serialisation sequences. \square

Theorem 4.3. *Let \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} be argumentation frameworks and $\Sigma' = \Sigma_s \setminus \{\mathbf{st}\}$, $\Sigma'' = \Sigma_s \setminus \{\mathbf{co}, \mathbf{st}\}$. Then, the following statements hold*

1. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^s \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{se} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \Sigma'$,*
2. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^n \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{se} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \Sigma'$,*
3. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{se} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \Sigma'$,*
4. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^l \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{se} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \Sigma''$,*
5. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{wm} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{se} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \{\mathbf{ad}, \mathbf{sa}\}$,*
6. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{nd} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{se} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \Sigma'$,*
7. *If $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\eta} \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{se} \mathcal{G}$, for $\sigma \in \Sigma_s$ and $\eta \in \{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{d}, \mathbf{ld}\}$.*

Proof. We show the relation for each equivalence notion as follows.

- (1) **Strong Equivalence** Let $\sigma \in \{\mathbf{ad}, \mathbf{pr}, \mathbf{uc}, \mathbf{sa}, \mathbf{gr}, \mathbf{co}\}$ be a semantics. We show that if two argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are strongly equivalent wrt. σ , then they are also serialisation equivalent wrt. σ , i. e., it follows from $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^s \mathcal{G}$, that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{se} \mathcal{G}$.

Assume that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^s \mathcal{G}$. Then it follows from Theorem 2.2 that $\mathcal{F}^{\kappa} = \mathcal{G}^{\kappa}$, for any kernel $\kappa \in \{\mathbf{s}\kappa, \mathbf{a}\kappa, \mathbf{g}\kappa, \mathbf{c}\kappa\}$. That leaves us to show that $\mathfrak{S}_{\sigma}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\sigma}(\mathcal{F}^{\kappa})$, with κ being the respective kernel for the semantics σ , for any argumentation framework \mathcal{F} . This follows for any semantics $\sigma \in \{\mathbf{ad}, \mathbf{pr}, \mathbf{uc}, \mathbf{sa}, \mathbf{gr}, \mathbf{co}\}$ directly from Lemma 4.1.

- (2) **Normal Expansion Equivalence** The statement follows immediately from Theorem 3.3 and item (1). In particular, normal expansion equivalence wrt. σ generally coincides with strong equivalence wrt. σ , which implies serialisation equivalence, as shown in item (1).

- (3) **Strong Expansion Equivalence** Let $\sigma \in \{\mathbf{ad}, \mathbf{pr}, \mathbf{uc}, \mathbf{sa}, \mathbf{gr}, \mathbf{co}\}$ be a semantics. We show that if two argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are strong expansion equivalent wrt. σ , then they are also serialisation equivalent wrt. σ .

Assume that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{sn} \mathcal{G}$. Then it follows from Theorem 2.3 that $\mathcal{F}^{\kappa} = \mathcal{G}^{\kappa}$, for the respective kernel $\kappa \in \{\mathbf{a}\kappa*, \mathbf{g}\kappa*, \mathbf{c}\kappa*\}$. That leaves us to show that $\mathfrak{S}_{\sigma}(\mathcal{F}') = \mathfrak{S}_{\sigma}(\mathcal{F}'^{\kappa})$, with κ being the respective kernel for the semantics σ , for any argumentation framework \mathcal{F}' . This follows for any

semantics $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{pr}, \text{uc}, \text{sa}, \text{gr}, \text{co}\}$ directly from Lemma 4.2. Hence, it follows that $\mathfrak{S}_\sigma(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_\sigma(\mathcal{G})$ and therefore $\mathcal{F} \equiv_\sigma^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$.

- (4) **Local Expansion Equivalence** We consider the semantics separately as follows.

ad,pr,uc Recall that local expansion equivalence wrt. these three semantics coincides and in addition to that also coincides with strong equivalence wrt. these semantics, cf. Theorem 3.2. It follows then directly via item (1) that local equivalence wrt. the above semantics implies serialisation equivalence wrt. these semantics.

sa,gr Note first that local expansion equivalence wrt. strong admissibility and grounded semantics coincide (Theorem 3.7. Furthermore, local expansion equivalence implies standard equivalence by definition (Baumann and Brewka, 2018). Notably, we have that serialisation equivalence and standard equivalence coincide in the case of strong admissibility (Proposition 4.2). Consequently, it follows that local equivalence wrt. strong admissibility (grounded semantics) also implies serialisation equivalence wrt. strong admissibility. Via Theorem 4.1 it follows then that serialisation equivalence wrt. grounded semantics is also implied.

- (5) **Weak Expansion Equivalence** Follows directly from the characterisation of weak expansion equivalence wrt. admissibility. In particular, $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{ad}}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{G}$ if and only if $\mathcal{A}_\mathcal{F} = \mathcal{A}_\mathcal{G}$, $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{ad}(\mathcal{G})$ and for every $E \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F})$ we have that $\mathbf{a} \notin E \cup E_\mathcal{F}^+$ iff $\mathbf{a} \notin E \cup E_\mathcal{G}^+$, cf. (Baumann and Brewka, 2018). The second part of this characterisation implies directly that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{ad}} \mathcal{G}$, which in turn implies $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{ad}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$, via Proposition 4.1.

The case of strong admissibility follows analogously.

- (6) **Normal Deletion Equivalence** We consider the semantics separately as follows.

ad,pr,uc Normal deletion equivalence implies standard equivalence in general (Baumann and Brewka, 2018). Since normal deletion equivalence wrt. **ad**, **pr** and **uc** coincide (Theorem 3.9), it follows that they all imply standard equivalence wrt. admissibility. Standard equivalence wrt. admissibility coincides with serialisation equivalence wrt. admissibility (Proposition 4.1) and preferred

semantics (Theorem 4.1), which in turn also implies serialisation equivalence wrt. unchallenged semantics (Theorem 4.1). Thus, the statement holds for **ad**, **pr** and **uc**.

sa,gr Normal deletion equivalence implies standard equivalence in general (Baumann and Brewka, 2018). Since normal deletion equivalence wrt. **sa** and **gr** coincide (Theorem 3.9), it follows that they both imply standard equivalence wrt. strong admissibility. Now, standard equivalence wrt. strong admissibility coincides with serialisation equivalence wrt. strong admissibility (Proposition 4.2) and grounded semantics (Theorem 4.1). Hence, the claim holds for **sa** and **gr**.

co First of all, we have that the $c\kappa^*$ -kernels applied on the restriction to the shared arguments are equivalent, i. e., $(\mathcal{F}|_I)^{c\kappa^*} = (\mathcal{G}|_I)^{c\kappa^*}$ with $I = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cap \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$. Via Lemma 4.2, it follows that $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{F}|_I) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{co}}((\mathcal{F}|_I)^{c\kappa^*})$ and $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{G}|_I) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{co}}((\mathcal{G}|_I)^{c\kappa^*})$, and therefore $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{F}|_I) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{G}|_I)$. Now, the shared part of both AFs contains the same self-attacks (since kernels do not remove self-attacks) and every non-shared argument must be self-attacking ($\text{Loop}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$). Furthermore, any non-shared argument can only attack other self-attacking arguments (cf. Definition 3.4). It is then easy to see that this does not affect the extension or the serialisation sequences in any way. Hence, $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{F}|_I) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{G})$ and therefore $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{co}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{G}$.

(7) **Update and (Local) Deletion Equivalence** Recall that these equivalence notions all coincide with syntactical equivalence, see Theorem 3.8. If $\mathcal{F} = \mathcal{G}$, then we clearly also have $\mathfrak{S}_{\sigma}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\sigma}(\mathcal{G})$. \square

Appendix C. Counterexamples for Sections 4 and 5

Example C.1. Consider the AFs \mathcal{F}_{27} and \mathcal{G}_{27} in Figure C.34. We have that \mathcal{F}_{27} and \mathcal{G}_{27} are serialisation equivalent wrt. $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{pr}, \text{uc}\}$, but not serialisation equivalent wrt. $\sigma \in \{\text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{sa}\}$. Both AFs have, for instance, two complete sequences: $(\{\mathbf{c}\}, \{\mathbf{b}\})$ and $(\{\mathbf{b}\}, \{\mathbf{c}\})$. However, we have that these two sequences are only stable sequences in \mathcal{G}_{27} , but not in \mathcal{F}_{27} , since \mathbf{a} is not attacked by the sequences.

Figure C.34: The AFs \mathcal{F}_{27} and \mathcal{G}_{27} from Example C.1.

Example C.2. Consider the AFs \mathcal{F}_{28} and \mathcal{G}_{28} in Figure C.35. We have that \mathcal{F}_{28} and \mathcal{G}_{28} are serialisation equivalent wrt. *st*, but not serialisation equivalent wrt. $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{gr}, \text{pr}, \text{uc}, \text{sa}\}$. Both AFs have no stable sequence, while \mathcal{F}_{28} has the sequence $(\{b\})$ for all of the other semantics and \mathcal{G}_{28} only the empty sequence.

Figure C.35: The AFs \mathcal{F}_{28} and \mathcal{G}_{28} from Example C.2.

Appendix D. Proofs for Section 6

Theorem 6.1.

1. EQ_{σ}^{se} is *coNP*-complete, for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{pr}, \text{co}, \text{st}\}$,
2. EQ_{σ}^{se} is in *P*, for $\sigma \in \{\text{sa}, \text{gr}\}$,
3. EQ_{uc}^{se} is Π_2^P -complete.

Proof. We proof each statement individually as follows:

- EQ_{ad}^{se} is *coNP*-complete.

For *coNP*-membership, consider the following non-deterministic algorithm for verifying that two given argumentation frameworks $\mathcal{F}_1 = (\mathcal{A}_1, \mathcal{R}_1)$ and $\mathcal{F}_2 = (\mathcal{A}_2, \mathcal{R}_2)$ are *not* serialisation equivalent. We first

guess a sequence $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n)$ with $S_1, \dots, S_n \subseteq \mathcal{A}_1$ and verify for each S_i ($i = 1, \dots, n$) that S_i is an initial set of $\mathcal{F}_1^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}}$, which can be done in polynomial time (Thimm, 2022). We then verify for each S_i ($i = 1, \dots, n$) that S_i is an initial set of $\mathcal{F}_2^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}}$. If one of the latter verification steps fails, (S_1, \dots, S_n) is then shown to be a serialisation sequence of \mathcal{F}_1 but not \mathcal{F}_2 and it follows $\mathcal{F}_1 \not\equiv_{\text{ad}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{F}_2$.

For **coNP**-hardness, we use the complementary problem of deciding credulous acceptance wrt. admissibility $\text{coCRED}_{\text{ad}}$. Since the problem of deciding whether there is an admissible set S with $\mathbf{a} \in S$ is **NP**-complete, see e. g. (Dvorák and Dunne, 2018), the problem $\text{coCRED}_{\text{ad}}$ is naturally **coNP**-complete. Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ and $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}$ be an instance of $\text{coCRED}_{\text{ad}}$. Let \mathbf{b} be an argument with $\mathbf{b} \notin \mathcal{A}$ and define $\mathcal{F}' = (\mathcal{A}', \mathcal{R}')$ via

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}' &= \mathcal{A} \setminus \{\mathbf{a}\} \cup \{\mathbf{b}\} \\ \mathcal{R}' &= \mathcal{R} \setminus \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}), (\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{a}) \mid \mathbf{c} \in \mathcal{A}\} \cup \{(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}) \mid (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) \in \mathcal{R}\} \cup \\ &\quad \{(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{b}) \mid (\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}\} \end{aligned}$$

In other words, \mathcal{F}' is the same AF as \mathcal{F} , only with the argument \mathbf{a} renamed to \mathbf{b} . We claim that \mathbf{a} is not contained in an admissible set of \mathcal{F} iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{ad}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{F}'$. We show both directions of the above statement individually.

“ \Rightarrow ” We know that \mathbf{a} is not contained in any admissible set of \mathcal{F} . Assume this direction does not hold, i. e., we have that $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\text{ad}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{F}'$. Then, w.l.o.g, there must be a serialisation sequence $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n)$ with $\mathcal{S} \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F})$ and $\mathcal{S} \notin \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}')$, or vice versa. Recall that \mathcal{F}' only differs from \mathcal{F} in the renamed argument \mathbf{b} . Clearly, that means all serialisation sequences that do not contain this argument will be the same for both frameworks. However, per our initial assumption, we know that \mathbf{a} is not in any admissible set of \mathcal{F} and thus \mathbf{b} is not in any admissible set of \mathcal{F}' . Hence, there can be no admissible serialisation sequence containing the argument, therefore both frameworks must have the same set of admissible serialisation sequences and are serialisation equivalent wrt. the admissible semantics.

“ \Leftarrow ” We know that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{ad}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{F}'$ and thus $\mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}) = \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}')$. Assume this direction does not hold and we have that there exists some

$E \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F})$ with $\mathbf{a} \in E$. Then, there must exist at least one admissible serialisation sequence (S_1, \dots, S_n) for \mathcal{F} with $S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n = E$ and $\mathbf{a} \in S_i$ for some $1 \leq i \leq n$. However, since \mathbf{a} is renamed to \mathbf{b} in \mathcal{F}' , it follows that $(S_1, \dots, S_n) \notin \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}')$ and therefore $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_{\text{ad}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{F}'$, which is a contradiction.

- EQ_{pr}^{se} is *coNP*-complete.

Follows directly from Theorem 4.1 and the above statement for admissibility.

- EQ_{gr}^{se} is in *P* and EQ_{sa}^{se} is in *P*. Both problems coincide (see Theorem 4.1) and are also equivalent to standard equivalence under strong admissibility (see Proposition 4.2), for which this problem is in *P*, as shown in Proposition 6.1.
- EQ_{co}^{se} is *coNP*-complete.

For *coNP*-membership, consider the following non-deterministic algorithm for verifying that two given argumentation frameworks $\mathcal{F}_1 = (\mathcal{A}_1, \mathcal{R}_1)$ and $\mathcal{F}_2 = (\mathcal{A}_2, \mathcal{R}_2)$ are *not* serialisation equivalent wrt. complete semantics. We first guess a sequence $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n)$ with $S_1, \dots, S_n \subseteq \mathcal{A}_1$ and verify in polynomial time, as described in the proof for the admissible semantics, that $\mathcal{S} \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}_1)$. Additionally, we verify in polynomial time that $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}_1^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n}) = \emptyset$ via the characteristic function, i. e., we verify that $\Gamma_{\mathcal{F}_1}(S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n) = S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n$. We then verify for each S_i ($i = 1, \dots, n$) that S_i is an initial set of $\mathcal{F}_2^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}}$ and that $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}_2^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n}) = \emptyset$. If one of the latter verification steps fails, (S_1, \dots, S_n) is then shown to be a complete serialisation sequence of \mathcal{F}_1 but not \mathcal{F}_2 and it follows $\mathcal{F}_1 \not\equiv_{co}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{F}_2$.

For *coNP*-hardness, we use the complementary problem of deciding credulous acceptance wrt. complete semantics coCRED_{co} and the proof is analogous to the hardness proof of the EQ_{ad}^{se} problem.

- EQ_{st}^{se} is *coNP*-complete.

For *coNP*-membership, consider the following non-deterministic algorithm for verifying that two given argumentation frameworks $\mathcal{F}_1 = (\mathcal{A}_1, \mathcal{R}_1)$ and $\mathcal{F}_2 = (\mathcal{A}_2, \mathcal{R}_2)$ are *not* serialisation equivalent wrt. stable semantics. We first guess a sequence $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n)$ with $S_1, \dots, S_n \subseteq \mathcal{A}_1$ and verify in polynomial time, as described in the proof for the

admissible semantics, that $\mathcal{S} \in \mathfrak{S}_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}_1)$. Additionally, we verify in polynomial time that $\mathcal{F}_1^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n} = (\emptyset, \emptyset)$. We then verify for each S_i ($i = 1, \dots, n$) that S_i is an initial set of $\mathcal{F}_2^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}}$ and that $\mathcal{F}_2^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n} = (\emptyset, \emptyset)$. If one of the latter verification steps fails, (S_1, \dots, S_n) is then shown to be a stable serialisation sequence of \mathcal{F}_1 but not \mathcal{F}_2 and it follows $\mathcal{F}_1 \not\equiv_{\text{st}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{F}_2$.

For **coNP**-hardness, we use the complementary problem of deciding credulous acceptance wrt. stable semantics $\text{coCRED}_{\text{st}}$ and the proof is analogous to the hardness proof of the $\text{EQ}_{\text{ad}}^{\text{se}}$ problem.

- $\text{EQ}_{\text{uc}}^{\text{se}}$ is Π_2^P -complete.

For Π_2^P -membership, we consider that the complement problem $\text{coEQ}_{\text{uc}}^{\text{se}}$, i. e., the problem of deciding whether two given argumentation frameworks $\mathcal{F}_1 = (\mathcal{A}_1, \mathcal{R}_1)$ and $\mathcal{F}_2 = (\mathcal{A}_2, \mathcal{R}_2)$ are *not* serialisation equivalent wrt. unchallenged semantics. We show that $\text{coEQ}_{\text{uc}}^{\text{se}}$ is in $\text{NP}^{\text{NP}} = \Sigma_2^P = \text{co}\Pi_2^P$. For that we adapt the algorithm for deciding skeptical acceptance wrt. unchallenged semantics from Bengel and Thimm (2022). More specifically, consider the following non-deterministic algorithm. We start by guessing an integer k . For $i = 1, \dots, k$, we iteratively guess a set $S_i \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ and verify that $S_i \in \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}_1^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}}) \cup \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}_1^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}})$. The latter can be accomplished by an **NP**-oracle call, since the problem is **coNP**-complete (Thimm, 2022). Finally, we verify that $\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}_1^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_k}) = \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}_1^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_k}) = \emptyset$, which can be done in $\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}} \subseteq \text{NP}^{\text{NP}}$ (Thimm, 2022). It follows that (S_1, \dots, S_k) is an unchallenged serialisation sequence of \mathcal{F}_1 . We then verify for each S_i ($i = 1, \dots, k$) that S_i is an unattacked or unchallenged initial set of $\mathcal{F}_2^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}}$ and that $\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}_2^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_k}) = \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}_2^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_k}) = \emptyset$. If one of the latter verification steps fails, (S_1, \dots, S_k) is then shown to be an unchallenged serialisation sequence of \mathcal{F}_1 but not \mathcal{F}_2 and it follows $\mathcal{F}_1 \not\equiv_{\text{uc}}^{\text{se}} \mathcal{F}_2$. This algorithm runs in Σ_2^P , so $\text{EQ}_{\text{uc}}^{\text{se}}$ is in Π_2^P .

For Π_2^P -hardness, we use the complementary problem of deciding credulous acceptance wrt. unchallenged semantics $\text{coCRED}_{\text{uc}}$ and the proof is analogous to the hardness proof of the $\text{EQ}_{\text{ad}}^{\text{se}}$ problem. \square

Proposition 6.1.

1. EQ_{sa} is in P ,
2. EQ_{uc} is in Π_2^P .

Proof. We show both statements separately as follows.

Eq_{sa} is in P. Consider the following algorithm for deciding whether two AFs \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are standard equivalent wrt. strong admissibility, which runs in polynomial time. For each AF,

- (1) Compute the grounded extension E_{gr} and let $\Sigma = E_{\text{gr}}$ be a propositional signature.
- (2) For each $\mathbf{a} \in E_{\text{gr}}$ and every attacker $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbf{a}^-$, let $\mathbf{b}_1, \dots, \mathbf{b}_n \in \mathbf{b}^- \cap (E_{\text{gr}} \setminus \{\mathbf{a}\})$ be the defenders of \mathbf{a} against \mathbf{b} in E_{gr} .
 - (2.1) Construct the Horn clause: $\mathbf{a} \rightarrow \mathbf{b}_1 \vee \dots \vee \mathbf{b}_n$. The intuition behind that is, if \mathbf{a} is in some strongly admissible set E , then at least one of its defenders $\mathbf{b}_1, \dots, \mathbf{b}_n$ must be contained in E as well.
- (3) Let $K_{\mathcal{F}}$ be the set of all these clauses for the AF \mathcal{F} , and $K_{\mathcal{G}}$ is the corresponding set for the AF \mathcal{G} .
- (4) Then $K_{\mathcal{F}}$ and $K_{\mathcal{G}}$ have the same set of classical models if and only if \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are equivalent wrt. strong admissibility.

Note that every model of $K_{\mathcal{F}}$ ($K_{\mathcal{G}}$) corresponds exactly to one strongly admissible set of \mathcal{F} (\mathcal{G}) and vice versa. Let $E' \in \text{sa}(\mathcal{F})$. The corresponding interpretation ω is then defined via

$$\omega(\mathbf{a}) = \begin{cases} \text{true} & \text{if } \mathbf{a} \in E', \\ \text{false} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

First note that for every argument $\mathbf{a} \notin E'$, we have $\omega(\mathbf{a}) = \text{false}$ and therefore every corresponding clause will be evaluated to *true*. If $E' = \emptyset$, it is then easy to see that every Horn clause $\mathbf{a} \rightarrow \mathbf{b}_1 \vee \dots \vee \mathbf{b}_n$ is evaluated to *true*, i.e., ω is a model of $K_{\mathcal{F}}$. If $E' = \{\mathbf{a}\}$, \mathbf{a} must be unattacked. Therefore, no clause for \mathbf{a} exists in $K_{\mathcal{F}}$. For any other argument $\mathbf{a}' \in \Sigma \setminus \{\mathbf{a}\}$, we have $\omega(\mathbf{a}') = \text{false}$, hence every possible clause for these arguments is satisfied. It follows again that $\omega \in \text{Mod}_{\Sigma}(K_{\mathcal{F}})$. Now, consider some $\mathbf{a} \in E'$. Then, since E' is strongly admissible, \mathbf{a} is strongly defended by $E' \setminus \{\mathbf{a}\}$. In particular, $E' \setminus \{\mathbf{a}\}$ includes a non-empty subset of the defenders of \mathbf{a} against every attacker \mathbf{b} , hence, the Horn clauses for \mathbf{a} are satisfied by ω . Overall, ω is then a model of $K_{\mathcal{F}}$.

Let $\omega \in \text{Mod}_\Sigma(K_{\mathcal{F}})$. The corresponding set E' is defined as $E' = \{\mathbf{a} \mid \omega(\mathbf{a}) = \text{true}\}$. First of all, note that E' is conflict-free, since $\Sigma(K_{\mathcal{F}})$ contains only arguments contained in the grounded extension. If $E' = \emptyset$, it trivially holds that E' is strongly admissible. Otherwise, for some \mathbf{a} with $\omega(\mathbf{a}) = \text{true}$, that implies that, for every clause, there is some \mathbf{b}_i with $\omega(\mathbf{b}_i) = \text{true}$ and therefore $\mathbf{b}_i \in E'$. By definition, we then know that \mathbf{a} is defended by \mathbf{b}_i against that attacker and since every clause must be satisfied by ω , it follows that \mathbf{a} is defended against every attacker. Furthermore, since \mathbf{a} is by definition not contained in the body of these rules, it follows directly that every \mathbf{a} is strongly defended by $E' \setminus \{\mathbf{a}\}$. Thus, $E' \in \text{sa}(\mathcal{F})$.

Hence, $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{sa}} \mathcal{G}$ if and only if $\text{Mod}_\Sigma(K_{\mathcal{F}}) = \text{Mod}_\Sigma(K_{\mathcal{G}})$. Since deciding equivalence of two Horn formulas is in P^2 , it follows that EQ_{sa} is also in P .

Eq_{uc} is in Π_2^P . For Π_2^P -membership, we consider that the complement problem coEQ_{uc} , i. e., the problem of deciding whether two given argumentation frameworks $\mathcal{F}_1 = (\mathcal{A}_1, \mathcal{R}_1)$ and $\mathcal{F}_2 = (\mathcal{A}_2, \mathcal{R}_2)$ are *not* standard equivalent wrt. unchallenged semantics. We show that coEQ_{uc} is in $\text{NP}^{\text{NP}} = \Sigma_2^P = \text{co}\Pi_2^P$. For that we adapt the algorithm for deciding skeptical acceptance wrt. unchallenged semantics from Bengel and Thimm (2022). More specifically, consider the following non-deterministic algorithm. We start by guessing an integer k . For $i = 1, \dots, k$, we iteratively guess some set $S_i \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ and verify that $S_i \in \text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}_1^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}}) \cup \text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}_1^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}})$. The latter can be accomplished by an NP -oracle call, since the problem is coNP -complete (Thimm, 2022). Finally, we verify that $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}_1^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_k}) = \text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}_1^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_k}) = \emptyset$, which can be done in $\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}} \subseteq \text{NP}^{\text{NP}}$ (Thimm, 2022). It follows that (S_1, \dots, S_k) is an unchallenged serialisation sequence of \mathcal{F}_1 and thus $E = S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_k$ is an unchallenged extension of \mathcal{F}_1 . We then verify for each S_i ($i = 1, \dots, k$) that S_i is an unattacked or unchallenged initial set of $\mathcal{F}_2^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}}$ and that $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}_2^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_k}) = \text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}_2^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_k}) = \emptyset$.

²Deciding whether a Horn formula is satisfiable is in P (Dowling and Gallier, 1984). Furthermore, observe that the negation of a Horn clause $C = x \rightarrow y_1 \vee \dots \vee y_m$ is equivalent to a conjunction of Horn clauses $\neg C \equiv x \wedge \neg y_1 \wedge \dots \wedge \neg y_m$. Given two Horn formulas $H_1 = C_1 \wedge \dots \wedge C_n$ and $H_2 = D_1 \wedge \dots \wedge D_m$, we have $H_1 \equiv H_2$ iff $H_1 \wedge \neg C_i$ is unsatisfiable for all $i = 1, \dots, n$ and $H_2 \wedge \neg D_i$ is unsatisfiable for all $i = 1, \dots, m$.

If one of the latter verification steps fails, E is then shown to be an unchallenged extension of \mathcal{F}_1 but not \mathcal{F}_2 and it follows $\mathcal{F}_1 \not\equiv_{uc} \mathcal{F}_2$. This algorithm runs in Σ_2^P , so EQ_{uc} is in Π_2^P . \square

Proposition 6.2.

1. EQ_σ^n is in L ,
2. EQ_σ^s is in L ,
3. EQ_σ^l is in L , for $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, uc, id, sst, ea\}$,
4. EQ_σ^l is in P , for $\sigma \in \{sa, gr\}$,
5. EQ_{st}^l is in coNP .

Proof. We consider each statement individually as follows.

1. Normal expansion equivalence wrt. any semantics can be characterised with the strong equivalence kernels for the respective semantics. Checking the equivalence of two kernels can be done in polynomial time with logarithmic space, cf. Oikarinen and Woltran (2011); Baumann et al. (2019).
2. Strong expansion equivalence is characterised by the modified kernels $\mathbf{a}\kappa^*$, $\mathbf{g}\kappa^*$, $\mathbf{c}\kappa^*$ and the $\mathbf{s}\kappa$ -kernel and it is easy to see that deciding whether two AFs have the same kernel can then be done in polynomial time with logarithmic space, since we only ever need to consider two arguments at the same time to determine whether some argument is redundant wrt. the kernel or only contained in one of the AFs.
3. The characterisation of local expansion equivalence wrt. $\sigma \in \{ad, pr, uc, id, sst, ea\}$ coincides with strong equivalence and is therefore in L , cf. Oikarinen and Woltran (2011).
4. For strong admissibility and grounded semantics, consider the following. First of all, we have to verify that $\mathcal{A}_\mathcal{F} = \mathcal{A}_\mathcal{G}$ and that $\Delta_\mathcal{F}(\emptyset) = \Delta_\mathcal{G}(\emptyset)$. Both of these checks can be done in polynomial time. Then, one of two conditions needs to be checked:
 - (1) $(\mathcal{F}^{\{a\}})^{\mathbf{g}\kappa} \doteq (\mathcal{G}^{\{a\}})^{\mathbf{g}\kappa}$, for all $\mathbf{a} \in \Delta_\mathcal{F}(\emptyset)$.
Verifying the syntactic equivalence of two AFs can be done in polynomial time, and we have to perform a linear number of those checks. Hence, this condition can be verified in polynomial time.
 - (2) Alternatively, if there is exactly one unattacked argument \mathbf{a} in both \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} , we have to check whether \mathbf{a} attacks the same arguments

in both AFs and if the reducts wrt. $\{\mathbf{a}\}$ are \mathbf{b} -pathological and \mathbf{b} is attacked by some argument \mathbf{d} in both AFs. By considering Definition 3.1, we can see that this can be done in polynomial time.

If this is not the case, we need to check whether the AFs $\mathcal{F}^{\{\mathbf{a}\}}$ and $\mathcal{G}^{\{\mathbf{a}\}}$ are self-loop pathological (cf. Definition 3.1), which can also be done in polynomial time.

Overall, we only have to perform various polynomial time checks, which means the problem can be decided in polynomial time for strong admissibility and grounded semantics.

5. For stable semantics, local equivalence is characterised in Theorem 9 of (Oikarinen and Woltran, 2011). It requires to check whether \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are strongly equivalent, or satisfy some other conditions. Two AFs \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are local expansion equivalent iff

- $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\text{st}}^s \mathcal{G}$, or
- $\text{st}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{st}(\mathcal{G}) = \emptyset$ and there is $\mathbf{a} \in (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \setminus \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}) \cup (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}} \setminus \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}})$ such that $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$, $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$ and for all $\mathbf{b} \in (\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cup \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}) \setminus \{\mathbf{a}\}$, we have $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \notin \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}} \cup \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$ and $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}} \cap \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{G}}$.

The first case can be decided in polynomial time. However, in the second case, we need to verify whether $\text{st}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{st}(\mathcal{G}) = \emptyset$, which corresponds to the complement of the existence problem for stable semantics, which has been shown to be NP-complete (Dvorák and Dunne, 2018). Hence, the complement can be decided in coNP. The further conditions amount to only polynomial time checks. Consequently, the problem of deciding local expansion equivalence wrt. stable semantics is in coNP. \square

Proposition 6.3.

1. EQ_{σ}^{wn} is coNP-complete, for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{st}\}$.
2. EQ_{σ}^{wn} is in P, for $\sigma \in \{\text{sa}, \text{gr}\}$.
3. $EQ_{\text{pr}}^{\text{wn}}$ is Π_2^P -complete.

Proof. To recall, we have $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{G}$ for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{st}, \text{sa}, \text{gr}, \text{pr}\}$ iff $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$, $\sigma(\mathcal{F}) = \sigma(\mathcal{G})$, and $E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}}^{\pm} = E \cup E_{\mathcal{G}}^{\pm}$ for all $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$, see (Baumann and Brewka, 2018) and Propositions 3.7 and 3.8.

1. $\text{EQ}_\sigma^{\text{wn}}$ is **coNP**-complete, for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{st}\}$:

We first show that $\text{coEQ}_\sigma^{\text{wn}}$, which asks whether $\mathcal{F} \not\equiv_\sigma^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{G}$ does not hold, is in **NP**. For that we consider the following non-deterministic algorithm

- (a) If $\mathcal{A}_\mathcal{F} \neq \mathcal{A}_\mathcal{G}$ return YES
- (b) Non-deterministically guess $E \subseteq \mathcal{A}_\mathcal{F}$
- (c) If $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ and $E \notin \sigma(\mathcal{G})$ return YES
- (d) If $E \notin \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ and $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{G})$ return YES
- (e) If $E \cup E_\mathcal{F}^+ \neq E \cup E_\mathcal{G}^+$ return YES
- (f) Return NO

Lines 3 and 4 can be executed in polynomial time for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{st}\}$ since the verification problems of these semantics can be solved in polynomial time. It should then be clear that the above algorithm solves $\text{coEQ}_\sigma^{\text{wn}}$ in non-deterministic polynomial time, so $\text{EQ}_\sigma^{\text{wn}}$ is in **coNP** (for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{st}\}$).

For **coNP**-hardness, we use the complementary problem of deciding credulous acceptance wrt. σ , coCRED_σ , so deciding whether a given argument \mathbf{a} is *not* contained in any σ -extension of a given \mathcal{F} , which is **coNP**-complete. Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ and $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}$ be an instance of coCRED_σ and assume $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \notin \mathcal{R}_\mathcal{F}$ (in this case the answer to coCRED_σ is trivially YES). Define $\mathcal{F}' = (\mathcal{A}', \mathcal{R}')$ via

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{A}' &= \mathcal{A}_\mathcal{F} \\ \mathcal{R}' &= \mathcal{R}_\mathcal{F} \cup \{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a})\}\end{aligned}$$

We claim that \mathbf{a} is not contained in any σ -extension of \mathcal{F} iff $\mathcal{F} \equiv_\sigma^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{F}'$.

- “ \Rightarrow ”: Assume that \mathbf{a} is not contained in any σ -extension. In order to show $\mathcal{F} \equiv_\sigma^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{F}'$ we check the conditions from above:
 - $\mathcal{A}_\mathcal{F} = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}'}$ follows by definition of \mathcal{F}' .
 - $\sigma(\mathcal{F}) = \sigma(\mathcal{F}')$: Let $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$. Since $\mathbf{a} \notin E$ by assumption, E is conflict-free in \mathcal{F}' . Moreover, as E is admissible in \mathcal{F} , it is also admissible in \mathcal{F}' since all attacks are already defended in \mathcal{F} and no new attack has been added. The same reasoning applies to $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{st}\}$. For the other direction, for all $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F}')$ we have $\mathbf{a} \notin E$ as E is conflict-free. Then E is also admissible (complete, stable) in \mathcal{F} as well. This shows $\sigma(\mathcal{F}) = \sigma(\mathcal{F}')$.

- $E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}}^+ = E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}'}^+$ for all $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$: Observe that for any E with $\mathbf{a} \notin E$, we have $E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}}^+ = E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}'}^+$, since \mathcal{R}' and $\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}}$ only differ in the attack (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) .
 - “ \Leftarrow ”: Since $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{R}'$, the argument \mathbf{a} cannot be in any σ -extension of \mathcal{F}' . Due to $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\sigma}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{F}'$, \mathbf{a} cannot be in any σ -extension of \mathcal{F} .
2. $\text{EQ}_{\sigma}^{\text{wn}}$ is in P , for $\sigma \in \{\text{sa}, \text{gr}\}$:
- For grounded semantics, we can check in polynomial time whether $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$, $\sigma(\mathcal{F}) = \sigma(\mathcal{G})$, and $E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}}^+ = E \cup E_{\mathcal{G}}^+$ for all $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ holds (since there is only one grounded extension and it can be computed in polynomial time).
- For strong admissibility, verifying that $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{sa}(\mathcal{G})$ holds can be done in polynomial time, cf. Proposition 6.1. Moreover, for checking $E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}}^+ = E \cup E_{\mathcal{G}}^+$ for all $E \in \text{sa}(\mathcal{F})$, we can slightly modify the approach used in Proposition 6.1. For each AF,
- (1) Compute the grounded extension E_{gr} and let $\Sigma = E_{\text{gr}} \cup (E_{\text{gr}})_{\mathcal{F}}^+$ be a propositional signature.
 - (2) For each $\mathbf{a} \in E_{\text{gr}}$ and every attacker $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbf{a}^-$, let $\mathbf{b}_1, \dots, \mathbf{b}_n \in \mathbf{b}^- \cap (E_{\text{gr}} \setminus \{\mathbf{a}\})$ be the defenders of \mathbf{a} against \mathbf{b} in E_{gr} .
 - (2.1) Construct the Horn clause: $\mathbf{a} \rightarrow \mathbf{b}_1 \vee \dots \vee \mathbf{b}_n$. The intuition behind that is, if \mathbf{a} is in some strongly admissible set E (and therefore in $E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}}^+$), then at least one of its defenders $\mathbf{b}_1, \dots, \mathbf{b}_n$ must be contained in E (and therefore in $E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}}^+$) as well.
 - (3) For each $\mathbf{a} \in E_{\text{gr}}$ and $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbf{a}_{\mathcal{F}}^+$ construct the Horn clause $\mathbf{a} \rightarrow \mathbf{b}$ with the intuition that, if \mathbf{a} is in some strongly admissible set E (and therefore in $E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}}^+$), then the argument \mathbf{b} attacked by \mathbf{a} must be in $E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}}^+$ as well.
 - (4) Let $K'_{\mathcal{F}}$ be the set of all these clauses for the AF \mathcal{F} , and $K'_{\mathcal{G}}$ is the corresponding set for the AF \mathcal{G} .

Since we already know that $\text{sa}(\mathcal{F}) = \text{sa}(\mathcal{G})$ holds, the above test ensures $E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}}^+ = E \cup E_{\mathcal{G}}^+$ for all $E \in \text{sa}(\mathcal{F})$ (with an analogous argumentation as in the proof of Proposition 6.1). It follows that $\text{EQ}_{\text{sa}}^{\text{wn}}$ is in P .

3. $\text{EQ}_{\text{pr}}^{\text{wn}}$ is Π_2^{P} -complete:
 Π_2^{P} -membership is analogous to the coNP -membership proof in 1 above. For hardness, we reduce from the problem of skeptical acceptance wrt. preferred semantics, i. e., so deciding whether a given argument \mathbf{a} is

contained in all preferred extensions of a given \mathcal{F} , which is Π_2^P -complete. Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ and $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}$ be an instance of that problem. Define $\mathcal{F}_1 = (\mathcal{A}_1, \mathcal{R}_1)$ and $\mathcal{F}_2 = (\mathcal{A}_2, \mathcal{R}_2)$ via (let x, y be fresh arguments)

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{A}_1 &= \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cup \{x, y\} \\ \mathcal{R}_1 &= \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}} \cup \{(\mathbf{a}, x), (x, y)\} \\ \mathcal{A}_2 &= \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cup \{x, y\} \\ \mathcal{R}_2 &= \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{F}} \cup \{(\mathbf{a}, x)\}\end{aligned}$$

We claim that \mathbf{a} is skeptically accepted wrt. preferred semantics in \mathcal{F} iff $\mathcal{F}_1 \equiv_{\text{pr}}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{F}_2$.

- “ \Rightarrow ”: Assume that \mathbf{a} is skeptically accepted wrt. preferred semantics in \mathcal{F} . In order to show $\mathcal{F}_1 \equiv_{\text{pr}}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{F}_2$ we check the conditions from above:
 - $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}_1} = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}_2}$ follows by definition of \mathcal{F}_1 and \mathcal{F}_2 .
 - $\text{pr}(\mathcal{F}_1) = \text{pr}(\mathcal{F}_2)$: Observe that

$$\text{pr}(\mathcal{F}_1) = \{E \cup \{y\} \mid E \in \text{pr}(\mathcal{F})\}$$

since $\mathbf{a} \in E$ for each $E \in \text{pr}(\mathcal{F})$ and $E \cup \{y\}$ is therefore admissible. Furthermore

$$\text{pr}(\mathcal{F}_2) = \{E \cup \{y\} \mid E \in \text{pr}(\mathcal{F})\}$$

as well, since y is unattacked in $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}_2}$ and therefore an element of every preferred extension.

- $E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}_1}^+ = E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}_2}^+$ for all $E \in \text{pr}(\mathcal{F}_2)$: We have $E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}_1}^+ = E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}}^+ \cup \{x, y\} = E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}_2}^+$ for all $E \in \text{pr}(\mathcal{F}_2)$.
- “ \Leftarrow ”: Let $\mathcal{F}_1 \equiv_{\text{pr}}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{F}_2$. Since y is unattacked in \mathcal{F}_2 it is necessarily contained in every preferred extension of \mathcal{F}_2 . Due to $\mathcal{F}_1 \equiv_{\text{pr}}^{\text{wn}} \mathcal{F}_2$, it follows that \mathbf{a} is contained in every preferred extension of \mathcal{F}_2 . This can only be if \mathbf{a} is contained in every preferred extension of \mathcal{F}_1 since \mathbf{a} is the only defender of y against x . It follows that \mathbf{a} is contained in every preferred extension of \mathcal{F} . \square

Proposition 6.4.

1. EQ_{σ}^u is in L .

2. EQ_σ^d is in L .
3. EQ_σ^{ld} is in L .
4. EQ_σ^{nd} is in P .

Proof. Items (1) to (3) follow trivially from the fact that these equivalence notions coincide with syntactical equivalence for all semantics, which can be verified in polynomial time with logarithmic space.

Regarding item (4), note first that in the case of stable semantics, this follows directly from Baumann (2014a); Baumann et al. (2019). In particular, normal deletion equivalence coincides with strong equivalence for stable semantics, which can be decided in polynomial time. For the remaining semantics, we consider the semantics based on their characterisations from Propositions 3.12 and 3.13. Both characterisations require that the syntactic conditions $Loop(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$ and $Att^{co}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$ (resp. $Att^{ad}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G})$) are satisfied. Clearly, these can be verified in polynomial time. The equivalence of the two $\mathfrak{a}\kappa^*$ -kernels of the restrictions $\mathcal{F}|_I$ and $\mathcal{G}|_I$ on the shared arguments $I = \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{F}} \cap \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{G}}$ can also be checked in polynomial time, cf. proof of Proposition 6.2. \square

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